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AI-Enabled Non-Invasive Smart Metering for Appliance-Level Energy Intelligence in Buildings

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Abstract—The increasing demand for energy-efficient and AI-driven building management systems requires detailed visibility of appliance-level consumption without introducing intrusive instrumentation. This paper presents an AI-enabled non-invasive smart metering platform designed to support appliance-level energy intelligence using mid-frequency measurements. The proposed system utilizes split-core current transformers and achieves measurement accuracy within $\pm 1\%$ while sampling electrical parameters at 50 ms intervals (20 Hz). A modular architecture combining MQTT-based real-time streaming, event-assisted steady-state feature extraction, and supervised classification enables near real-time Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring (NILM).

The system was experimentally validated under controlled laboratory conditions at the University Science Park TECHNICO using a calibrated Portable Test Equipment as a reference instrument. Experimental results demonstrate high classification accuracy for common household appliances, particularly resistive loads, while maintaining computational efficiency suitable for embedded deployment. The study confirms that 20 Hz sampling provides a practical compromise between billing-grade smart meters and high-frequency research systems.

The proposed architecture forms a scalable foundation for AI-driven building applications, including nearly real-time management and dynamic energy control, while highlighting limitations related to load density and overlapping appliance signatures.

Index Terms—Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring (NILM), Smart Metering, Appliance-Level Energy Disaggregation, Artificial Intelligence, Smart Buildings

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing energy demand in residential and commercial buildings has intensified the need for intelligent energy management solutions. Buildings account for a significant portion of global electricity consumption, making them a primary target for sustainability strategies and carbon reduction policies. Recent advances in artificial intelligence (AI) have enabled the development of AI-driven buildings, where energy consumption is continuously monitored, analyzed, and optimized to achieve dynamic energy efficiency control.

A fundamental requirement for AI-based energy optimization is detailed visibility of appliance-level consumption. Traditional smart metering systems typically provide aggregated energy data at low sampling rates (e.g., 1 Hz or lower), which is insufficient for accurate identification of individual loads. While plug-level monitoring offers high granularity, it

increases installation complexity, cost, and maintenance effort, limiting scalability in real-world deployments.

Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring (NILM) has emerged as a promising solution to address this challenge. NILM aims to disaggregate the total electrical load measured at a single point into its appliance-level components. By analyzing variations in voltage and current signals, AI-based algorithms can identify operational states of individual appliances without requiring dedicated sensors for each device. However, the effectiveness of NILM strongly depends on the quality, resolution, and reliability of the measurement infrastructure. High-frequency measurement systems provide detailed transient information but are costly and computationally demanding while compared to low-frequency smart meters that often fail to capture sufficient features for accurate load disaggregation.

Within this paper we address the gap by presenting an AI-enabled non-invasive smart metering platform designed specifically to support appliance-level energy intelligence in buildings. The proposed system utilizes split-core current transformers for safe and non-intrusive installation, achieving measurement accuracy within $\pm 1\%$. The platform samples electrical parameters at 50 ms intervals (20 Hz), providing a balanced trade-off between feature richness and data efficiency. Measured data are transmitted in real time via the MQTT protocol, enabling integration with AI-based analytics and building energy management systems.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Existing Technological Solutions

Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) has become a fundamental component of modern power systems, enabling automated meter reading, bidirectional communication, and interval-based consumption profiling. Smart meters deployed within AMI frameworks are primarily designed for billing, grid monitoring, and demand response applications [1]. These devices typically record aggregated active energy consumption over predefined integration windows, most commonly 15-minute intervals, although some configurations allow 1-minute resolution depending on regulatory and operational requirements [2].

While interval data significantly improves visibility compared to traditional electromechanical meters, the temporal

granularity remains limited for high-resolution energy analytics. Research on smart meter data analytics indicates that most large-scale deployments rely on low-frequency aggregated measurements, constraining their applicability for detecting short-duration load events [3]. Appliance switching operations, such as motor startups or resistive load activation, typically occur within timeframes of hundreds of milliseconds to a few seconds. Such transient behaviors are averaged out in 15-minute or even 1-minute load profiles, making conventional billing meters unsuitable for appliance-level identification.

From a metrological perspective, smart meters are designed according to standardized accuracy classes defined in international standards such as IEC 62053 and EN 50470, which ensure reliable long-term energy measurement for billing purposes [4]. These standards focus on steady-state accuracy and compliance testing but do not impose requirements on high-frequency waveform acquisition or transient signal capture. Consequently, billing-grade meters prioritize measurement stability and regulatory compliance over temporal resolution.

To overcome these limitations, several approaches have been proposed in both academia and industry. Research efforts have focused on improving load disaggregation through the use of high-resolution datasets such as UK-DALE [5] and advanced algorithms including particle filtering techniques [6].

In parallel, commercial intelligent energy monitoring systems such as Sense and Smappee utilize non-invasive current transformers combined with proprietary algorithms and cloud-based analytics to estimate appliance-level consumption from a single measurement point. Although these systems demonstrate the feasibility of practical NILM deployment, they are typically closed-source, vendor-specific platforms with limited transparency regarding signal processing methodologies and performance validation.

Research-oriented measurement platforms and high-frequency acquisition systems have been developed to support advanced load disaggregation studies. These systems often operate at sampling frequencies ranging from 1 Hz to several kilohertz, enabling detailed transient analysis but increasing hardware complexity, storage demands, and computational requirements [7]. Such solutions may not be economically or operationally suitable for large-scale deployment in residential or commercial buildings.

In summary, existing technological solutions can be categorized into: (i) utility-grade smart meters optimized for aggregated billing data, (ii) proprietary commercial NILM-enabled monitors, and (iii) high-frequency research measurement platforms. Utility-grade meters lack sufficient temporal resolution for reliable appliance recognition, while high-frequency research systems introduce increased complexity and cost. This gap motivates the development of a non-invasive, accurate, mid-frequency smart metering platform specifically designed to support appliance-level energy intelligence in AI-driven buildings.

B. NILM Techniques

Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring (NILM) was first introduced by Hart in 1992 as a method for disaggregating appliance-level consumption from aggregate electrical measurements obtained at a single point of connection [8]. The fundamental principle of NILM is that individual appliances exhibit distinguishable electrical signatures that can be detected when they switch states. Hart's original approach was event-based and relied on detecting step changes in real and reactive power to infer appliance activation and deactivation events.

Mathematically, the aggregated power signal can be expressed as

$$P(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N P_i(t) + \epsilon(t), \quad (1)$$

where $P(t)$ represents the measured total active power, $P_i(t)$ denotes the contribution of the i -th appliance, N is the number of appliances, and $\epsilon(t)$ represents measurement noise and modeling error. The objective of NILM is to estimate $\hat{P}_i(t)$ for each appliance given only the aggregated signal $P(t)$.

A. Event-Based and Steady-State Approaches: Event-based NILM methods detect abrupt changes in aggregate power, typically using thresholding on ΔP :

$$\Delta P(t) = P(t) - P(t - \Delta t). \quad (2)$$

When $|\Delta P(t)|$ exceeds a predefined threshold, a switching event is assumed to have occurred. Detected events are then matched to known appliance signatures using clustering or pattern recognition techniques [8]. These approaches are computationally efficient and well suited for moderate sampling rates; however, they may struggle with overlapping events and multi-state appliances.

Steady-state methods analyze stable operating regions of appliances, using features such as active power, reactive power, RMS current, and power factor [9]. These methods typically require segmentation of the aggregated signal into stationary intervals before classification.

In contrast, transient-based NILM techniques exploit high-frequency waveform characteristics captured during appliance startup or switching transitions [10]. Such approaches rely on short-duration transient signatures, often requiring sampling rates in the kHz range. Although transient analysis improves discrimination between similar steady-state loads, it significantly increases hardware and data processing requirements.

B. Machine Learning Approaches: With the increasing availability of smart meter data, NILM research has progressively shifted toward supervised machine learning methods. These approaches treat load disaggregation as a classification or regression problem, where extracted features form a vector

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = [P(t), Q(t), I_{\text{RMS}}(t), \cos \phi(t), \dots], \quad (3)$$

which is used to estimate appliance states.

The k -Nearest Neighbors (kNN) classifier assigns appliance labels based on proximity in feature space [11]. Support Vector

Machines (SVM) construct optimal separating hyperplanes to distinguish between appliance classes, often providing improved generalization performance in high-dimensional feature spaces [12]. These traditional machine learning approaches are effective when discriminative features are carefully engineered but may require extensive feature selection and preprocessing.

C. Deep Learning-Based NILM: Recent advances in deep learning have significantly influenced NILM research. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been successfully applied to learn hierarchical features directly from raw or minimally processed power signals [13]. Instead of explicit feature engineering, CNN-based architectures model NILM as a sequence-to-sequence or sequence-to-point learning problem, estimating appliance power consumption directly from aggregated input windows [14].

Given an input window $\mathbf{P}_{t:t+T}$ of aggregated power measurements, a neural network learns a nonlinear mapping

$$\hat{P}_i(t) = f_{\theta}(\mathbf{P}_{t:t+T}), \quad (4)$$

where f_{θ} represents the parameterized neural network and θ denotes its learned weights. Deep architectures generally outperform traditional approaches in complex scenarios involving multi-state and overlapping loads; however, they require substantial labeled training data and computational resources [15].

In summary, NILM techniques range from classical event-based methods to advanced deep learning architectures. Event-based and steady-state approaches are computationally efficient and compatible with moderate sampling frequencies, while transient-based and deep learning methods benefit from higher-resolution data. The selection of methodology is therefore closely linked to the characteristics of the measurement infrastructure, particularly sampling rate and signal fidelity.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

This section details the architectural framework of the proposed system, including the measurement and processing blocks, the selected sampling strategy, and the communication infrastructure. Together, these components form the foundation for reliable data acquisition, real-time NILM processing, and integration with AI-driven building management systems.

A. Block Diagram

The proposed system architecture is designed to support real-time appliance-level energy intelligence in buildings. It follows a layered structure separating measurement, communication, processing, and application functionalities. The overall architecture is illustrated conceptually in Fig. 1.

The architecture consists of the following main components:

1. *Measurement Layer:* The Measurement Layer includes non-invasive split-core current transformers (CTs), signal conditioning circuitry, and an embedded data acquisition unit. Electrical quantities such as RMS current and active power are sampled at 50 ms intervals (20 Hz). This layer ensures metrological accuracy within $\pm 1\%$ and provides temporally fine-grained measurements suitable for event detection.

Fig. 1. Proposed system architecture for AI-enabled smart metering and NILM processing.

2. *Data Acquisition and Streaming Layer:* Measured samples are timestamped and transmitted using the MQTT protocol. The embedded firmware performs primary preprocessing, including RMS computation and noise filtering. The MQTT-based communication ensures lightweight, low-latency streaming compatible with IoT infrastructures and building management systems.

3. *Storage Layer:* Two storage mechanisms are implemented:

- **Time-Series Database:** Stores aggregated measurements and recognized appliance activity for historical analysis.
- **Pattern Database:** Maintains labeled appliance signatures used for training and validation of classification models.

This separation enables independent management of raw measurement data and learned appliance patterns.

4. *Processing and Intelligence Layer:* The Processing Layer performs load disaggregation and pattern recognition. It consists of three functional modules:

- **Event Detection and Feature Extraction Module:** Detects significant changes in aggregate power and computes feature vectors for classification.
- **Pattern Repository:** Stores extracted appliance signatures and learned feature patterns for supervised training and incremental refinement.
- **Real-Time Classification Engine:** Performs in-buffer recognition using sliding windows of incoming samples to identify appliance states in near real time.

The in-buffer recognition mechanism processes a finite window of recent measurements

$$\mathbf{P}_{t:t+T} = \{P(t), P(t + \Delta t), \dots, P(t + T)\}$$

and outputs predicted appliance activity before storing results in the time-series database.

5. *Application Layer:* The Application Layer provides user interaction and visualization functionalities. It includes:

- **Pattern Labeling Interface:** Allows users to assign semantic labels to detected appliance signatures during supervised training.
- **Visualization Dashboard:** Displays real-time and historical appliance activity, enabling energy monitoring and behavioral analysis.

This layer supports integration with building energy management systems and enables AI-driven energy optimization strategies.

Overall, the proposed architecture enables a complete workflow from non-invasive measurement to real-time appliance recognition and visualization. The modular design supports scalability and allows independent improvement of sensing, communication, and intelligence components.

B. Sampling Strategy

The sampling strategy of the proposed smart metering platform is designed to balance temporal resolution, data volume, and computational feasibility. The system operates with a fixed sampling interval of 50 ms, corresponding to a sampling frequency of 20 Hz. This mid-frequency approach is selected to provide sufficient temporal granularity for appliance event detection while avoiding the complexity of high-frequency waveform acquisition.

Conventional utility-grade smart meters typically provide aggregated measurements over 1-minute or 15-minute intervals, which are insufficient for capturing short-duration switching events. Appliance activation, particularly for resistive loads and motor-driven equipment, often produces detectable power variations within timeframes of several hundred milliseconds to a few seconds. If the sampling interval Δt is significantly larger than the event duration τ_e , i.e.,

$$\Delta t \gg \tau_e, \quad (5)$$

the transient signature becomes averaged within the integration window, reducing its detectability. By selecting $\Delta t = 50$ ms, the system ensures that typical appliance switching events are represented by multiple consecutive samples, improving event localization and feature extraction reliability.

From a signal representation perspective, the aggregated power signal can be considered a discrete-time sequence:

$$P[n] = P(n\Delta t), \quad (6)$$

where $\Delta t = 50$ ms. At 20 Hz, a one-second interval contains 20 samples, which is sufficient to characterize steady-state transitions and short-duration load variations without requiring kHz-level waveform capture.

Compared to high-frequency transient-based NILM systems operating in the kHz range, the proposed sampling strategy significantly reduces data throughput and storage requirements. The approximate data rate R can be expressed as:

$$R = f_s \cdot S, \quad (7)$$

where f_s is the sampling frequency and S is the size of a single measurement record. Reducing f_s from 1 kHz to 20 Hz lowers the raw data rate by a factor of 50, directly impacting communication bandwidth, storage footprint, and processing load.

The selected sampling frequency is therefore particularly suitable for event-based and steady-state NILM techniques,

which rely primarily on changes in aggregated active power rather than high-frequency transient waveforms. Furthermore, the 20 Hz resolution supports near real-time in-buffer recognition while maintaining compatibility with embedded and IoT-based deployment scenarios.

In summary, the adopted 50 ms sampling interval represents a compromise between low-resolution billing meters and high-frequency research-grade systems. It provides sufficient temporal detail for appliance-level energy intelligence while preserving scalability and computational efficiency in AI-driven building applications.

C. Communication Architecture

The communication architecture of the proposed system is designed to ensure scalable, low-latency, and modular data exchange between metering devices, processing services, and application interfaces. The overall structure is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Communication architecture of the proposed smart metering platform.

At the core of the architecture is the **Smart Meter**, which produces high-granularity electrical measurements at 50 ms intervals. The device publishes measurement records in near real time to a **Message Broker** using the MQTT protocol over TCP/IP. This publish–subscribe paradigm decouples data producers from consumers, enabling multiple services to subscribe to the same measurement stream without increasing device-side complexity.

The **Message Broker** acts as a central distribution node, ensuring reliable and asynchronous data delivery. From this point, multiple system components may subscribe to the measurement topics. Service-oriented processing modules perform preprocessing tasks such as filtering, feature extraction, and statistical aggregation before storing processed data in a **Time-Series/Relational Database**. This separation ensures that raw streaming data and structured historical records are managed independently.

The **Time-Series/Relational Database** stores aggregated samples, computed features, and recognized appliance activity. It serves as persistent storage for both analytical processing

and historical evaluation. Communication between services and the database is performed over TCP/IP using standardized database interfaces.

A dedicated **Backend** service provides an API layer that enables controlled access to stored measurements and processed results. This abstraction allows external applications to retrieve pre-analyzed samples without directly interacting with the database. The **Frontend** component represents the application layer described in the system architecture section, providing visualization of recognized appliances and historical consumption trends.

The **Mobile Application** is used primarily for device orchestration, configuration, and commissioning. It communicates with the smart meter via Bluetooth for local setup and via TCP/IP when accessing backend services. This dual communication path separates operational control from high-volume measurement streaming.

To ensure measurement reliability, a **Calibration Source** is incorporated into the architecture. The calibration device is connected at the same electrical point as the smart meter and communicates reference measurements via an RS485 interface to an MQTT forwarder. These reference data can be published to the same broker, enabling automated accuracy validation and comparative analysis under controlled conditions.

Overall, the communication architecture supports real-time streaming, modular processing, persistent storage, and scalable application access. The use of standardized communication protocols (MQTT, TCP/IP, RS485, Bluetooth) ensures interoperability and facilitates integration with AI-driven building management systems.

IV. NILM IMPLEMENTATION AND EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

This section presents the implementation of the proposed NILM framework and evaluates its performance under experimental conditions. First, the methodological formulation and classification approach are described. Subsequently, the experimental setup and obtained results are presented and discussed.

A. Methodology and Problem Formulation

The implemented NILM framework follows the aggregated load formulation introduced in (1). The objective is to estimate appliance operational states from discrete measurements obtained at 20 Hz, as defined by the selected sampling strategy.

The disaggregation task is formulated as a binary state estimation problem. The appliance state vector is defined as

$$\mathbf{s}[n] = [s_1[n], s_2[n], \dots, s_N[n]], \quad (8)$$

where $s_i[n] \in \{0, 1\}$ represents the OFF/ON state of appliance i at discrete time index n .

Switching events are detected using the power difference criterion defined in (2). When the threshold condition is satisfied, a candidate transition is identified and a short sliding window of samples is extracted for feature computation.

While the general feature representation is described in (3), the implemented system uses a reduced feature vector optimized for real-time processing:

$$\mathbf{x}[n] = [P_{\text{mean}}, P_{\text{std}}, \Delta P, I_{\text{RMS}}], \quad (9)$$

where statistical descriptors are computed within the detected event window.

Appliance classification is performed using a supervised k -Nearest Neighbors (kNN) classifier. During the training phase, labeled feature vectors are stored in the pattern repository. During runtime, incoming feature vectors are compared against stored patterns using Euclidean distance, and classification results are further validated through temporal consistency constraints to suppress spurious detections.

This implementation leverages the 20 Hz sampling resolution to reliably capture switching dynamics while maintaining computational efficiency suitable for embedded and IoT-based deployment.

B. Experimental Setup

The proposed architecture was experimentally validated under controlled laboratory conditions at the University Science Park TECHNICOM. The deployment included the developed MeriTO BASE smart meter and a Portable Test Equipment (PTE) unit provided by Applied Meters, which served as a calibrated reference instrument.

The MeriTO BASE device was installed using non-invasive split-core current transformers at the same measurement point as the PTE system to enable direct comparison of recorded electrical quantities. The PTE system provided high-accuracy reference measurements for verification of active power and RMS current values. The laboratory setup is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Laboratory deployment of MeriTO BASE (CEELABS) smart meter and Portable Test Equipment (Applied Meters) used for calibration and validation.

Several household appliances were operated individually and in overlapping scenarios to generate representative load

profiles. The evaluated appliances included a heating kettle (resistive load), toaster (short-duration resistive load), washing machine (multi-stage motor load), and tumble dryer. Each appliance was activated multiple times to capture steady-state operation as well as switching events.

Aggregated power measurements were recorded at 50 ms resolution and streamed through the MQTT-based architecture. A representative example of the recorded aggregated signal and corresponding appliance-level annotation is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Example of aggregated power measurements and annotated appliance activity during laboratory experiments.

Ground truth labels were generated based on controlled activation timing and validated against reference measurements from the PTE system. The resulting dataset was used for training and validating the implemented NILM classifier.

C. Results and Discussion

The measurement accuracy of the MeriTO BASE smart meter was evaluated against the Portable Test Equipment (PTE) reference instrument. Comparative measurements confirmed that the developed system achieved an active power accuracy within $\pm 1\%$, validating the suitability of the platform for NILM applications.

The implemented kNN-based NILM classifier was evaluated using the labeled laboratory dataset described in the previous subsection. For single-appliance activation scenarios, the system achieved high recognition performance, particularly for resistive loads such as the heating kettle and toaster, which exhibit distinct steady-state power levels. Motor-driven appliances, such as the washing machine, were correctly identified during dominant operational phases, although minor misclassifications occurred during transitional states.

Table I summarizes representative classification results obtained during controlled experiments.

The results confirm that a 20 Hz sampling frequency provides sufficient temporal resolution for reliable event detection and steady-state classification in small-scale environments. The event-assisted steady-state approach proved computationally efficient while maintaining near real-time recognition capability.

TABLE I
REPRESENTATIVE NILM CLASSIFICATION PERFORMANCE

Appliance	Accuracy	F1-score
Kettle	98%	0.97
Toaster	96%	0.95
Washing machine	92%	0.90
Tumble dryer	94%	0.92

However, scalability represents an inherent limitation of mid-frequency NILM systems. As the number of simultaneously operating appliances increases, particularly when devices exhibit similar steady-state power characteristics, distinguishing individual contributions becomes more challenging. Overlapping loads and multi-state appliances introduce ambiguity in feature space, which can reduce classification accuracy.

In the conducted experiments, the system demonstrated very good performance in environments comparable to a single room or small office setting. As infrastructure density grows, more advanced feature representations or hybrid classification methods may be required to maintain discrimination capability.

Overall, the proposed architecture demonstrates that non-invasive mid-frequency smart metering can effectively support appliance-level energy intelligence in controlled building environments, forming a practical foundation for AI-driven energy efficiency strategies.

It is important to note that the experimental evaluation was conducted using a limited set of appliance types. While these appliances provide a useful baseline for validating the proposed approach, they do not fully capture the diversity and variability of real-world electrical devices.

In practical deployments, buildings typically contain a significantly larger number of appliances with heterogeneous characteristics, including multi-state devices, nonlinear loads, and electronically controlled systems. The limited appliance set may therefore lead to optimistic performance estimates, particularly in scenarios with low load diversity and minimal overlap. Consequently, the generalization of the presented results to more complex environments should be interpreted with caution.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented an AI-enabled non-invasive smart metering platform designed to support appliance-level energy intelligence in buildings. The proposed solution addresses the gap between low-resolution billing smart meters and high-frequency research-grade measurement systems by adopting a mid-frequency sampling strategy of 20 Hz. The developed MeriTO BASE device, combined with a modular MQTT-based communication architecture, enables reliable real-time data acquisition and scalable integration into building management infrastructures.

Experimental validation performed at the University Science Park TECHNICOM confirmed that the system achieves measurement accuracy within $\pm 1\%$ when compared to calibrated reference instrumentation. The implemented event-assisted

steady-state NILM methodology demonstrated high recognition performance for common household appliances under controlled laboratory conditions. Resistive loads exhibited particularly strong classification accuracy due to distinct steady-state characteristics, while motor-driven appliances were correctly identified during dominant operational phases.

The results indicate that 20 Hz sampling provides sufficient temporal resolution to capture switching events without incurring the complexity and data overhead associated with kHz-level acquisition systems. This balance between temporal granularity and computational efficiency makes the proposed architecture suitable for embedded and IoT-based deployment scenarios. Furthermore, the modular separation of sensing, processing, storage, and application layers ensures extensibility and compatibility with AI-driven analytics frameworks.

However, the study also highlights inherent limitations of mid-frequency NILM systems. As the number of simultaneously operating appliances increases, particularly when devices exhibit similar steady-state power levels, classification ambiguity becomes more pronounced. In environments with high infrastructure density, more advanced feature representations or hybrid machine learning approaches may be required to preserve discrimination capability.

Despite these limitations, the presented platform demonstrates that non-invasive smart metering can effectively support appliance-level monitoring in environments comparable to a single room or small office. Such granularity is sufficient for a wide range of AI-driven building applications, including anomaly detection, occupancy inference, behavioral analysis, and demand-side energy optimization.

Future work will focus on extending the system toward larger-scale deployments and incorporating advanced machine learning methodologies inspired by recent developments in state-of-the-art artificial intelligence research. In particular, the integration of deep sequence models, attention-based architectures, and self-supervised representation learning may enhance the system's capability to discriminate overlapping and multi-state appliance behaviors. Exploring hybrid architectures that combine physics-informed modeling with data-driven approaches represents another promising direction. Furthermore, the incorporation of adaptive and continual learning mechanisms could enable long-term deployment in dynamic building environments without requiring extensive retraining. These research directions position the proposed platform not only as a practical engineering solution but also as a foundation for further exploration within the broader AI research community. Ultimately, the presented work contributes to the advancement of sustainable, AI-driven energy management systems capable of supporting next-generation intelligent buildings.

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The role and potential applications of video technology combined with advanced image processing methods in waste sorting

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Abstract—This paper focuses on the application of video-analytical systems supported by artificial intelligence with the aim of improving the quality of source-separated municipal solid waste across the entire waste management chain. Contamination and improper sorting significantly reduce recycling efficiency and the value of secondary raw materials. Although advanced detection technologies are already employed at sorting facilities, the study extends this concept to earlier stages of the chain, including mobile applications for waste producers, monitoring at collection points, and camera systems integrated into waste collection vehicles. The proposed framework demonstrates how computer vision and AI-based evaluation can enable real-time detection of sorting errors, identification of contamination, and the generation of structured data for municipalities and waste collection companies. Emphasis is placed on preventive and educational measures complemented by data-driven feedback and incentive mechanisms. The integrated deployment of computer vision has the potential to reduce contamination rates, enhance recycling efficiency, optimize operational processes, and support transparent, data-driven municipal waste management within the transition toward a circular economy.

Keywords—Computer vision; Video-analytical system; Waste sorting; Municipal waste management; Contamination monitoring; User engagement

I. INTRODUCTION

Efficient municipal solid waste management is essential for the transition toward a circular economy, while the quality of separate collection fundamentally determines recycling performance. In practice, separately collected waste is often contaminated or incorrectly classified, which reduces the quality of secondary raw materials and limits their recycling potential [1]. This issue is also evident in Slovakia, where, despite the target of exceeding a 55% recycling rate by 2025, the actual rate reached only approximately 43.7% in 2020, highlighting persistent deficiencies in collection and sorting systems [2]. Between waste generation and its processing at sorting lines, a complex chain of processes takes place, beginning at the point of waste generation—households, commercial entities, and public spaces—and continuing

through separate collection, transportation, sorting, treatment, and subsequent recycling or other recovery operations [1, 3].

Computer vision is already applied on sorting lines, where deep learning-based image recognition methods enable automatic classification of recyclable waste material types, identification of visually challenging materials, and detection of contamination in the sorting process [4]. Beyond sorting facilities, computer vision can be deployed at multiple stages of the sorting chain, where, in combination with AI-based evaluation, it enables continuous assessment of waste quality, identification of contamination, and detection of systemic issues. This article focuses on the potential application of computer vision within the waste sorting process with the objective of improving overall sorting quality. Advanced detection technologies and computer vision applied on sorting lines already provide effective detection and sorting capabilities. The possibilities of using computer vision in the remaining, preceding parts of the separate waste collection and sorting chain are a less explored and relatively complex problem, which this article will focus on.

II. MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE FLOW AND PROCESS CHAIN

Building on the discussion of the quality of source separated waste and its impact on recycling efficiency, a more detailed analysis of the municipal solid waste flow within the waste management system is presented. The scheme illustrates a typical process chain of waste management, starting from waste generation at the source and continuing through subsequent stages until final material recovery or disposal. This chain consists of several consecutive steps, whose interconnections and operational quality fundamentally influence the overall level of material recovery and the environmental sustainability of the entire system.

The chain begins at the waste generator, represented by households, commercial entities, public institutions or residents. At this stage, basic source separation of waste into designated containers according to material fractions is carried out. The waste is subsequently accumulated at collection points and transported by specialized collection vehicles to facilities dedicated to waste recovery or treatment. The quality of the input material at this stage directly determines the

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technological complexity of downstream processes. Following transport, waste is processed in material recovery facilities, where it undergoes mechanical and sensor based sorting. As illustrated in the “Fig. 1.”, sorting lines equipped with conveyor belts and separation units enable the division of waste into individual material streams. Materially suitable fractions are subsequently directed to recycling plants, where they enter secondary production processes, while non recyclable residues are sent either to energy recovery facilities or to landfills [1]. This multi stage flow clearly demonstrates that failures or inefficiencies at any stage of the chain may lead to degradation of material value and increased environmental burden. From the perspective of modern waste management, it is therefore essential to consider the entire chain as an integrated system. In the context of sorting lines, advanced monitoring technologies, including computer vision, represent a promising approach for enhancing process transparency, optimizing material flows, and enabling early identification of quality related issues in source separated waste streams [4].

Fig. 1. Municipal Solid Waste Flow

III. MONITORING AND SUPPORT FOR IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF SEPARATED WASTE ACROSS INDIVIDUAL STAGES OF THE COLLECTION AND PROCESSING CHAIN

In relation to the aforementioned waste flow chain, it is necessary to highlight the problematic aspects that arise within this process. These issues primarily concern waste sorting and occur at every stage of the chain. They significantly affect the overall quality of waste separation. Therefore, improving the quality of separated waste requires the systematic elimination of identified risk factors at each stage of the process.

A. Waste producer - mobile application

The first shortcomings in waste separation emerge already at the level of the waste producer. At this initial stage, situations frequently occur in which producers fail to ensure correct waste sorting. Such problems often result either from insufficient knowledge of sorting principles or from a low level of motivation and interest in waste separation. As a

consequence, individuals may incorrectly allocate waste to collection containers, which leads to contamination of otherwise properly separated waste streams and negatively affects subsequent processing.

A typical example involves common packaging materials. Waste producers must determine the type of waste represented by a given packaging and decide how it should be properly sorted. If the producer lacks sufficient knowledge of packaging labels or sorting rules, but is willing to separate waste correctly, accessible and clearly understandable information becomes essential. This requirement applies not only to packaging but also to other types of discarded items.

The situation becomes more complex in the case of products composed of multiple materials. For instance, a yogurt container may consist of a plastic cup, a metal lid, and a paper sleeve. In such cases, proper sorting requires knowledge of whether the individual components should be separated before disposal. Moreover, sorting regulations may differ across cities or regions. For example, in the city of Trnava plastics, metals, and beverage cartons are collected in a single container, while in Žilina plastics and composite packaging are collected separately.

Another important factor concerns the availability and location of collection infrastructure. At the end of this stage, waste producers typically face two key questions: what type of waste they are dealing with and how it should be sorted, and where the waste should be disposed of, including the location of relevant collection points or civic amenity sites.

B. Waste collection point

The primary objective of this phase is to ensure the correct disposal of waste into appropriate collection containers while preventing contamination of both the collection site and separated waste fractions. Within this stage, two key problems can be identified: the incorrect placement of waste into unsuitable containers and the pollution of collection sites by waste deposited outside designated containers.

Improper sorting represents a major issue affecting separation quality. When waste is disposed of in the wrong container, contamination of otherwise properly separated fractions occurs. As a result, materials that were initially correctly sorted become degraded, creating complications for subsequent stages of the waste management chain, particularly during processing in sorting facilities.

The second problem concerns the pollution of collection sites. This typically arises when waste, often bulky or specific types that should be delivered to civic amenity sites, is left outside containers. Such situations may result from insufficient awareness of appropriate disposal options or from irresponsible disposal practices. Consequently, hygienic and environmental conditions at collection sites may deteriorate.

Two fundamental questions therefore arise: how to ensure correct waste disposal into appropriate containers and how to minimize the pollution of collection sites. These issues may be addressed through preventive and corrective measures. Waste producers can receive guidance or warnings when incorrect disposal is detected, while information about proper disposal procedures should be provided. In cases where the originator of improperly disposed waste can be reliably identified, sanctioning measures in accordance with applicable legislation may also be considered.

C. Waste collection vehicle

During the stage of waste collection by collection vehicles, the primary objective is to ensure quality control of collected fractions while optimizing the overall collection process. This phase directly builds upon the problems identified in the preceding stage. While contamination at the previous stage may occur at the level of a single container, during the collection process this issue may become significantly amplified. The collection of a contaminated container can degrade already collected and properly separated waste within the entire load, thereby reducing the quality of the collected fraction and complicating subsequent processing.

Particular attention must be paid to the so-called “white fraction”, which includes food residues, grease, oils, moist organic remains, biodegradable waste, and other undesirable impurities frequently present in plastic and paper fractions. These impurities substantially contribute to contamination and may limit or even prevent further processing in sorting facilities.

To address these challenges, the functionality of waste collection vehicles may be extended to include monitoring and quality control mechanisms during container emptying and vehicle movement. Such systems could assess the condition of collection sites, detect bulky waste in their vicinity, and evaluate the quality of separately collected waste directly at the point of collection. The recorded observations may subsequently serve as a basis for corrective actions, including operational adjustments, modifications to collection schedules, or structured feedback directed toward waste producers.

D. Waste sorting line

The final stage of the waste separation process is represented by sorting facilities, where the deficiencies arising in the preceding phases of the chain become most apparent. Insufficient sorting quality at the level of the waste producer, collection site, or collection process leads to the necessity of additional re-sorting, thereby increasing both the technological and labor demands of waste processing. In unfavorable cases, waste may be contaminated to such an extent that it cannot be transferred to a contractual off-taker for further material recovery. Such waste must subsequently be directed to landfill disposal, resulting in the loss of potential revenue from the sale of properly sorted recyclable materials. At the same time, additional costs are incurred in connection with the transportation and landfilling of waste, while landfill fees have shown a long-term upward trend. This situation therefore represents not only an environmental concern but also a significant economic burden for municipalities.

IV. CAPABILITIES OF COMPUTER VISION

Video-analytical systems deployed across the waste management chain follow a unified processing architecture. At each monitored location, cameras capture continuous image or video streams that are processed by embedded AI models. The system first performs object detection and/or segmentation to identify relevant waste items and contextual elements (e.g., containers, vehicle compartments, conveyor belts). Temporal tracking modules associate detections across frames to interpret events. A decision layer evaluates compliance with predefined sorting rules and generates structured metadata (e.g., type of waste, contamination level, event timestamp). Depending on the deployment scenario,

inference is executed locally on edge devices or partially in centralized infrastructure.

A. Image Understanding at the Source (Mobile Application)

Real-time object detection models from the YOLO family are widely adopted due to their favorable balance between accuracy and inference speed, making them suitable for deployment on mobile and edge devices [7]. Transformer-based detectors such as DETR and its real-time variants (e.g., RT-DETR) introduce an end-to-end detection paradigm that removes hand-crafted components such as anchor design and non-maximum suppression, improving contextual reasoning and robustness in cluttered scenes [8, 9].

For more detailed visual analysis, including multi-material packaging or partially occluded objects, Vision Transformers (ViT) enhance global feature modeling capabilities [10]. Pixel-level understanding becomes particularly relevant when evaluating contamination or separating visually overlapping materials. Foundation segmentation models such as Segment Anything (SAM) enable prompt-based object segmentation and can generalize to previously unseen object types without extensive retraining, increasing adaptability in municipal environments [11].

To integrate visual recognition with region-specific sorting regulations, multimodal Vision-Language Models (VLMs), such as CLIP-like architectures, allow semantic alignment between images and textual descriptions [12]. This enables the system not only to classify an item but also to generate context-aware explanations reflecting local sorting policies.

B. Video-Based Monitoring at Collection Points

At waste collection points, the video-analytical system operates as an event-detection pipeline in a dynamic and uncontrolled environment. The camera continuously captures the disposal area, and embedded AI models perform real-time object detection to identify both the waste item and the corresponding container. Temporal tracking modules associate detections across consecutive frames to confirm whether an actual disposal event occurred. A rule-based decision layer evaluates the compatibility between the detected waste type and container fraction. Based on this evaluation, the system may trigger immediate feedback and generate structured metadata for supervisory analysis.

Real-time object detection models such as YOLO-based architectures and transformer-based detectors are used to identify deposited waste items and container types [7, 14]. By combining object classification with spatial reasoning, the system evaluates sorting compliance in real time.

C. Contamination Assessment in Collection Vehicles

Within waste collection vehicles, the system performs pre-emptying quality assessment of containers. Cameras installed on the vehicle capture the container content immediately before lifting and emptying. The AI pipeline applies detection and segmentation models to identify material fractions and estimate their spatial distribution.

Transformer-based detectors such as RF-DETR extend the DETR paradigm toward high-accuracy real-time performance and are suitable for dense, heterogeneous container scenes [14]. Their global attention mechanisms improve robustness

when materials are partially occluded, compressed, or visually degraded.

For quantitative contamination assessment, instance and semantic segmentation architectures are required. Models such as Mask2Former enable unified multi-class segmentation within complex scenes [15]. Foundation segmentation models derived from the Segment Anything paradigm further allow flexible mask generation and adaptation to new packaging types without extensive retraining [11].

Inference is executed on embedded edge platforms installed directly in collection vehicles. Edge processing reduces latency, limits bandwidth requirements, and supports privacy-by-design principles by avoiding continuous transmission of raw video data. Model compression techniques such as quantization and pruning ensure real-time performance under constrained computational resources [13].

V. DEPLOYMENT POSSIBILITIES OF COMPUTER VISION AND ITS APPLICATION IN THE DETECTION OF IMPROPER WASTE SORTING

The entire waste management chain should be perceived as an integrated system in which advanced monitoring technologies, including computer vision, represent a promising tool for enhancing process transparency, optimizing material flows, and enabling the early identification of quality-related issues in source-separated waste. From a systemic perspective, computer vision can be implemented at multiple stages of waste collection and sorting. Its deployment may be considered at the level of the waste producer through a mobile application, at collection points, within municipal waste collection vehicles, or along sorting lines in material recovery facilities. Such an integrated approach enables continuous monitoring of waste flows and creates the preconditions for improving the quality of source separation and the efficiency of subsequent processing stages.

A. Mobile application

At the level of the waste producer, computer vision implemented through a mobile application can significantly reduce improper sorting before waste enters the collection system. Using a mobile device, the user captures an image of a product or its packaging. An image-based analytical system subsequently identifies the material type, considers its condition, and determines the appropriate waste fraction in accordance with local regulations. The output consists of a clear and unambiguous instruction accompanied by a brief explanation. In the initial stage of sorting, such a smartphone application would be capable of analysing the captured waste item, determining its material composition, and assessing the level of contamination. Based on this evaluation, the waste producer could make an informed decision at the primary stage of sorting, thereby ensuring higher-quality separation and minimizing contamination. The system could provide explicit instructions, for example: “Dispose of in plastics,” “Contaminated → mixed waste,” or “Lid into the yellow container, paper sleeve into the blue container.” In this form, the application would function as an educational assistant, supporting waste producers in understanding and correctly applying sorting principles. Additional functionalities could include saving frequently sorted products for future reference or informing the user about the nearest collection point. The added value of this solution lies in reducing error rates at the source, improving the quality of separated waste streams,

enabling the system to adapt and learn from user behaviour, and contributing to long-term educational and behavioural change in waste sorting practices.

Fig. 2. Deployment of Computer Vision in Mobile Applications

B. Waste collection point

The deployment of computer vision at collection points represents an effective instrument for improving the quality of source separation and preventing the pollution of public spaces. Through video monitoring, it is possible to assess the type of waste being deposited, the specific container into which the waste is disposed, the placement of waste outside designated containers, and, in certain cases, the waste producer as well as the number of individuals present at a given collection site. This approach enables the identification of potential contamination, improper use of containers, and deficiencies in users’ sorting practices. At the same time, it facilitates verification of compliance with established sorting regulations. The detection of the number of users may also serve as a basis for statistical analysis of collection point utilization. A significant limitation, however, remains the use of opaque waste bags, as their contents cannot be visually assessed, thereby preventing the detection of possible contamination or improper sorting. Following the capture and evaluation of improper disposal, either incorrect placement of waste into an inappropriate container or deposition of waste outside designated containers, an immediate real-time response may be initiated. Such a response could take the form of a notification delivered to the respective waste producer via a mobile device. Examples of such notifications include: “This waste does not belong in this container,” “Please place the waste into the appropriate container,” or “Please deliver this waste to a civic amenity site.” These notifications would be neutral, educational, and adaptively repeated when necessary.

The outputs generated through computer vision monitoring would also include records for supervisory authorities, enabling the identification of repeated contamination of specific fractions or frequent disposal of waste outside containers. Based on the collected data, it would be possible to generate statistics on collection point utilization, peak usage times, and common sorting errors. The added value of this approach lies in cleaner collection sites, a reduction in illegal dumping in the vicinity of containers, and the availability of structured, data-driven insights for municipal waste management.

C. Waste collection vehicle

The application of computer vision in waste collection vehicles is conceptually similar to its deployment at collection points. The key difference lies in the fact that its integration into collection vehicles enables systematic quality control of source-separated waste and optimization of the collection process itself. Camera systems installed on vehicles can capture the contents of containers prior to emptying, monitor the condition of collection sites, and, through artificial intelligence algorithms, assess contamination levels, the presence of unauthorized waste fractions, and the so-called

white fraction, such as food residues and organic contamination. In addition, AI systems may evaluate the condition of the collection site after waste collection has taken place.

The outputs generated by such systems can be divided into two main categories according to their intended use. The first category includes information directed to the waste collection company responsible for transporting waste from collection points. These data may take the form of labels or digital records linked to specific containers, indicating high contamination levels or repeated sorting deficiencies. Such information may support operational decision-making, including providing structured feedback to the respective municipality or, in extreme cases, refusing the collection of a contaminated container in accordance with applicable legislation. The second category comprises information intended for local authorities. Data obtained from collection vehicles may help identify and analyse problematic locations, including long-term trends in contamination or improper sorting. Processed in this way, the data may support adjustments to the collection system, infrastructure optimization, and the implementation of targeted communication strategies aimed at residents of specific localities. The overall added value of this approach lies in reducing the amount of degraded separated waste, strengthening transparency between municipalities and collection companies, and promoting a waste collection system focused not only on quantitative targets but also on qualitative performance.

D. Waste sorting line

The objective of sorting lines is to maximize the quality of output material fractions and to provide feedback to the overall waste management system. In this context, computer vision would be capable, at the initial stage of the sorting process, of analysing the composition of the delivered waste and identifying typical contaminants. Along the sorting line itself, the system could detect material misclassifications, thereby supporting automated re-sorting operations. The outputs would include detailed data on contamination levels according to waste origin, such as specific areas, collection types, and related parameters. In addition, recurrent sorting errors made by waste producers could be identified. Further outputs would consist of structured feedback directed to municipalities, waste collection companies, and potentially to the mobile application used by waste producers. The added value at this stage would lie in higher recycling efficiency and reduced costs associated with additional re-sorting. This phase would effectively close the data loop within the entire waste management system, enabling continuous improvement based on data-driven feedback.

VI. POSSIBLE APPROACHES TO INFORMING AND INFLUENCING THE WASTE PRODUCER

A. Technological Aspects of Implementation

The video-analytical system ensures secure storage of video records together with structured metadata (time, location, type of sorting error) and enables automated communication with the waste producer. Identification may operate at multiple levels—from basic authentication via access card or mobile application to advanced methods such as facial or vehicle license plate recognition. In cases of improper or intentional mis-sorting detected through AI-based video analysis, corrective measures are applied within a multi-

level framework primarily oriented toward education and positive motivation, with sanctions considered a last resort. The first level consists of real-time, anonymous educational notification enabling immediate behavioral correction. The second level provides personalized digital feedback explaining the error and its environmental implications. The third level introduces motivational incentives, such as point-based or financial rewards, to reinforce proper sorting behavior. Targeted sanctions are implemented only in cases of repeated or deliberate violations.

B. Legislative Frameworks

The application of video technologies in waste management does not rest solely on their technical feasibility, but equally on compliance with the applicable legal framework. Regulation in this context is not merely a formal layer superimposed on technological innovation; it can decisively shape and limit implementation. Insufficient legal assessment at the design stage may result in the inability to operate the system or in subsequent intervention and sanctions by supervisory authorities. Given the interdisciplinary nature of the issue, technical design and legal compliance must be considered in parallel rather than sequentially.

From a regulatory perspective, three interrelated dimensions can be identified: the system itself, the subjects involved in waste management, and the data processed through the deployment of video technologies. These dimensions are analytically distinct yet practically inseparable.

At the level of the system, the primary question concerns its legal qualification, particularly where video technologies incorporate elements of automated image analysis or decision-making. The Regulation introduces a risk-based approach, classifying AI systems into categories that determine the scope and intensity of regulatory obligations [6]. In the waste management context, a system may potentially fall within the high-risk category if it produces outputs that affect individuals' rights or obligations, such as automated detection of improper waste sorting linked to sanctions, or if it involves biometric identification. Such classification entails extensive compliance requirements, including risk management procedures, documentation, transparency obligations, and, in certain cases, conformity assessment. Even where a system does not qualify as high-risk, its deployment must still be evaluated in light of proportionality and potential interference with fundamental rights.

The second dimension concerns the subjects operating within the waste management structure. As it is stated, waste management systems typically involve waste producers, organizations that provide waste collection vehicles, waste collection and processing companies and municipalities. The introduction of video technologies requires a clear allocation of roles and responsibilities: determining which entity acts as the controller, which as the processor, and who bears accountability for lawful data processing. While objectives such as improving sorting rates or preventing illegal dumping are legitimate public interests, the means employed must be proportionate and necessary in relation to those aims.

The third, and arguably most complex, dimension relates to data. Video technologies typically process image recordings that constitute personal data where individuals can be directly or indirectly identified [5]. Any processing operation must rely on a valid legal basis. In the context of

public waste management, this will generally be the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or compliance with a legal obligation.

The principle of data minimization requires that monitoring be limited to what is strictly necessary. This applies not only to the technical configuration of cameras but also to retention periods, access controls, and security measures. Where systematic monitoring of publicly accessible areas occurs on a large scale, a data protection impact assessment may be required. An additional layer of complexity arises from the informational value of waste itself. The content of waste may indirectly reveal sensitive information about an individual's health status, lifestyle, or other personal characteristics. If the system were to enable biometric identification, such as facial recognition, it would involve the processing of special categories of personal data, triggering a significantly stricter legal regime.

C. Municipal Strategic and Communication Objectives

From a municipal governance perspective, the video-analytical system represents a strategic instrument for promoting environmentally responsible behavior among waste producers. Through incentive-based mechanisms—such as point-based systems, reductions in municipal waste fees, or anonymized community benchmarking—the municipality may positively influence the quality of waste sorting. The overarching objective is to reduce contamination rates within collection fractions, enhance operational efficiency, and strengthen public trust in the transparency and fairness of the municipal waste management system. An additional motivational measure may involve the gradual reduction of waste fees for producers who consistently comply with sorting regulations and demonstrate responsible behavior.

VII. CONCLUSION

The study demonstrates that video-analytical systems based on computer vision and deep learning represent an effective tool for improving sorting quality in municipal waste management systems. By enabling real-time detection of improper disposal, contamination assessment, and structured event recording at waste collection points, during collection operations, and at recycling centres, the technology enhances operational transparency and supports data-driven decision-making. When integrated with access control mechanisms and implemented in accordance with privacy-by-design and data protection principles, such systems primarily support preventive, educational, and incentive-based approaches rather than punitive measures. Consequently, computer vision represents a strategic instrument for increasing the purity of collected fractions, optimizing waste collection logistics, and strengthening public trust in sustainable waste governance.

At the same time, the deployment of computer vision requires balancing efficiency and monitoring with the protection of privacy. Waste may possess not only environmental but also informational value, and its combination with visual monitoring may increase the risk of profiling or intrusive surveillance. Therefore, sustainable

implementation requires the integration of privacy safeguards during system design, comprehensive risk assessment, and transparent communication with affected individuals.

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Procedural Generation of Synthetic Road Scenes for Training Anomaly Detection Models

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Abstract—Modern computer vision systems are increasingly driven by artificial intelligence (AI), particularly in applications such as object detection from camera footage in traffic safety. Training reliable object detection models requires large quantities of diverse and high-quality image data, which are often difficult to obtain from real-world environments alone. In this work, we present an approach to procedural 3D scene creation using parametric modeling techniques that enable the controlled generation of realistic urban road environments. The generated scenes are rendered with high visual fidelity and used to produce highly variable synthetic datasets for training computer vision models. The proposed framework allows systematic modification of scene parameters such as object placement, environmental conditions, and camera configuration. The resulting synthetic data are used to train a YOLO (You Only Look Once) based object detector capable of identifying a new class of road objects—manholes. Experimental results demonstrate that procedurally generated synthetic datasets can effectively support the training of object detection models for traffic safety applications.

Index Terms—procedural scene, synthetic data, computer vision, model training, object detection, traffic safety

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Motivation

Modern urban infrastructure faces challenges to ensure safety: How to effectively monitor the condition of large road networks in real time. Traditional monitoring methods based on human labor and regular inspections are proving inadequate in terms of scalability and cost.

With the development of advanced computer vision algorithms, particularly deep learning-based object detectors, including YOLO variants, a new path opens for automatizing these processes. However, efficiency is directly dependent on the quality and quantity of training data, which can be a critical bottleneck for applications focused on unique anomalies.

B. Problem Statement

One of the crucial anomalies in the city landscape can be a damaged road or missing manhole covers. Missing covers pose a critical risk to motorists, cyclists, and pedestrians. It is a global problem, often compounded by the theft of cast iron elements to cash out at metal scrap yards. Although modern image-based object detectors achieve high accuracy in recognizing common features, such as cars or pedestrians, in the case of missing manhole covers, they face the long-tail distribution problem [1]. This means that these cases occur so rarely that the model fails to learn their specific visual features or interprets them as noise in the data.

C. Proposed Approach

This article describes the development and implementation of a procedural framework in Blender [2] to generate high-fidelity synthetic data to address the lack of real-world images of anomalies, such as missing manhole covers. The system uses procedural modeling using Geometry Nodes [3] to generate variations of road scenes, allowing the automated generation of annotated images and segmentation masks. This approach not only drastically reduces the cost of data collection and annotation, but also allows the simulation of extreme lighting and weather conditions that are difficult to capture in the real world, increasing the robustness of the final neural network models.

D. Contributions

The main contributions of the current work are the development of a procedural framework for controllable road scene generation that supports the injection of anomalies for safety-critical objects while allowing for the generation of synthetic data with automatically generated annotations. Moreover, we conduct an experimental evaluation for the detection of objects

when a model is trained on a combination of real data, AI-enhanced data, and synthetic data.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Object Detection in Traffic Safety

Detection of road infrastructure anomalies, such as damaged or missing manhole covers, represents an important component of modern intelligent transportation systems and smart city infrastructures. Traditional approaches often rely on manual inspections or specialized sensors, e.g. mobile laser scanning, which uses algorithms, such as random forests, to identify geometric features of objects on the road [4] [5].

In recent years, the focus has been on image-based object detection methods, driven by the efficiency of deep learning architectures such as YOLO [6] and vision transformers [7]. These models enable real-time operation with a standard vehicle-mounted camera. However, the performance of such detectors is dependent on the availability of high-quality training data. For traffic safety applications, it is important to have a balanced dataset that includes safety-critical events and road states that are severely underrepresented in real-world traffic. The absence of such balance leads to the long-tail problem [1], where rare anomalies, such as missing manhole covers, are often misclassified as noise or normal road texture. To ensure the reliability of these systems, alternative methods are necessary to supplement sparse data distributions, leading to an increased use of synthetic data.

B. Synthetic Data for Computer Vision

Using synthetic data has become a key strategy for addressing data imbalance and the long-tail effect. By generating artificial images, it is possible to create a dataset in which rare phenomena are represented with sufficient frequency for effective neural network training. Previous work in the field of domain randomization shows that the variability of the synthetic environment helps overcome the Sim2Real gap [8] [9] [10], the difference in model performance when transitioning from simulated synthetic data to reality. Recent studies suggest that combining domain randomization with physics-based rendering [11] or neural rendering techniques [12] can further improve the generalization of detectors to real-world tasks.

The advantage of synthetic data is not only quantity but also, above all, the possibility of automatically generating annotations without human error. In our work, we use synthetic data to "fill in" the missing parts of the long tail, thereby teaching the model to recognize the visual features of anomalies that would otherwise be very difficult and time-consuming to capture in the real world.

C. Procedural Scene Generation

Although diffusion-based generative models (e.g., Stable Diffusion [13]) currently dominate in synthetic image data generation, they have fundamental limitations for training

detectors in technical and safety-critical domains. These black-box models often lack geometric accuracy and cannot guarantee strict consistency between the synthetic image and its annotations (e.g., bounding boxes or masks). In this context, procedural frameworks, such as BlenderProc [14], Kubric [15], or Syclops [16], are increasingly promoted in the professional literature for generating training data.

These tools use parametric control over the 3D scene, enabling the simulation of physically correct lighting, texture variability, and complex geometric surface deformations. The main advantage of the procedural approach over generative AI is the ability to generate pixel-perfect segmentation masks that are strictly bound to the 3D geometry of objects. In the context of road anomaly detection, this deterministic approach ensures that every variation is represented in the dataset with absolute precision. This is a necessary prerequisite for training robust models that must reliably distinguish potentially dangerous defects, which may often appear small in the image, from visual noise in real-world operation.

III. PROBLEM DEFINITION

A. Application Context

This work addresses the detection of missing manhole covers in road environments using vehicle-mounted RGB cameras. A missing manhole cover represents a safety-critical road anomaly that can cause vehicle damage, traffic disruption, or accidents. Therefore, early and reliable detection of such anomalies is important for the monitoring of road safety and infrastructure.

The goal is to automatically identify and localize manhole covers in images captured by different types of vehicle operating under real traffic conditions, and to distinguish their state (open/closed).

B. Detection Task

The system's input is a single RGB image acquired by a vehicle-mounted camera. Depending on the annotations provided and the detector design, the output consists of either:

- Bounding boxes localizing non-missing/missing manhole instances, or
- Instance segmentation masks precisely outlining the different manhole areas.

The task can therefore be formulated as an object detection or instance segmentation problem, where the target classes correspond to *non-missing (closed)* or *missing (open)* manhole covers.

C. Camera Configurations and Viewpoint Variability

Images are captured from heterogeneous vehicle platforms with different camera positions and viewing geometries. Typical configurations include:

- Rear-mounted cameras on trucks, positioned higher above the ground and observing a relatively small road area behind the vehicle.

- Front-mounted cameras in passenger vehicles, typically installed at a lower height and covering a wider field of view in front of the car.

These differences introduce significant variability in viewing angle and perspective, apparent size of the manhole in the image, distance to the anomaly, field of view, and illumination conditions and shadows. The detection system must therefore generalize across multiple camera geometries and operational conditions.

D. Challenges

The main challenges of the problem addressed include:

- rarity of missing manhole events in real-world datasets,
- large variability in road appearance and environmental conditions,
- visual similarity between intact and missing manholes in certain viewpoints, and
- safety-critical requirement to minimize false negatives (missed anomalies).

Collecting and annotating sufficient real-world data of missing manholes is difficult due to their relatively low frequency of occurrence. This data scarcity motivates the use of synthetic data generation to enrich the training dataset.

E. Synthetic Data Assumptions

To overcome the limited availability of real anomaly data, synthetic road scenes are generated using a procedural modeling framework. The generation process allows controlled variation of:

- road geometry and surface appearance,
- placement and state of manholes (intact or missing),
- lighting and weather conditions, and
- position and orientation of the camera.

The rendering pipeline automatically produces RGB images along with corresponding ground truth annotations (bounding boxes or instance masks).

F. Objectives

The primary objective is to design and validate a procedural scene generation framework capable of producing large amounts of realistic and highly variable synthetic data for training object detection models.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Overview of the Proposed Framework

The framework combines procedural modeling and parametric modeling paradigms within the Blender [2] environment, leveraging the Geometry Nodes [3] system for rule-based geometry generation and exposing adjustable parameters to control scene variability. Photorealistic image synthesis is performed using the physically based Cycles [17] renderer.

The overall workflow (see Figure 1) consists of procedural scene construction, parameter-driven configuration of scenario attributes, anomaly insertion, and automated rendering with annotation export. The system allows predefined traffic scenarios to be generated through a structured user interface while

Fig. 1: Workflow description

Fig. 2: Overview of the designed city scene

maintaining full control over geometric, environmental, and camera-related variables. This approach enables systematic exploration of scene configurations while maintaining the reproducibility and scalability required for dataset generation.

B. Procedural Scene Generation

1) *Scene Components*: The synthetic environment is a parametrized urban area composed of modular 3D assets representing typical street infrastructure. The scene includes road surfaces, sidewalks, manhole covers, buildings, greenery, and common urban accessories such as traffic signs, street lamps, and traffic lights. Assets are organized in Blender’s Asset Browser to enable structured management and reuse.

Buildings are generated from modular segments that allow flexible assembly in various architectural forms. Facade elements, floor counts, and structural variations are combined to produce visually distinct instances while maintaining realistic proportions. Urban accessories and greenery are distributed across the scene in a manner reflecting typical city layouts. All assets are optimized to balance geometric realism and

rendering efficiency. See the overview of the city area scene in Figure 2.

Hierarchical relationships are established between the elements of the scene. For example, manhole placement is procedurally linked to the street geometry, ensuring that modifications to the road automatically trigger the recalculation of manhole positions. Similarly, buildings and sidewalks are generated relative to the road layout, maintaining spatial consistency across scene variations.

2) *Parametrization*: Parametric modeling is used to expose adjustable attributes of the scene that can be systematically varied. The parameters are accessible through a structured user interface integrated into the Blender environment. These controls allow for modification of scenario-specific elements, such as manhole density and the ratio of open to closed covers, as well as broader scene attributes, including building height ranges, facade composition, and vegetation density.

The camera configuration is also parametrized to replicate real-world vehicle-mounted setups. Adjustable parameters include camera height, tilt angle, field of view, and relative mounting position, enabling simulation of both front-mounted passenger vehicle cameras and elevated rear-mounted truck cameras. These configurations directly influence perspective projection and object scale within the rendered images (see Figure 3).

Lighting conditions are controlled through a physically based sky model that allows adjustment of sun elevation, intensity, and atmospheric properties. Procedural materials further enhance variability by enabling controlled changes in surface textures, coloration, and aging. Together, these parametric controls allow for systematic exploration of scene configurations while preserving realistic urban structure.

3) *Scene Variability Strategy*: Scene variability is achieved through controlled sampling of the defined parameter space. Each generated scene instance is produced by selecting parameter values within predefined ranges and optionally varying random seeds that influence object placement and material variation. This hybrid approach combines structured scenario definition with stochastic variation, ensuring both realism and diversity.

The procedural logic embedded within Geometry Nodes enables automatic recalculation of dependent geometry when upstream parameters are modified. As a result, large numbers of unique yet structurally coherent urban scenes can be efficiently generated. By adjusting anomaly frequency, lighting conditions, camera setups, and environmental composition, the system produces datasets that capture substantial appearance variation required for robust machine learning training.

C. Anomaly Modeling: Missing Manhole Covers

The anomaly of interest is a manhole structure without a protective cover, which exposes the underlying cavity. Within the procedural framework, manholes are instantiated along road surfaces using a geometry node system that governs spatial placement, density, and orientation. Each manhole

instance is assigned a state variable indicating whether it is intact or missing (see Figure 4).

In the missing-cover state, the cover geometry is removed and replaced with a recessed cavity model featuring appropriate depth and interior surface properties. Material adjustments and shading interactions are incorporated to ensure a realistic visual appearance under varying lighting conditions. The proportion of open versus closed manholes is explicitly controlled through exposed parameters, allowing systematic adjustment of class balance in the generated dataset.

By integrating anomaly modeling directly into the procedural graph, the framework enables the efficient generation of rare yet safety-critical scenarios without manual editing. This ensures reproducibility while supporting large-scale synthetic data creation.

D. Synthetic Data Rendering and Annotation

The rendering is performed using Blender’s Cycles engine to achieve physically based illumination and realistic material interaction. Camera models are configured to approximate real vehicle-mounted imaging systems, including perspective projection, field of view, camera distortion, and resolution settings consistent with target deployment platforms. A geometry node-based camera rig allows for systematic variation of camera position and tilt, enabling simulation of heterogeneous vehicle viewpoints.

Dataset generation can be automated using Blender’s Python API, which orchestrates parameter sampling, scene updates, and batch rendering. For each rendered RGB image, corresponding ground-truth annotations are automatically generated. Depending on the training objective, annotations include instance segmentation masks or bounding boxes for manhole instances or other objects in the scene. An example of the final rendered scene, together with a precise instance segmentation mask, is shown in Figure 5.

E. Object Detection Training Setup

The YOLOv8 model [18] was chosen as the object detector, initialized with pre-trained weights from the COCO dataset. To assess performance across different computational capacities, both the nano (YOLOv8n) and small (YOLOv8s) architecture variants were evaluated. For each experiment, identical training configurations and hyperparameters were maintained to ensure comparable results across different training strategies. Three primary training strategies were investigated: (i) training exclusively on procedural synthetic data, (ii) training on real data supplemented with AI-generated examples of the missing class (open manhole), and (iii) a hybrid combination of real, AI-generated, and procedural synthetic data.

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

A. Dataset and Evaluation Description

The real-world training and testing data originate from the CAMAN tool [20], which was used to collect the dataset, representing highly variable urban environments captured by vehicle-mounted cameras. A key challenge in assembling the

(a) Selected adjustable parameters of the camera (b) Example of the placement of the camera in the scene

Fig. 3: Parametrized camera configuration

Fig. 4: Parametric setup for manhole distribution in the scene

datasets was the absence of real annotated examples of the *open manhole* class. To overcome this, a generative crop-and-paste method was used: the manhole region was cropped from a real image, edited using the Gemini 2.5 Flash Image model [19] to remove the cover and reveal the opening. The result was pasted back into its original position. Such Real+AI dataset preserves spatial annotations without the need for manual relabeling. Table I shows the distribution of the training splits. All models were then evaluated on a fixed and isolated test set of 106 real images, with a balanced split of 50 open and 56 closed manholes. This test set remained unchanged across all experiments to ensure a fair baseline.

TABLE I: Overview of training datasets.

Data type	Train	Val	Objects Opened	Objects Closed
Synthetic	160	40	509	692
Real+AI	314	84	185	199
Real+AI+Synth.	474	124	694	891

The primary metric is mAP@50, with mAP@50-95, precision, recall, and the F1 score tracked in addition [21]. From a safety perspective, minimizing false-negative detections of the

open manhole class is important, because in a traffic scenario, failure to detect such a critical object can have catastrophic consequences.

B. Results

The quantitative results for the YOLOv8n and YOLOv8s architectures are summarized in Table II and Table III, respectively. Models trained exclusively on the Synthetic dataset failed to detect the open manhole class in real-world test images (AP50 open = 0.000 for both variants), confirming a significant Sim2Real domain shift when relying strictly on procedural data.

The inclusion of AI-generated examples (Real+AI dataset) represented a positive shift, allowing the networks to establish initial feature representations for the rare anomaly. Under this strategy, the YOLOv8n model achieved an overall mAP@50 of 0.459.

The best overall performance was achieved by the **Real+AI+Synth.** dataset, demonstrating the value of hybrid training with procedural data. This combination yielded the highest overall mAP@50 for both YOLOv8n (0.490) and YOLOv8s (0.427). Crucially for safety applications, this comprehensive dataset also maximized detection performance for the critical *open manhole* class, achieving an AP50 of 0.218 with the YOLOv8n architecture. The structural variability provided by the procedural synthetic scenes successfully complemented the AI-augmented real data, thereby improving the model's generalization to real-world anomalies.

TABLE II: Results on the test set (YOLOv8n).

Dataset	mAP@50	mAP@50-95	F1	AP50 open	AP50 closed
Synthetic	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Real+AI	0.459	0.272	0.429	0.185	0.732
Real+AI+Synth.	0.490	0.305	0.476	0.218	0.762

VI. DISCUSSION

A. Practical Deployment Considerations

The procedural synthetic framework streamlines deployment across diverse vehicle fleets. Instead of costly real-world

(a) Final rendered image using Cycles renderer (b) Instance segmentation mask for the rendered image

Fig. 5: Example of synthetic data rendering and automatic annotation

TABLE III: Results on the test set (YOLOv8s).

Dataset	mAP@50	mAP@50-95	F1	AP50 open	AP50 closed
Synthetic	0.101	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.203
Real+AI	0.313	0.184	0.341	0.028	0.598
Real+AI+Synth.	0.427	0.285	0.407	0.096	0.757

data collection for new camera heights or angles, tailored training datasets can be rapidly generated by adjusting virtual camera parameters. This flexibility accelerates the adaptation of object detectors to new hardware configurations and operational environments.

B. Safety Implications

Minimizing false negatives for the *open manhole* class is critical for safety. Real-world datasets naturally underrepresent extreme, high-risk edge cases such as heavy shadows or poor lighting. Synthetic generation mitigates this risk by deliberately simulating and oversampling these hazardous scenarios, ensuring the model is explicitly trained to reliably detect anomalies under visually degraded conditions that are difficult to capture in reality.

In real-world deployment, objects located far from the vehicle camera suffer from low spatial resolution and severe perspective distortion, increasing the likelihood of false positive detections. To address this, the current production pipeline incorporates a distance-based Region of Interest (ROI) filtering mechanism. The system restricts the evaluation to specific safety zones, ignoring objects beyond a predefined threshold (e.g. distances greater than 15 m). Limiting the algorithm to objects within close proximity eliminates unreliable predictions caused by poor viewing angles, significantly reduces the false positive rate, and focuses computational resources exclusively on immediate hazards.

VII. LIMITATIONS

As demonstrated by the experimental results, pure synthetic training is insufficient for zero-shot real-world deployment. Consequently, hybrid training approaches or advanced domain adaptation strategies remain necessary to achieve reliable detection.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that hybrid training strategies combining real, AI-generated, and procedural synthetic data significantly improve the detection of rare road anomalies. The best performance was achieved using the combined Real+AI+Synthetic dataset, which improved overall detection metrics and substantially increased performance for the safety-critical open manhole class. The results highlight the value of procedural synthetic data as a complementary augmentation strategy that enhances dataset diversity and supports scalable deployment across varying hardware configurations. However, the findings also confirm that synthetic data alone remains insufficient for reliable real-world deployment, reinforcing the need for hybrid datasets or domain adaptation techniques in safety-critical perception systems.

A. Future Work

Future work will focus on expanding the scope and operational efficiency of the proposed framework through the following objectives: (i) Extension to additional anomaly categories by incorporating diverse hazards such as wildlife detection or structural road damage. (ii) Integration of domain adaptation techniques to further bridge the Sim2Real gap. (iii) Multi-sensor synthetic data generation by expanding the pipeline to support other sensor simulation like LiDaR. (iv) Real-world pilot validation.

A key refinement in these upcoming iterations will be the optimization of the synthetic data distribution to better serve production requirements. Prioritizing the generation of synthetic images where anomalies are located closer to the camera aligns the training data with production-ready ROI filtering. By minimizing the generation of distant, low-resolution objects that are typically ignored during real-world inference, we can ensure the model focuses its learning capacity on the most immediate and relevant safety risks.

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Digital Twin of a Structured-Light 3D Camera

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Abstract—Accurate 3D reconstruction in industrial environments requires millimeter-level precision and geometric traceability, which purely data-driven monocular approaches cannot guarantee. Structured-light cameras provide high-resolution depth based on triangulation, but development and evaluation of reconstruction pipelines and learning-based refinement methods are limited by restricted access to real sensor data. In this work, we present the concept of digital twin of a structured-light 3D camera. The system simulates an acquisition pipeline, including pattern projection, virtual scene rendering, precise camera and projector alignment, and synchronized pattern-capture sequences. Unlike simplified depth simulators, the proposed model combines photometric realism with explicit modeling of the triangulation process, enabling reproducible generation of physically plausible structured-light data across diverse materials and scenes. Preliminary evaluations indicate realistic behavior, consistent with real sensors, supporting its use for algorithm development, hybrid analytical-learning approaches, and synthetic training data generation.

Index Terms—3D scanning, structured-light camera, digital twin, synthetic data, graphical engines, rendering

I. INTRODUCTION

There are many techniques for acquiring a 3D reconstruction of a real scene. Recently, monocular depth prediction has improved substantially due to large pre-trained transformer-based models [1], which infer 3D structure from RGB images using knowledge learned from large-scale datasets. The predicted depth maps can be converted into 3D meshes [2], and some approaches generate full 3D models directly in an end-to-end manner [3]. However, monocular reconstruction inherently suffers from scale ambiguity and strong dependence on the statistical distribution of the training data. As a result, these methods rely on learned priors rather than explicit geometric constraints, which limits precision and traceability of the reconstruction process [4].

For applications requiring millimeter-level accuracy, such as industrial inspection, dedicated sensing hardware remains essential [5]. Stereo vision systems use two calibrated RGB cameras to recover depth through triangulation, but still require accurate calibration, robust correspondence estimation, and geometric computation [6]. Calibration errors directly propagate to depth inaccuracies, limiting reliability in high-precision scenarios. Other sensing modalities rely on different physical principles. Time-of-flight (ToF) cameras estimate depth by measuring the travel time of emitted light. While robust in

many environments, these sensors typically exhibit higher noise levels than triangulation-based systems, particularly near object boundaries [7]. Their spatial resolution is also limited by sensor architecture, and depth discontinuities may appear blurred. Although LiDAR often relies on the ToF principle, other modalities like triangulation and Frequency-Modulated Continuous Wave (FMCW) also exist, each with its own inherent trade-offs in range, precision, and complexity.

Structured-light cameras address some of these limitations by using triangulation similar to stereo vision but replacing one camera with a projector placed at a known baseline. By projecting predefined patterns and observing their deformation, correspondences between projector and camera pixels can be established to compute depth [8]. In controlled environments this approach provides high spatial resolution and sub-millimeter accuracy, particularly for surfaces with diffuse reflectance. However, performance degrades for complex materials. Reflective or glossy surfaces can distort the projected pattern, while translucent materials may transmit light and produce distorted or missing reconstructions [9]. Strong ambient illumination and limited projector power further restrict the usable measurement range.

Ideally, the robustness of modern data-driven approaches could be combined with the precision and geometric consistency of dedicated sensing hardware. However, training such methods requires large amounts of data, which are scarce for structured-light sensors due to their limited deployment and the proprietary nature of many industrial datasets. This motivates the use of digital twins, which represent virtual models of physical entities or processes [10]. In this work, we develop a digital twin of a structured-light camera that simulates projection, capture, and triangulation in a controllable virtual environment. The system generates photorealistic synthetic data with reproducible ground-truth geometry and physically plausible sensor interactions. This enables training data generation for tasks such as noise filtering, artefact removal, and hybrid reconstruction pipelines, while also allowing controlled experimentation with alternative hardware configurations such as different lenses, baselines, or projector designs before implementation in real devices.

The proposed digital twin framework aligns with the goals of the InnovAIte Slovakia project, which promotes the development of advanced AI technologies and research prototypes, including methods based on synthetic data and computer vision, to address real-world challenges across multiple domains.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Digital Twins

The concept of a digital twin refers to a virtual model that replicates the structure, behavior, and environmental interactions of a physical system, and it has been widely used in industry for process simulation, performance evaluation, and predictive maintenance [11]. More recently, digital twins have been applied to sensing systems such as cameras and depth sensors, where virtual sensors are placed in simulated environments to reproduce image formation. Existing work includes modeling camera intrinsics, extrinsics, and basic optics to generate synthetic training data and evaluate perception pipelines, as well as more advanced approaches that simulate lens distortion, sensor noise, motion blur, exposure dynamics, and rolling shutter effects [12]. In active 3D sensing, digital twins may also model illumination and structured-light projection to replicate depth acquisition. Creating high-fidelity twins of structured-light cameras remains challenging due to complex light interactions, which has led to recent efforts combining physically based rendering with explicit sensor modeling to approximate real-world behavior [13].

B. Synthetic Data

Synthetic data generation has become an established approach for training and validating computer vision and 3D reconstruction methods when large annotated real-world datasets are unavailable or difficult to obtain [14]. Modern rendering engines allow creation of photorealistic scenes with precise ground-truth annotations, including depth and geometry [9].

A persistent challenge, however, is the sim-to-real gap, caused by discrepancies between simulated and physical environments [15]. Differences in material reflectance, illumination, optical distortions, and sensor-specific noise can lead to systematic performance degradation when models trained on synthetic data are deployed on real sensors. In active depth systems, this issue is particularly pronounced, as the measured signal depends on the interaction between projected light patterns and scene materials. Simplified simulation approaches that directly output ideal depth maps fail to reproduce typical artefacts such as decoding errors, multipath effects, or distortions caused by reflective and translucent surfaces [9].

To mitigate this gap, prior work has explored domain randomization, domain adaptation, and increasingly realistic sensor modeling [16]. In the case of structured-light cameras, reducing the sim-to-real discrepancy requires explicit modeling of the triangulation process together with photorealistic rendering. This motivates the development of digital twins that simulate the complete sensing pipeline rather than only generating synthetic depth outputs, enabling more reliable transfer of algorithms from simulation to real-world deployment.

C. Graphical Engines

Modern physically based rendering frameworks provide the foundation for building high-fidelity digital twins of optical sensors [17]. In our experiments, two environments proved suitable for simulating a structured-light 3D camera:

Blender with the LuxCoreRender¹ engine, and Unreal Engine 5 with hardware-accelerated ray tracing [18]. Blender combined with LuxCoreRender offers a physically accurate path-tracing pipeline capable of simulating complex light transport, material reflectance, and optical effects. Physically based material models and spectral light transport allow accurate evaluation of photometric phenomena that influence pattern visibility and decoding. However, such simulations are computationally demanding and typically operate in an offline rendering workflow, which limits their use for interactive experimentation or large-scale dataset generation.

In contrast, Unreal Engine 5 provides a real-time rendering environment with support for physically based materials, hardware ray tracing, and programmable rendering pipelines. Its rendering framework allows implementation of projector pattern emission, synchronized image capture from virtual cameras, and direct control over camera intrinsics, extrinsics, and image acquisition parameters [17]. Engine components such as the camera actor system, material graph, and post-processing pipeline enable simulation of sensor-level effects including lens distortion, exposure adjustments, and noise models. Compared to offline rendering approaches, Unreal Engine therefore provides a more practical platform for iterative development, large-scale synthetic data generation, and interactive evaluation of structured-light sensing pipelines.

III. TECHNOLOGY

While consumer-grade depth sensors such as the Intel RealSense series² provide convenient and affordable 3D data from active stereo or time-of-flight principles, their precision, resolution, and robustness are limited for high-accuracy industrial tasks. These systems are typically designed for general computing and robotics applications where sub-centimeter accuracy suffices, but they do not meet the millimeter-level precision and dynamic scene performance required in demanding automation or inspection pipelines [9]. Here, we focus on creation of a digital twin of an industrial grade device.

A. PhoXi 3D Camera

The Photoneo MotionCam-3D represents an industrial structured-light 3D camera designed for high resolution, accuracy, and dynamic capture capability in a single device. It is based on Parallel Structured Light technology, which captures high-density 3D point clouds in near real time while avoiding motion blur even for rapidly moving objects. Unlike traditional sequential structured-light systems that require static scenes, the parallel acquisition approach effectively freezes dynamic scenes in a single snapshot, enabling high-quality area depth at frame rates up to approximately 20 fps. In this work, we create a digital twin of the MotionCam-3D M variant³, which provides a scanning range of roughly 497 mm to 939 mm with a depth map resolution of 1680 x 1200 pixels in static mode and up to the same resolution in dynamic mode.

¹<https://luxcorerender.org>

²<https://www.realsenseai.com>

³<https://www.photoneo.com/products/motioncam-3d-m/>

The Photoneo sensor operates on the structured-light principle of observing the deformation of projected patterns, but it does so using a high-power light in the visible spectrum rather than the infrared light common in other sensors [8]. It uses a laser whose beam is swept across the scene by a controllable mirror, forming a sequence of projected illumination patterns. These patterns encode the spatial position of the projected ray along the scanning direction. In practice, several binary Gray-code patterns are projected to determine a coarse spatial index of the projector coordinate. To further refine this estimate, additional sinusoidal phase-shift patterns are used to recover a continuous phase value, enabling sub-pixel precision. By combining the discrete Gray-code index with the continuous phase information, the system determines the correspondence between camera pixels and projector rays, from which depth is computed through triangulation between the camera and projector. Our goal is to reproduce these pattern images synthetically within a virtual environment, enabling the creation of a digital twin of the depth acquisition pipeline.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

To construct the digital twin of the structured-light sensor, we first extracted the geometric configuration and camera parameters of the real device using the PhoXiControl software⁴. The software provides access to the intrinsic parameters of the camera as well as the spatial configuration of the sensing system, including the relative placement of the camera and the projector. A screenshot of this interface is shown in Fig. 1. These parameters were obtained after calibrating the physical camera using a marker calibration pattern, which allowed us to determine the precise pose of the camera within the captured scene and measure the baseline between the camera and projector.

Using this information, we recreated the real scanning setup in a virtual environment. The scene was first constructed in Blender, where we placed a 3D model of a toy bear that had previously been printed using a 3D printer and used as the primary scanned object. Additionally, a 3D model of a glass was included in the scene to match the real experimental setup⁵. The bear model was positioned in the scene according to the calibrated pose obtained from PhoXiControl, and virtual camera and projector elements were placed with the correct relative baseline and orientation. An overview of the reconstructed virtual scene together with the 3D model of the bear is shown in Fig. 2.

After reconstructing the scene geometry in Blender, the environment was imported into Unreal Engine 5, where the sensing simulation was implemented. Within the engine, we configured the virtual camera and implemented projection of the structured-light patterns to match the specifications of the real Photoneo device. This setup allowed us to reproduce the projection–capture configuration of the physical camera and generate synthetic pattern observations consistent with the structured-light depth estimation pipeline.

⁴<https://www.photoneo.com/downloads/phoxi-control/>

⁵<https://www.skeletex.xyz/redirect/camera-dt-innovaite>

Fig. 1: Visualization of the real scene and camera volumes.

(a) Scene construction in Blender.

(b) Toy bear 3D model.

Fig. 2: Visualization of the synthetic scene, notice position and projection volumes of both camera and the projector.

V. EVALUATION

At the current stage of development, we perform a qualitative evaluation of the proposed digital twin by visually comparing the projected pattern images captured by the real sensor with those rendered in the virtual environment. Figure 3 shows a side-by-side comparison of the real scene recorded by the structured-light camera and the corresponding synthetic rendering generated in the simulation. The comparison focuses primarily on the appearance and spatial distribution of the projected light patterns, which are the key observable used by the depth reconstruction pipeline.

While the synthetic patterns closely resemble the real measurements, several physical effects are not yet modeled. The current implementation does not reproduce the radial distortion from the device’s lenses, which causes noticeable geometric deformation in the real images. Additionally, the rendered projection lacks the characteristic sensor noise that introduces visible intensity fluctuations in the projected signal. Because of these missing effects, the simulated data cannot yet be directly processed by the complete depth estimation pipeline. Nevertheless, the strong qualitative similarity of the results confirms that the proposed approach is a promising basis for constructing a faithful digital twin of the structured-light acquisition process.

(a) Real pattern image from the 3D camera.

(b) Rendered synthetic pattern image from Unreal Engine.

Fig. 3: Comparison between real and rendered pattern image.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, we presented a digital twin of a structured-light 3D camera implemented in Unreal Engine 5, designed to simulate the full projection–capture–reconstruction pipeline. The system provides configurable pattern projection, physically-based rendering, and realistic camera modeling.

To assess the fidelity of the proposed model, we captured real-world evaluation scenes using a physical structured-light camera and replicated these scenarios in the virtual environment. Comparative analysis indicates that the simulated data reproduce key characteristics observed in real measurements, including behavior on reflective and complex materials. While further quantitative evaluation is needed, the preliminary results demonstrate that the digital twin provides a sufficiently realistic approximation.

Future work will focus on enhancing the realism by modeling physical phenomena like lens distortion, sensor noise, and inter-reflections. We will then leverage this improved simulation to generate large-scale annotated datasets, enabling us to train robust 3D reconstruction algorithms and systematically quantify the sim-to-real gap for industrial applications.

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Towards Motion Synthesis for Rare and Dangerous Event Recognition

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Abstract—The detection of rare and dangerous behaviors in video surveillance is often hindered by the scarcity of real-world training data. Although general action recognition datasets excel at identifying common activities, they lack the specialized motion sequences required to train robust AI for security-critical scenarios. This research proposes a data augmentation framework that utilizes a parametric 3D human model and movement synthesis to bridge this gap. By combining motion capture data with generative motion tools, we create synthetic sequences of rare events that can be effectively combined with a parametric SMPL model and used for direct animation or synthetic data generation.

Index Terms—synthetic data, motion synthesis, parametric human model, dangerous behavior, event detection

I. INTRODUCTION

Video surveillance represents a crucial part of modern security infrastructures. Recognizing rare and hazardous events, such as a person with a weapon or knife, a person fainting, a left-behind item, or suspicious behavior remains a critical challenge in the computer vision field. Emergency scenarios require a robust action recognition system to enable early intervention in public safety applications.

Existing general action recognition datasets such as Kinetics [1], UCF101 [2] and AVA [3] contain common activities, e.g. walking, running, crawling, dancing, etc. However, these datasets offer limited coverage of dangerous human-centric behaviors. Consequently, specialized databases focused on this have been introduced [4]. They focus on various areas, but mainly on people carrying or aiming handguns or assault rifles.

Although numerous real-world datasets are available, they still contain gaps due to scenarios that were either not captured or only captured a limited number of times. This creates an opportunity to utilize synthetic data to bridge the gaps and enhance existing datasets. Advances in 3D human models create new approaches to generate data that capture rare and dangerous scenes. These 3D human models provide a foundation that can be animated using motion capture data or human motion generation tools.

This paper explores human models together with motion data and motion synthesis as a pathway to extend existing datasets using synthetic data focused on the detection of rare and dangerous events. The main contributions can be summarized as follows:

- 1) provision of a review what kind of motion data are missing for dangerous motion synthesis,
- 2) an analysis of state-of-the-art methods for motion synthesis and generation, where we show which methods can be used to bridge the gap of motion data scarcity for rare events,
- 3) proposal of a framework for motion driven synthesis based on the SMPL model.

II. RELATED WORK

Synthetic data generation for the detection of emergency events in surveillance scenarios lies at the intersection of multiple research domains including 3D human modeling, animating human models, and rendering the final scene. Although general action recognition research focuses on recognizing common daily activities, recent efforts have shifted towards detecting high-risk behaviors as part of early warning systems.

In this section, we first closely look at 3D human body models that are easily controllable and form the backbone of the human-centric generation pipelines. We then discuss real-world databases consisting of 2D images or monocular sequences and subsequently datasets containing motion capture data that can be applied to human models. Finally, we examine the motion synthesis tools that offer the ability to generate motions that can be later used to animate the model.

A. 3D Human Models

Parametric 3D human body models have become a fundamental component in computer graphics and computer vision use cases that involve virtual humans. These models excel at controlling the body shape and parameterizing it, enabling a realistic reconstruction. Due to their ability to produce anatomically consistent meshes and their compatibility with industry-standard tools, they are widely used in tasks including human pose and shape estimation [5] and synthetic data generation [6].

The *Skinned Multi-Person Linear* (SMPL) model [7] is one of the most popular parametric 3D human models in computer vision. It represents the human body as a triangular mesh that is controlled by the input shape and pose parameters. The shape parameters are used to define the anatomical shape of the body while the pose parameters define joint rotations. The SMPL+H model extends the original one by incorporating

Fig. 1. Comparison of the base SMPL [7] model and the advanced SMPL-X [8] model, both with visualized kinematic skeletons.

the articulated hand models derived from MANO [9]. This improvement significantly increases the expressive ability of the entire model. The SMPL-X model [8] unifies all previous developments by integrating the SMPL body, MANO hand models, and FLAME head model [10]. In addition to full-body articulation, it supports detailed hand poses and facial expressions through additional parameters. The resulting detail representation is particularly important in applications where hand-object interaction and mimicry play a key role. Fig. 1 illustrates the SMPL and SMPL-X models compared side by side together with the highlighted bones.

Recent developments in 3D human modeling aim to enhance the realism and cover more diverse human appearances. The MHR model [11] introduces improvements in the representation of body geometry while maintaining compatibility of the parametric control and animation frameworks. Although the MHR model is SMPL-based, the Anny model [12] represents a completely independent model that focuses on improved realism and easy-to-understand parameterization.

B. Real-World Databases

Real-world data are crucial for training any action recognition system or for evaluating existing ones. Early large-scale action recognition datasets, such as UCF101 [2] focused on capturing common everyday activities, including walking, running, and human-object interactions. Although these databases are very useful, they rarely include emergency or dangerous situations.

Therefore, to address this limitation, several specialized datasets designed for violent or abnormal behavior have been

Fig. 2. Comparison between various datasets focused on violence and danger detection.

introduced. The RWF-2000 [13] contains real-world surveillance videos classified as violent or non-violent, which makes it suitable for evaluation of violence detection algorithms. The clips were collected from public sources and usually capture public spaces such as streets and public transportation.

More recent datasets capture a wider range of dangerous and suspicious events. The VID dataset [14] provides annotated video sequences focused on interactions between people in possibly dangerous situations. Similarly, the FiDaSS dataset [15] targets firearm detection and detection of individuals carrying weapons in surveillance situations. Examples from RWF-2000, VID, and FiDaSS are illustrated in Fig. 2. Another recent dataset, DVD [16], expands this research area by focusing on violence detection, providing nearly three million annotated video frames.

These datasets provide a great base for training rare event detection systems and also serve as benchmarks for evaluation. However, despite their growing availability, they still suffer from limited coverage due to the low frequency of such events or ethical and legal constraints. Synthetic data generation is a promising approach for extending existing datasets by providing additional examples. Parametric human models combined with motion data and realistic rendering have the potential to create new training samples while complementing existing datasets.

C. Motion Datasets

To make human models move, motion data must be applied to their kinematic skeletal structure. Motion capture (Mocap) datasets provide such information by recording real human motion using the specialized capture systems and storing them as sequences of joint rotations that can later be mapped to a human model to make it move. One of the first is the CMU Mocap Database [17] composed of a large collection of motion sequences covering daily activity. Several years later, AMASS [18] introduced a major step. It aggregates motion capture data from multiple smaller datasets and unifies them, preparing them for use in the SMPL parameter space. Thanks

to this representation, motion capture data can be directly used with the SMPL-based human models.

Fig. 3. Example of BABEL dataset depicting motion with corresponding textual labels. Adapted from [19].

Although AMASS focuses primarily on unifying motion representation, the BABEL dataset [19] enriches it with semantic annotations, providing each motion sequence detailed action labels that are valuable for multimodal systems and action recognition tasks. Fig. 3 illustrates examples from the BABEL dataset. The HumanML3D dataset [20] further extends this idea by pairing human motion sequences with natural language descriptions. While BABEL focuses on semantic labeling of motions using predefined action categories, HumanML3D provides richer textual annotations that describe the motion in natural language. Such datasets are particularly useful for developing text-to-motion generation systems. One of the more recent datasets, Motion-X [21], introduced a large-scale database designed for motion understanding and motion generation tasks. It consists of human motion sequences together with corresponding textual descriptions and annotations.

Despite the multiple existing datasets, the majority focus on common daily activities, while rare and dangerous behaviors for surveillance scenarios remain underrepresented. This is the source of motivation for creating new motion sequences for these scenarios.

D. Motion Synthesis

Recent advances in motion synthesis aim to generate realistic human movements directly from high-level input, such as textual descriptions, visual input, or other semantic representations. Several frameworks have been proposed to address this task using generative models. MDM [23] introduces a diffusion-based approach to generate human motion conditioned on text descriptions. The model learns to refine motion representations, producing temporally coherent human movements based on the given prompt. Similarly, Motion-Diffuse [24] applies diffusion models for text-driven human motion generation, focusing on improving the motion diversity given the textual description and the resulting movements.

Fig. 4. Example of Hi-Motion framework that synthesizes motion based on the input prompt. Adapted from [22].

The reasoning power of Large Language Models (LLMs) can also be leveraged for 3D human modeling and motion synthesis. For example, M-Adaptor [25] is built for direct motion synthesis. Its goal is to generate a fluid sequence of frames and focuses on the physics and coordination of a whole body moving through time (e.g., running and jumping). On the other hand, ChatPose [26] is built for pose reasoning. It treats a 3D pose as a word in a conversation. You can ask it "How would this person look if they were exhausted?" and it will output a single 3D pose that reflects that state.

Another recent framework, Hi-Motion [22], focuses on generating temporally consistent human motion sequences from textual prompts while maintaining realistic body dynamics. For dangerous event motion synthesis, the M-Adaptor approach provides a methodology for generating sequences from the text prompts (e.g. person falling, man pulling a weapon, etc.), while the ChatPose offers a framework that can interpret complex scenes or videos directly, where visual context plays a key role.

III. OUR APPROACH

The goal of our framework is to generate synthetic video sequences capturing rare and dangerous events occurring in public spaces. These data will be used to enhance existing surveillance datasets and enable the training of more robust detection systems. The overall workflow is illustrated in Fig. 5 and combines parametric human models, motion synthesis, and controlled scene rendering to create realistic scenarios.

A. Human Model Initialization

The first step is the initialization of a parametric human model. We use an SMPL-based model [7] as the base representation due to its easy controllability and compatibility with existing motion datasets [18]. To generate multiple diverse

Fig. 5. Illustration of target pipeline.

synthetic characters, we randomly sample the shape parameters within the valid parameter space. This allows the system to create individuals with different body proportions such as height and weight. The resulting human model serves as the base that will later be animated.

B. Motion Generation

The next stage focuses on the motion sequences used to animate the human model. We will utilize the existing datasets mentioned in Sect. II. However, instead of relying solely on available data, which mostly contain everyday activities, we employ text-driven motion synthesis methods. Based on the input prompt provided, the motion generation framework conditions on the prompt and produces a sequence of joint rotations that represents the motion. The output of this stage is a structured motion representation composed of poses that can be directly applied to the kinematic skeleton.

C. Scene Rendering

In the final stage, the character animated in the previous stage is placed into a pre-prepared virtual environment. The environment is designed to mimic typical surveillance settings such as indoor public spaces, transportation hubs, parks, and open areas. The rendering process combines an animated human model with scene geometry, lighting, and camera configuration to produce realistic images or video sequences. Additional improvements such as multiple human models, objects, and additional elements can be introduced to enhance the realism of the scene. All parts will be rendered using one of the available industry-standard tools such as Unreal Engine [27], Unity [28] or Blender [29]. The resulting data can then be used as training data for detection systems to help improve their ability to detect rare, emergency, and dangerous events.

IV. DISCUSSION

The main objective of this work is not to present a generation-ready framework but rather to examine the current state of research in this area, outline future steps, and propose a possible pipeline for generating synthetic video sequences

of rare or dangerous events for recognition. In Sect. II, we review the parametric human models, existing datasets, and recent motion generation tools. Subsequently, we identify the components that can be combined into a unified framework for this task in Sect. III.

The pipeline outlined consists of three key components. The first is a parametric human model. The second is a motion generation module, and the last one is a scene rendering module. Although each of these elements already exists independently, their combination is relatively unexplored.

An important aspect of future work will be the evaluation of the generated data. Recent frameworks such as CLaM [30] provide standardized evaluation tools for text-driven motion generation. As CLaM is focused primarily on the base SMPL model, its extensions CLaM-H and CLaM-X were introduced together with the M-Adaptor framework [25].

Another important challenge lies in the potential domain gap between synthetic and real surveillance data. Despite the fact that synthetic environments allow precise control over scene parameters, visual differences between rendered and real data may affect the performance of trained models.

Overall, this work aims to provide a conceptual foundation for future research on motion-driven synthetic data generation for rare and dangerous situations. By identifying relevant datasets, human models, and motion synthesis approaches, this study outlines a possible integration pipeline and serves as a starting point for the development of practical systems capable of producing synthetic surveillance data for training detection systems.

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Pointing-Based Object Recognition

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Abstract—This paper presents a comprehensive pipeline for recognizing objects targeted by human pointing gestures using RGB images. As human-robot interaction moves toward more intuitive interfaces, the ability to identify targets of non-verbal communication becomes crucial. Our proposed system integrates several existing state-of-the-art methods, including object detection, body pose estimation, monocular depth estimation, and vision-language models. We evaluate the impact of 3D spatial information reconstructed from a single image and the utility of image captioning models in correcting classification errors. Experimental results on a custom dataset show that incorporating depth information significantly improves target identification, especially in complex scenes with overlapping objects. The modularity of the approach allows for deployment in environments where specialized depth sensors are unavailable.

Index Terms—Object detection, pointing gesture recognition, computer vision, monocular depth estimation, human-robot interaction, vision-language models.

I. INTRODUCTION

Natural and intuitive control forms are increasingly important in human-robot interaction (HRI). In domestic and industrial settings, robots are expected to understand human intent through non-verbal cues. Among these, pointing gestures are perhaps the most fundamental way humans designate objects in shared environments [1].

The objective of this work is to design and evaluate a robust pipeline capable of identifying a pointed-at object using a single RGB frame. We propose a pipeline that integrates various state-of-the-art modules to solve the pointing target problem in a practical setting. We specifically investigate how monocular 3D depth reconstruction and textual object descriptions from vision-language models can resolve the spatial ambiguities and classification errors inherent in traditional 2D pipelines.

We evaluate the proposed pipeline on our custom dataset consisting of images of humans pointing at objects placed on a table in front of them. The dataset contains ground truth annotations of pointed-at objects and covers scenes of varying difficulties.

The proposed pipeline includes object detection [2], [3], computation of the pointing vector, body keypoint localization [4], depth reconstruction with MoGe [5], and image captioning using BLIP [6], ViT-GPT2 [7], and GIT [8]. In total, four object detection models and three image captioning models were tested. We found that incorporating depth reconstruction helps reduce the number of false negative cases, and that adding textual descriptions of selected objects increases classification reliability in more complex scenes. The resulting solution is a comprehensive system that combines visual data

from the camera, estimation of the spatial arrangement of objects, and auxiliary textual descriptions of selected objects, thereby improving the accuracy of identifying the intended target of the pointing gesture.

II. RELATED WORK

The field of object recognition has seen a paradigm shift with the advent of Deep Learning [9]. Modern architectures like YOLO [2], [10] have revolutionized real-time object detection by framing the task as a single regression problem, providing a high balance between inference speed and accuracy. Furthermore, open-vocabulary detectors like OWL-ViT [3] allow for the detection of objects based on natural language queries instead of relying on fixed sets of object categories, making it more versatile in HRI scenarios.

Human pose estimation has similarly progressed, with frameworks like MediaPipe [4] providing efficient solutions for tracking body keypoints. These models allow for the extraction of skeletal data, which is essential for calculating the direction of a pointing gesture. However, 2D pose data alone is often insufficient for accurate pointing direction estimation in complex 3D environments.

Recent advancements in monocular geometry estimation [5], [11] have opened new possibilities. Deep neural networks such as MoGe [5] allow for the reconstruction of 3D point clouds from a single 2D image by estimating a depth map and camera intrinsics simultaneously. This allows the system to map 2D image coordinates to full 3D coordinates.

Additionally, the rise of vision-language models [6]–[8] has introduced the concept of image captioning. The captioning models can generate descriptive text for specific regions of an image. Such captioning can be used to enhance the object description for downstream processing. Image captioning can also serve as a verification step by cross-referencing the object detector labels to improve classification reliability.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed system follows a modular architecture where the input RGB image is processed through three primary parallel branches: object detection, pose estimation, and depth estimation. These outputs are then integrated in a fusion module to identify the target object. The full pipeline is visualized in Fig. 1. In the text below we describe its individual components.

Fig. 1. The full pipeline of the proposed system. The input image (a) is fed into three parallel branches: pose estimation (b), object detection (c) and depth estimation (d). The outputs of the three branches get combined to first classify whether pointing occurs and which detected object is pointed at (e). Finally, an image captioning module (f) is used to provide a better description of the object and to potentially fix an incorrect object label assignment.

A. Object Detection Branch

We employ a variety of object detection models to ensure the system can identify a wide range of household and industrial items. We utilize YOLOv8 and the more recent YOLO11 in various sizes (small, medium, large) provided by Ultralytics [2] to test the trade-off between speed and accuracy. For objects not included in the standard COCO dataset [12], we integrate OWL-ViT [3], which uses a Vision Transformer [13] backbone to perform open-vocabulary detection based on text prompts. The output of this branch is a set of bounding boxes $B = \{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n\}$ and their associated class labels.

B. Human Pose Recognition

To accurately identify the user’s intent, the system must first extract a reliable representation of the human skeletal structure. We utilize the MediaPipe Pose framework [4]. This model provides 33 3D landmarks, representing the major joints of the human body. We note that the 3D landmarks are provided in normalized coordinates and thus they do not represent the 3D positions of the joints in the scene, but only their relative position to each other.

C. Depth Estimation

A core component of our pipeline is the use of the MoGe model [5] for monocular depth estimation. For every pixel in the input image, MoGe predicts a depth value, effectively creating a 2D-to-3D mapping. This allows us to transform the 2D centroids of the detected object bounding box b_i into 3D points \vec{o}_i in a camera-centered coordinate system. Similarly, we can lift the 2D skeleton landmarks to 3D coordinates.

D. Object Recognition

We consider a pointing ray of the form $\vec{p}_w - \vec{p}_s$, which is the difference between the 3D position of the wrist and shoulder. To calculate the pointing score for each object, we also consider the 3D centroid of each detected bounding box \vec{o}_i . We then calculate a pointing score S_i for each object i :

$$S_i = \frac{\vec{v} \cdot \vec{u}_i}{\|\vec{v}\| \cdot \|\vec{u}_i\|}, \quad (1)$$

where $\vec{u}_i = \vec{o}_i - \vec{p}_s$ is the vector from the user’s shoulder to the object’s 3D centroid. Among the objects we select the one with the highest score as the pointed-at object. This 3D approach significantly reduces the “overlap” problem where a 2D ray might pass through multiple bounding boxes.

In our evaluation we also include a variant of the proposed method where we keep both the pointing direction and the object directions in 2D.

E. Gesture Recognition

To identify whether pointing occurs the system relies on the spatial relationship between the 3D positions of shoulder (\vec{p}_s), the elbow (\vec{p}_e), and the wrist (\vec{p}_w). Determining whether the user is actively pointing or simply resting their arm is treated as a binary classification task. We leverage the FLAML library [14] to optimize a classification model based on the extracted pose features. Two distinct feature representations were evaluated to find the optimal balance between simplicity and precision:

- **kpOnly (Keypoints Only):** This set includes the raw x, y, z coordinates of $\vec{p}_s, \vec{p}_e, \vec{p}_w$. These coordinates are normalized relative to the torso size to ensure the model is invariant to the user’s distance from the camera.
- **full (Extended Feature Set):** Beyond raw coordinates, this set includes engineered geometric features designed to capture the “intent” of the gesture. These include the 3D angle at the elbow joint (to measure arm extension), the Euclidean distance between the wrist and the torso, and the cosine similarity between the forearm and upper arm vectors to quantify the “straightness” of the pointing arm.

For both of these cases we also include the best achieved object score among the features.

The resulting classifier allows the system to trigger the object recognition and depth estimation modules only when a high-confidence pointing gesture is detected, thereby reducing computational overhead and minimizing false positives caused by natural body movements.

F. Image Captioning

Standard object detectors often fail on ambiguous items (e.g., distinguishing a white mug from a roll of toilet paper). To address this, we integrated an Image Captioning module. When a pointing gesture is detected, the system crops the target bounding box and passes it to models such as BLIP [6], ViT-GPT2 [7], or GIT [8]. These models generate a textual description of the object. If the caption strongly contradicts the detector’s label (e.g., the detector assigns the “cup” label but the caption includes “toilet paper”), the system can flag the result for manual verification or update the label based on the caption’s higher semantic understanding.

The captions can be beneficial even when the object detectors assign correct labels as the richer textual representation of the object can potentially be used in further downstream tasks.

IV. DATASET AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

To evaluate the system, we collected a custom dataset specifically designed to challenge the spatial logic of pointing recognition. The dataset consists of high-resolution RGB

Fig. 2. Sample images from our dataset. We use different types of gestures to indicate pointing at objects and neutral poses (no pointing). The dataset captures different levels of complexity in terms of item positions.

frames of users pointing at various objects in a room. For example images see Fig. 2.

To create the dataset we recruited 5 participants (3 women, 2 men) and instructed them to point at a specific object with one hand, both hands or to assume a neutral pose without pointing at an object. The objects were placed on a table in front of the participant. The data is categorized into two levels of complexity based on object placement:

- 1) **Easy Cases:** Objects are placed on a single plane (e.g., a table) with significant horizontal spacing (see Fig. 2 right). In these cases, 2D geometry is usually sufficient for identification.
- 2) **Hard Cases:** Objects are arranged in depth (e.g., one bottle behind another see Fig. 2 left) or very close to each other. These scenarios create overlapping bounding boxes in the 2D image, making it impossible to identify the target without depth information.

In total our dataset contains 376 annotated images. We split the data for training and testing. The training set contains 154 images (77 easy cases, 72 hard cases) and the test set contains 222 images (115 easy cases, 107 hard cases). Both sets contain images with participants pointing with either their left hand, right hand, or both.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section we present the results for individual components and various configurations of the full proposed pipeline.

A. Gesture Recognition

We first investigate how well our system is able to detect whether pointing is occurring (see Sec. III-E). Table I shows the results when objects are detected using YOLO11s object detector [2]. The results show that using the full feature set is generally better than the kpOnly feature set. Additionally, the results show that incorporating the 3D information from MoGe [5] improves the accuracy significantly. We also evaluated classification accuracy in combination with other object detection models: YOLOv8s, YOLOv8n, YOLO11n [2] and OWL-ViT [3] showing very similar results.

TABLE I

THE CLASSIFICATION ACCURACY RESULTS FOR DETERMINING WHETHER POINTING OCCURS IN AN IMAGE (SEE SEC. III-E). THE RESULTS SHOWN ARE FOR COMBINATION WITH YOLO11s [2] WITH (✓) AND WITHOUT (×) MOGE DEPTH ESTIMATION [5].

Case	MoGe	Features	Precision	Recall	F1	Accuracy
Easy	✓	kpOnly	0.53	0.86	0.66	0.77
Easy	✓	full	0.56	0.91	0.69	0.80
Hard	✓	kpOnly	0.48	0.83	0.61	0.71
Hard	✓	full	0.47	0.80	0.59	0.70
Easy	×	kpOnly	0.50	0.70	0.59	0.67
Easy	×	full	0.56	0.67	0.61	0.72
Hard	×	kpOnly	0.35	0.55	0.42	0.54
Hard	×	full	0.46	0.61	0.53	0.65

TABLE II

COMPARISON OF OBJECT RECOGNITION PERFORMANCE ACROSS VARIOUS DETECTION MODELS WITH (✓) AND WITHOUT (×) MOGE DEPTH ESTIMATION [5]. RESULTS ARE CATEGORIZED INTO EASY CASES (HORIZONTAL SEPARATION) AND HARD CASES (DEPTH-WISE OVERLAP).

Easy Cases					
Model	MoGe	Precision	Recall	F1	Accuracy
YOLOv8s	×	0.42	0.49	0.45	0.63
	✓	0.49	0.67	0.56	0.74
YOLOv8n	×	0.54	0.44	0.49	0.70
	✓	0.51	0.62	0.56	0.74
YOLO11n	×	0.46	0.39	0.43	0.65
	✓	0.53	0.72	0.61	0.76
OWL-ViT	×	0.53	0.56	0.55	0.67
	✓	0.51	0.82	0.63	0.76
Hard Cases					
Model	MoGe	Precision	Recall	F1	Accuracy
YOLOv8s	×	0.32	0.35	0.33	0.55
	✓	0.43	0.75	0.54	0.68
YOLOv8n	×	0.35	0.44	0.39	0.59
	✓	0.41	0.70	0.52	0.68
YOLO11n	×	0.44	0.43	0.44	0.64
	✓	0.41	0.69	0.51	0.67
OWL-ViT	×	0.31	0.40	0.35	0.55
	✓	0.39	0.74	0.51	0.66

B. Object Recognition

The results for pointed-at object recognition across different detection models and the impact of 3D information are summarized in Table II. The experimental data reveals a consistent and significant performance gain when integrating monocular depth estimation via MoGe [5].

In Easy Cases, where objects are primarily distributed horizontally on a single plane, the transition from 2D to 3D logic provided a noticeable boost in reliability. For instance, using YOLO11n, the accuracy increased from 0.65 to 0.76 when MoGe was enabled. Similarly, OWL-ViT achieved its highest F1-score of 0.63 and a peak recall of 0.82 in the 3D configuration, suggesting that even in simple scenes, including depth information is beneficial.

The advantage of the 3D approach is most pronounced in Hard Cases, characterized by depth-wise overlapping objects.

In these scenarios, 2D-only methods struggle significantly because a single pointing vector often pierces multiple overlapping bounding boxes. The 2D methods saw accuracy drops to as low as 0.55, while the 3D-integrated models maintained more stable performance, with YOLOv8s and YOLOv8n both reaching 0.68 accuracy. Moreover, for YOLOv8s, the recall more than doubled from 0.35 to 0.75 when 3D information was used.

Among the tested detectors, YOLO11n and OWL-ViT paired with MoGe performed best. OWL-ViT demonstrated superior recall (0.82 in Easy, 0.74 in Hard), which is particularly beneficial for HRI applications where missing a user’s intent is often more detrimental than a slight decrease in precision. The results confirm that regardless of the underlying detection architecture, the reconstruction of 3D spatial relationships is the primary driver for resolving ambiguity in monocular pointing gesture recognition.

C. Performance of Image Captioning

TABLE III

POINTED-AT OBJECT RECOGNITION RESULTS FOR YOLO11s [2] OBJECT DETECTOR COMBINED WITH DIFFERENT IMAGE CAPTIONING METHODS USED FOR CORRECTING BADLY CLASSIFIED OBJECTS (SEE SEC. III-F).

Case	Captioning	Precision	Recall	F1	Accuracy
Easy	×	0.56	0.91	0.69	0.80
	BLIP	0.58	0.92	0.71	0.81
	ViT-GPT2	0.56	0.91	0.69	0.80
	GIT	0.58	0.92	0.71	0.81
Hard	×	0.47	0.80	0.59	0.70
	BLIP	0.51	0.81	0.62	0.71
	ViT-GPT2	0.48	0.80	0.60	0.71
	GIT	0.47	0.80	0.59	0.70

In several instances, both OWL-ViT [3] and YOLO [2] misclassified objects due to lighting or unusual angles. For example, a pair of folded socks was occasionally identified as "sports ball" by the detector. However, the GIT model [8] correctly generated the caption "a pair of socks on a table," which allowed the system to correct the classification. The results for our pipeline with various image captioning models in combination with YOLO11s [2] are shown in Table III. The BLIP image captioning network [6] performed the best in terms of improved accuracy of the method.

While the captioning models are computationally more expensive and slower than the detectors, they only need to be triggered once a pointing gesture is confirmed, making them viable for near-real-time applications.

D. Limitations

Despite the improvements, the system faces challenges with extreme distances. As the distance between the user and the object increases, small errors in the estimated pointing vector result in large displacements at the target, sometimes causing the system to miss the object entirely. Additionally, the monocular depth estimation, while impressive, still lacks the millimeter precision of hardware-based depth sensors.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents an integrated pipeline for pointing-based object recognition using only monocular RGB data. By combining modern object detectors, pose estimation, monocular depth estimation, and vision-language models, we created a system that can resolve spatial ambiguities in 3D space without the need for specialized hardware.

The results demonstrate that while 2D methods are sufficient for simple layouts, 3D reconstruction is essential for handling complex, real-world environments with overlapping objects. The use of image captioning as a secondary classification check further enhances the reliability of the system. Future work may focus on integrating temporal information from video streams to smooth out jitter in the pointing vector and exploring the use of gaze estimation to further refine the user's intent.

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Proactive Soft Target Protection: Integrating Edge AI Video Analytics and Synthetic Data

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Abstract—Securing public spaces and so-called soft targets require a shift from reactive measures to proactive security systems. Although current European and national legislation (EU, Czech Republic, Slovakia) sets out strict methodological requirements for the protection of these areas, their actual implementation is limited by traditional camera systems (CCTV). These systems are primarily dependent on human operators, which leads to significant operational shortcomings due to cognitive fatigue, a large number of false alarms, and an inability to respond to dynamic threats in a timely manner. This paper analyzes the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and edge-computing-based video analytics as a necessary solution to overcome these technological barriers. However, since training accurate AI models for weapon or anomaly detection faces a lack of real training data and strict privacy restrictions (GDPR, EU AI Act), this paper proposes the use of synthetic data as a key innovation. The generation of synthetic, fully annotated 3D scenarios allows models to be trained for rare and edge cases without processing actual citizens' biometric data. The combination of domain-specific security methodologies, AI video analytics, and synthetic data thus creates a robust, reliable, and legally compliant framework for modern public space protection. This paper further outlines the requirements for synthetic data to improve the training process and defines the verification conditions required to reach a certainty threshold (e.g., verifying a weapon detection with a gunshot, verifying line crossing by direction, and keeping the human in the loop) to minimize risks.

Keywords—*soft targets, public space protection, video surveillance systems (CCTV / VSS), artificial intelligence (AI), edge computing, synthetic data, anomaly detection.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Securing public spaces and protecting so-called soft targets are currently among the highest strategic priorities within the European security architecture.

In professional discourse, soft targets are defined as publicly accessible objects, spaces, or events with a high concentration of civilians, characterized by the absence or low level of built-in physical protection against violent attacks. These include, in particular, schools and educational facilities, shopping centers, hospitals, transport hubs, religious institutions, and venues for major cultural and sporting events.

Due to their openness, easy accessibility, and often symbolic significance, these locations become highly attractive targets for a variety of attackers, whose goal is usually to maximize the number of victims and have the greatest possible psychological impact on society. Given the deteriorating security situation and the continuing threat of asymmetric attacks, it is therefore imperative to develop new, technologically advanced approaches to protecting these vulnerable areas.

The rapidly increasing capabilities of video technology and software tools for processing and evaluating captured data provide ever-improving options. To effectively leverage this positive technological trend, it is essential to align business requirements for technology with these evolving capabilities. Tasks assigned to technology should be defined in a way that fully leverages the latest technological capabilities while respecting its limitations. In this context, efficiency also means designing a cost-effective solution that offers:

- the gradual implementation of tools and phased cost distribution, with priorities set from a security perspective,
- solutions addressing the most critical requirements at an acceptable cost,
- solutions that maximize the use of existing investments (legacy infrastructure),
- a solution architecture that is sustainable in the long term.

II. SELECTED LEGISLATIVE APPROACHES

The protection of public spaces and soft targets is currently shaped by strong legislative and methodological pressure to move from a reactive approach to proactive risk management.

A. European Union

A key legislative instrument of the European Union is the Critical Entities Resilience Directive (CER 2022/2557) [1], which member states were required to implement by October 2024 and which extended protection and risk management obligations to key sectors, including transport and public administration. In parallel, the European Artificial Intelligence Act (EU AI Act) [2] came into force in August 2024,

introducing a strict framework for technological security solutions. The AI Act categorizes systems according to risk and, in order to protect fundamental rights, explicitly prohibits practices deemed to pose unacceptable risks as of early 2025, such as widespread real-time biometric identification in public spaces (except for the prevention of terrorism or the search for victims), untargeted collection of faces from the internet (facial scraping), and emotion recognition in schools and workplaces.

CER Directive (EU Directive 2022/2557 on the resilience of critical entities): A key directive that member states had to implement by October 2024. It extends risk management and protection obligations to 11 key sectors, including public administration and transport [1].

EU AI Act (Regulation 2024/1689 on artificial intelligence): The world's first comprehensive legal framework for AI, which came into force in August 2024. It introduces a risk-based approach and strictly regulates high-risk systems. At the same time, it comprehensively bans social scoring techniques and the untargeted collection of faces from the internet [2].

GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation - EU Regulation 2016/679): Strictly regulates the collection and processing of personal data, which directly affects the operation of camera systems (VSS) and the collection of biometric data [3].

EU Action Plan to Support the Protection of Public Spaces (2017): A strategic document of the European Commission that defines procedures to reduce the vulnerability of public places to terrorist attacks and promotes the concept of "Security by Design".

European standards are grounded in the "security-by-design" principle, which requires the integration of security features into architectural and urban planning.

B. Czech Republic

In the Czech Republic, methodological support for soft targets has been systematized over the long term. It is based on the methodologies of the Czech Ministry of the Interior and comprehensive tools that help operators tailor security measures to specific factors such as vulnerability, preparation time, and financial capabilities. A significant contribution is the technical standard ČSN 73 4400, effective since September 2016, which focuses on crime prevention and security management in schools. The standard not only defines specific technical measures but also sets out a comprehensive security management cycle and practically addresses the frequent conflict between security requirements and fire safety standards.

ČSN 73 4400: A key technical standard that defines a systematic approach to safety in schools. It is not just about installing technology, but about a cycle that includes a safety audit and regime measures.

Concept of Soft Target Protection: A government strategic document that launched the national protection system. However, on February 9, 2026, the Supreme Audit Office (SAO) of the Czech Republic issued a report in which it found that the Ministry of the Interior of the Czech Republic had failed to create a functioning national system for the protection of soft targets. The report directly criticized the lack of investment programs for the modernization of security elements, such as camera systems.

Methodology for the Protection of Soft Targets (MOMeC) & Basics of Soft Target Protection: Practical methodologies serving as guidelines for identifying threats, modeling security measures, and procedures for detecting abandoned luggage.

C. Slovak Republic

Critical Infrastructure Act (Act No. 367/2024 Coll.) and Strategy for the Resilience of Critical Entities in the Slovak Republic: A new law implementing the CER Directive and a concept paper approved by the government in January 2026 change the protection model from a passive to a proactive and dynamic risk management and prevention system.

Action Plan for the Protection of Soft Targets for 2025: A document approved by the Government of the Slovak Republic, which defines the introduction of accredited programs and the creation of manuals for building city camera infrastructure.

D. Objective and Problem Definition

The common denominator of the European, Czech, and Slovak legislative frameworks is strong top-down pressure to transition to sophisticated and proactive security measures in public spaces.

However, everyday practice reveals a critical problem: legislative requirements and theoretical methodologies often outpace the actual technological, personnel, and financial capabilities of ordinary operators. The methodologies directly acknowledge that many highly vulnerable soft targets do not have the budget for costly technological solutions. Entities are thus forced to comply with strict protection standards, but without the deployment of intelligent and affordable technological solutions, these efforts often remain only theoretical contingency plans that fail in the dynamics of a real incident due to the cognitive and physical limits of human attention.

III. SURVEILLANCE SYSTEMS: LIMITATIONS AND RESPONSE LOGIC

Although traditional video surveillance systems (VSS) have long been the standard in securing public spaces, their historical concept as "*passive* recorders" is reaching critical limits in the modern era. The real effectiveness of these systems in preventing incidents is significantly limited by the following factors.

A. Main problems and pitfalls of traditional VSS

- **Cognitive limits of the human factor**: The systems are completely dependent on the attention of operators. Research shows the phenomenon of attention fatigue, where operators miss approximately 45% of events after 12 minutes of monitoring and up to 95% after 20 minutes [4].
- **High false alarm rate** (false positives): Motion-based detection without contextual analysis leads to operator overload (alert fatigue). The system is unable to distinguish between real threats and normal operational events (e.g., maintenance with tools vs. an attacker, shadows, weather changes) [4].
- **Blindness to specific threats** (edge cases): Traditional technologies fail in dynamic conditions (crowds, poor lighting) and when objects are obscured (occlusion). They are unable to adapt to new tactics used by attackers, which leads to dangerous false negatives [6].

B. Response activation logic and verification mechanisms

Overcoming these limitations requires a paradigm shift in the logic by which a security response is initiated. AI model detection alone is only an initial *trigger*, which must be followed by a robust verification process to achieve a sufficient level of confidence before an alarm is raised.

This process involves multi-stage verification that combines technological and human capabilities:

Multi-Layer Soft Target Protection Framework

Fig. 1. Proposed multi-layer soft target protection framework. IP cameras feed into an edge computing device for real-time AI inference (weapon/anomaly detection, crowd analysis, perimeter monitoring). Detections pass through a multi-stage verification module (visual and audio confirmation) before reaching the human-in-the-loop operator dashboard, which triggers a graduated response. A feedback loop enables ongoing false-alarm correction.

- **Verification prerequisites for reaching a threshold of certainty:** Multimodal inputs must be used to corroborate critical event detections. For example, in the case of weapon detection (visual input), confidence exceeds the decision threshold only after the detection of a shot (audio input) or a specific aggressive posture. In the case of a perimeter breach, motion detection alone is not sufficient; direction verification is also required (e.g., entry into the zone vs. authorized exit).
- **The human-in-the-loop principle:** Even with the most advanced AI, a qualified operator must have the final say in declaring an alarm. This validation serves to minimize

false alarms, which would otherwise lead to unnecessary and costly emergency responses and panic. In some cases, an automated notification (alerting the emergency response unit for further action) may be triggered when no operator is available to perform manual verification.

- **Crisis scenarios** (e.g., evacuation): In the event of confirmed incidents such as accidents, explosions, or fires, the system must automatically provide support for evacuation (detection of escape route accessibility), while the responsibility for activating the public address system and evacuation broadcast remains with trained personnel.
- **Risks and training on synthetic data:** The greatest risk remains human error under pressure. Therefore, it is essential to use synthetic data not only for AI training, but also for training operators and emergency responders. Virtual simulations allow them to experience and practice responses to extreme situations (active shooter, crowd panic) that rarely occur in real life but require immediate and flawless responses.

CURRENT STATE OF AI APPROACHES FOR PROTECTING SOFT TARGETS

This section reviews the current state of the art (SOTA) in AI-based video analytics for security scenarios in public spaces.

A. Proactive security and technological capabilities

The current technological paradigm represents a transition from reactive surveillance to proactive security using artificial intelligence (AI) and advanced computer vision. The integration of AI transforms existing camera infrastructure into active sensors that can continuously analyze large volumes of image data. A key advantage is that these systems are deployed as a software layer on top of existing IP cameras, reducing the need for costly hardware replacement [5].

A major step forward for public spaces is decentralized data processing directly at the edge of the network (edge computing). With local processing, image data does not need to be continuously sent to remote cloud servers, which reduces latency and supports compliance with personal data protection requirements [5].

Today, modern real-time models of the YOLO family (particularly those branches validated for production deployment) are used in the detection layer, while newer variants (e.g., YOLOv12) [7] are also appearing in research. At the same time, the importance of RF-DETR-type transformer detectors is growing, as they are emerging as a leading alternative in terms of accuracy/speed [8].

B. Practical use cases

The deployment of modern VSS equipped with deep learning models brings several key application scenarios to the protection of public spaces [6].

- **Weapon Detection** is performed by new-generation real-time detectors (YOLO, RF-DETR), which are increasingly supplemented by object segmentation verification to reduce false alarms.
- **Fight and Anomaly Detection** is shifting from purely pose-based approaches to a broader multimodal and

open-vocabulary understanding of incidents, which better covers non-standard or rare situations [9].

- **Crowd analysis** no longer relies only on simple people counting, but also incorporates density estimation, anomalous trajectory detection, and temporal crowd dynamics modeling, which supports the prevention of panic and critical overcrowding [10].
- **Abandoned luggage and suspicious activities** are detected and managed through a combination of detection, tracking, and time aggregation of behavior (e.g., loitering), providing operators with sufficient time for intervention [9].

C. SOTA direction in security video analytics

Current developments are moving towards hybrid pipelines that combine fast detection, segmentation, temporal modeling, and semantic interpretation of events.

A notable trend is represented by the foundation segmentation models of the Segment Anything family; the latest SAM3 line expands the possibilities of promptable segmentation and object tracking in video, which is relevant for spatial verification of incidents in complex scenes [14].

At the same time, the importance of temporal context is growing, as security incidents are sequential in nature and require decisions to be made about the development of the situation over time, not just about an isolated frame.

At the application level, therefore, a combination of detection models, segmentation models, and a higher semantic layer (including multimodal VLM) is being promoted, which increases the robustness of the system and reduces the rate of false alarms in real-world public spaces [10] [16].

IV. TRAINING DATA: REAL VS. SYNTHETIC

Overcoming the limitations of traditional VSS requires the deployment of AI video analytics based on deep learning models. However, this is not the only possible solution, but rather the dominant technological direction, whose performance is directly dependent on the quality, scope, and representativeness of the training data.

A. The problem with real data

For modern detection models (e.g., current YOLO branches and RF-DETR transformer detectors) [7], [8] to reliably recognize weapons, aggression, and anomalous behavior, they require extensive and well-annotated data. However, real CCTV data often does not contain enough rare incidents (active attacks, crowd panic, complex borderline scenarios), resulting in datasets that are imbalanced and lack variability.

The collection and processing of real recordings are also limited by legal and ethical requirements. When working with image data of individuals, it is necessary to comply with the GDPR [3] and the requirements of the AI Act [2] for high-risk systems. Non-targeted collection of faces from public sources (facial scraping) for database creation is prohibited in the EU, and the operation of AI security systems must be based on a clear legal basis, purpose limitation, and appropriate technical and organizational measures.

B. The contribution of synthetic data

Synthetic data is an important tool for expanding training sets [11], [12], [13], especially for rare and dangerous scenarios that are difficult or unethical to obtain in real-world operations. In practice, 3D simulation environments (Unreal Engine, Unity, Blender) are used, in which security scenarios can be generated with a high degree of control over the scene and at the same time obtain accurate annotations (bounding boxes, masks, depth, tracking ID, trajectories) [15].

Synthetic Data Generation and Hybrid Training Pipeline

Fig. 2. Synthetic data generation and hybrid training pipeline. Parameterized 3D scenes (Blender) produce rendered sequences with

automatic ground-truth annotations (bounding boxes, instance masks, tracking IDs). Synthetic datasets are combined with real CCTV calibration data in a hybrid training protocol that addresses the sim-to-real domain gap via domain randomization [11]. Trained models are deployed on edge devices and continuously monitored through an evaluation and retraining loop.

This approach allows for the systematic modeling of edge cases (different camera angles, occlusions, lighting, smoke/fog, crowd density) and increases the robustness of models against environmental changes. Generative models, including diffusion models, are used as an additional layer to increase visual variability and data distribution coverage.

C. Limitations and methodological additions

Synthetic data significantly reduces barriers to dataset creation but does not eliminate the need for real validation data. A key technical challenge remains *the "domain gap"* — the distributional difference between simulated and real-world CCTV imagery. In practice, a hybrid approach is therefore used: synthetic data to cover edge cases and targeted real data for calibration and performance verification.

Synthetic data therefore does not fully replace real data across all tasks, but serves as a critical enabler for the development, testing, and hardening of AI video analytics pipelines for the protection of soft targets.

D. Implementation strategy and operational sustainability of AI video analytics

The effectiveness of AI video analytics in protecting soft targets must be evaluated systematically, not just by isolated detection metrics. The key indicators are the false alarm rate, alarm verification time, performance stability over time, operational availability, and impact on operator cognitive load. From a long-term sustainability perspective, pipeline reproducibility, decision auditability, and ongoing validation against changing operating conditions are also critical.

A multi-phase implementation model appears to be methodologically appropriate. In the pilot phase, the goal is to verify technical feasibility on a representative subset of cameras with precisely defined KPIs and a reference baseline. The subsequent calibration phase includes domain fine-tuning of models, optimization of decision thresholds, and a combination of synthetic and real data to reduce domain shift. The integration phase involves expansion to multiple locations, standardization of the MLOps process (drift monitoring, model versioning, controlled retraining), and formalization of operational governance, including incident response protocols. The production phase is characterized by continuous evaluation, periodic rebenchmarking, and updating of model components in response to new types of threats.

This structured implementation minimizes the risk of premature technological escalation, allows for the gradual accumulation of evidence of effectiveness, and supports the long-term economic, technical, and regulatory sustainability of the system in the context of public space protection.

E. Proposed framework and technical contribution.

The specific contribution of this work is a domain-tailored framework for integrating synthetic data into the training and validation pipeline of AI video analytics for soft target protection. The framework comprises four components: (1) a typology of security-relevant scene classes (weapon visibility, crowd anomaly, perimeter breach, abandoned object); (2) a

structured 3D scene generation methodology using Blender, parameterizing camera placement, lighting, occlusion levels, actor density, and weapon types, with automatic export of bounding-box and instance segmentation annotations; (3) a hybrid training protocol combining synthetic data for rare and edge-case coverage with targeted real CCTV data for domain calibration, addressing the sim-to-real gap through domain randomization [11]; and (4) a deployment-ready edge AI verification logic incorporating multi-modal event confirmation and human-in-the-loop validation as described in Section III. The framework will be validated against real surveillance footage collected within the InnovAIte project under an appropriate legal basis.

V. CONCLUSION

The protection of public spaces and soft targets against asymmetric threats requires a comprehensive paradigm shift from a reactive approach to a proactive risk management system. While European, Czech, and Slovak methodological frameworks and legislation provide a strong theoretical foundation based on the principles of "security-by-design," their real-world application is often constrained by the limits of human attention, budget constraints, and the technological inadequacy of traditional camera systems (VSS).

As this analysis has shown, the key to overcoming these barriers is the integration of artificial intelligence and advanced video analytics into hybrid multi-layer pipelines. Transforming passive cameras into active sensors through deep learning models, temporal modeling of incidents, and edge computing provides security forces with the ability to detect threats such as weapons, crowd anomalies, and abandoned luggage earlier, shifting the focus from post-incident forensic analysis towards proactive prevention and faster response.

A fundamental innovative step towards the sustainability, reliability, and ethical acceptability of these systems is the use of synthetic data. The generation of synthetic, fully annotated 3D scenarios allows AI models to be trained for extreme and edge cases that rarely occur in real-world operations or are difficult to capture ethically. Synthetic data also significantly reduces barriers to working with sensitive data, but in practice it does not completely replace real validation data; the highest robustness is achieved by a hybrid approach combining synthetic data to cover edge cases and targeted real data for performance calibration.

The future of public space protection does not lie in restricting public access, but in intelligent, auditable, and operationally sustainable monitoring. A combination of domain security readiness, automated AI video analytics, synthetic data, and a phased implementation strategy creates a robust framework that allows public spaces to remain open while increasing their level of protection.

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Mobile applications and their functions in the field of waste separation

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Abstract—Correct household waste sorting is a prerequisite for high-quality recycling streams, yet citizens often face item-level uncertainty caused by composite packaging, inconsistent local rules, and limited feedback at the point of disposal. This paper synthesizes evidence on citizen information needs and reviews representative European mobile applications supporting household waste separation. We structure recurring sorting decisions into six question categories and map them to common app functionalities, ranging from text search and collection calendars to barcode scanning, image-based recognition, and rule-grounded conversational assistants. We further summarize feasible AI approaches for mobile workflows, including vision-based recognition and retrieval-augmented language models grounded in municipality-specific guidelines. Based on the synthesis, we propose a prioritized feature set for citizen-facing applications that emphasizes reliable localization of rules, low-friction item identification (text, barcode, photo), evidence-linked explanations, and lightweight engagement mechanisms. The resulting recommendations provide actionable guidance for municipalities and developers seeking to balance implementation complexity with measurable value in reducing contamination and improving user adherence.

Keywords—waste sorting, recycling, mobile applications, circular economy, computer vision, retrieval-augmented generation

I. INTRODUCTION

Municipal solid waste management is increasingly framed within the circular economy, which aims to reduce dependence on virgin resources by keeping materials in use and supporting closed-loop systems whenever feasible [1]. Achieving these goals depends not only on collection infrastructure but also on the quality of household source separation. In practice, sorting errors and contamination of recyclable streams remain persistent challenges, often driven by item-level uncertainty and variability in municipality-specific sorting rules.

Citizen-facing digital tools, particularly smartphone applications, offer a scalable channel for providing timely, localized guidance at the point of disposal. Experimental evidence indicates that dedicated recycling applications can support pro-recycling attitudes and perceived usefulness, which are associated with continued use [2]. Technology adoption studies further suggest that intentions to use recycling applications are shaped by acceptance factors such

as performance expectancy and facilitating conditions, implying that practical impact depends on both content quality and usability [3].

Beyond individual studies, integrative reviews highlight that digitalization can improve information flows and decision-making in waste management [4]. However, information provision alone may not sustain behavior change. Systematic evaluations of sustainable waste-management applications report frequent use of persuasive design strategies—such as personalization, reminders, effort reduction, and self-monitoring—that can strengthen engagement and adherence [5]. In parallel, computer vision methods have been applied to waste image classification, demonstrating the potential of AI-assisted recognition to reduce user effort while supporting categorization accuracy [6]. Behavioral mechanisms remain critical: normative feedback can influence behavior but may trigger “boomerang” effects for high-performing users unless designed carefully [7], and economic instruments such as performance-dependent waste fees have been associated with increased recycling and composting in municipal contexts [8]. Gamified and incentive-oriented platforms have also been examined as tools to promote informed recycling, indicating that reinforcement and peer influence can enhance learning and engagement when aligned with behavioral determinants [9].

This paper makes three contributions: (i) it structures recurring citizen information needs during everyday sorting decisions, (ii) it reviews representative features observed in European mobile applications supporting waste sorting, and (iii) it summarizes feasible AI-assisted approaches for item identification and rule-grounded guidance. Based on this synthesis, we propose an evidence-informed, prioritized set of recommended functionalities to help municipalities and developers balance implementation complexity with expected value in reducing contamination and improving adherence.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section II formulates recurring decision questions at the point of disposal; Section III reviews representative application feature patterns; Section IV summarizes feasible AI approaches for mobile sorting workflows; and Section V consolidates prioritized implementation recommendations.

II. KEY QUESTIONS FOR EFFECTIVE WASTE SORTING

Effective household waste sorting can be viewed as a sequence of recurring micro-decisions made at the point of disposal. These decisions are shaped by municipality-specific collection schemes, accepted fractions, and operational constraints of sorting and recycling facilities, which together

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contribute to contamination risks and recurring user confusion [4], [5]. For the purposes of this study, we structure common information needs into six question categories:

1) *What goes where?* Residents require an item-level bin assignment under local rules. Even when broad categories appear universal, accepted items and fraction definitions differ across municipalities.

2) *Is it a single material or a composite?* Everyday products often include multi-layer packaging or mixed materials. Correct sorting depends on recognizing composites and understanding how they are treated locally.

3) *Should the item be separated into parts?* Sorting may require disassembly (caps, pumps, labels, sleeves, inserts). Residents must know when separation improves recoverability versus when it is unnecessary or discouraged.

4) *Are there local exceptions to general rules?* Items that seem recyclable may be excluded due to logistics or downstream processing limitations. Local exceptions are therefore frequent sources of avoidable errors.

5) *Which items should never be placed in recycling bins?* Hazardous waste, electronics, batteries, and safety-risk items must be excluded to protect collection and sorting operations.

6) *Is the item sufficiently empty and clean?* Guidance is needed on emptying/cleaning thresholds that reduce contamination without imposing excessive effort or water use.

III. COMPARISON OF MOBILE APPLICATIONS

This section reviews representative citizen-facing mobile applications available in Europe that support waste separation, collection logistics, and user engagement. Applications were selected to cover (i) guidance-first designs focused on item-level sorting decisions, (ii) logistics support (collection calendars, reminders, and collection-point maps), and (iii) engagement mechanisms such as gamification or rewards. Publicly available descriptions (official websites and app store listings) were used to identify primary functionalities and claimed advanced features (see [10]–[19], [22]–[34]). The goal is not to provide an exhaustive market inventory but to summarize recurring feature patterns relevant to the decision needs in Section II.

Table 1 provides an overview of selected applications. Ecoembes' A.I.R-e offers conversational assistance for recycling questions and photo-based guidance [10], [11]. Bower illustrates a reward-oriented model combining identification (barcode and image-based recognition) with incentives, with public documentation describing its use of Google Cloud services for recognition workflows [12]. Digi-Cycle links product identification to location-dependent disposal rules and collection points [13], [14]. In the Czech context, Kam s ním? represents a directory-style approach combining search with mapping of appropriate disposal locations, including special waste streams [15]. TrashOut focuses on community reporting of illegal dumps and locating nearby recycling points [16]. Sensoneo's Citizen App is positioned as an interface to sensor-enabled waste infrastructure in smart-city deployments (e.g., bin locations and fill-level information) [17]. Overall, the reviewed applications suggest that core value is typically achieved by reducing user uncertainty through localized instructions and/or access to relevant disposal infrastructure, while

advanced features vary substantially across products. Information summarized in Tables 1–3 was extracted from official websites and/or app store listings of the respective solutions [10]–[19], [22]–[34].

TABLE I. SELECTED CITIZEN-FACING APPLICATIONS SUPPORTING WASTE SORTING AND RECYCLING.

App Name	Country	Main Functionality	AI / Advanced Features
A.I.R-e (Ecoembes)	Spain	AI chatbot and sorting assistant for all types of packaging	AI-powered image recognition and NLP chatbot to identify waste from photos.
Bower (Plovie)	Germany / Spain	Global app that rewards users for recycling. Scans packaging to find local bins.	AI recognition (Google Gemini) identifies items without barcodes via camera.
Digi-Cycle	Austria / Germany	Local sorting guide and recycling center map based on specific product data.	Barcode scanning & data-driven sorting advice for specific brands.
Kam s ním?	Czechia	Interactive map for legal waste disposal (medicine, bulk, textiles, etc.).	Extensive database of collection points & "Where to throw it" search engine.
TrashOut	Slovakia / Czechia	Mapping illegal dumps and locating nearest recycling collection points.	Crowdsourced waste mapping and collection schedules.
Gdzie wyrzucić śmieci?	Poland	Search engine for sorting rules (primarily Warsaw, but applicable elsewhere).	Smart search database covering over 1,000 types of waste.
Green Bin	Slovakia	Comprehensive sorting guide and collection calendar for Slovak municipalities.	Notifications for collection dates and sorting "cheat sheets" for households.
Waste Monitoring App	Slovakia	Poor navigation and low engagement further undermine sustainable waste management.	Citizens lack real-time information on nearby bins and fill levels, leading to overflowing waste and dirty streets.

To further examine engagement mechanisms, Table 2 summarizes applications that motivate participation through rewards.

TABLE II. REWARD-ORIENTED APPLICATIONS AND INCENTIVE MECHANISMS.

App Name	Country	Type of reward	How it works?
Bower (Plovie)	CZ, SK, PL, DE, ES	Cash, coupons	Scan the barcode on the packaging, throw it away in the trash, and earn points that can be converted into cash or discounts (payout provider depends on region).
Moje Odpadky (MESOH)	CZ	Discount on waste disposal fees	A unique Czech system. You earn points for sorting waste into marked bags, which will reduce your municipal fees by up to 70% at the end of the year.

TABLE II. REWARD-ORIENTED APPLICATIONS AND INCENTIVE MECHANISMS (CONTINUED).

App Name	Country	Type of reward	How it works?
RecycleMich	AT, DE	Coupons (e.g., Lidl, McDonald's, etc.)	A widely used Austrian incentive app. You scan aluminum and plastic packaging. You win weekly prizes or monthly vouchers for the points you collect.
Reciclos (Ecoembes)	ES	Material prizes, raffles, gifts	National-scale Spanish incentive program. You earn points for scanning cans and PET bottles, which you can use to enter competitions to win bikes, scooters, or donate to charity.
RecomApp	PL	Discounts in stores	It works with bottle vending machines in Poland. You can exchange points for returned packaging for discount codes at partner stores.
Sorteusz	PL	Points and game rewards	A gamified app where you climb the rankings and earn rewards for sorting correctly and adding new products to the database.
TrashOut	CZ, SK, Global	Badges and community recognition	It focuses on reporting illegal dumps. The reward is an "Environmental Profile" and points for your municipality in the global rankings.
Zálohujte.sk (DRS)	SK	Money EUR 0.15/ package	It is not just one app, but a system. Many Slovak chains (Lidl, Kaufland) integrate bottle purchases into their loyalty point apps.
EcoScan	DE	Discount coupons	It uses AI to identify packaging materials and offers discounts on eco-friendly products from partner brands.
CleanSpot	ES	Local benefits	It tracks your carbon footprint. In some Spanish cities, points can be exchanged for tickets to cultural events or public transport.

Ecoembes' RECICLOS provides an example of an app-mediated return-and-reward approach for specific packaging categories [18] and is described as a good practice within the EU Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform [19]. These examples indicate that incentives can be implemented either as a primary design goal (reward-first apps) or as a supporting layer complementing guidance functions.

Finally, Table 3 focuses on scanning and recognition capabilities used to address the primary citizen barrier identified in Section II—uncertainty about the correct disposal bin.

TABLE III. SCANNING AND RECOGNITION APPROACHES IN SELECTED APPLICATIONS.

App Name	Country	Scanning Type	Reported technology / approach
Bower (Plovie)	Global (CZ, SK, DE, ES)	Photo & Barcode	Google Gemini AI - Recognizes objects without barcodes
A.I.R-e (Ecoembes)	Spain	Photo	Custom AI Chatbot - Analyzes images sent via chat
EcoScan	Germany / EU	Photo & Barcode	Material Recognition - Identifies composite materials
SORTaPP	Czechia	Photo (Symbols)	Image Recognition - Identifies recycling symbols
Sorteusz	Poland	Barcode	Database API - Massive EAN library for Poland
Digi-Cycle	Austria / Germany	Barcode	Location-based Logic - Matches EAN with local rules
RecycleMich	Austria	Barcode	Incentivized Scanning - Rewards for scanning packaging
Scrapp	Germany / Global	Barcode	Global Library - Barcode scan + item search; guidance according to local rules
ReciclaYa	Spain	Barcode & Receipts	Retail Integration - Scans receipts for sorting info

Across the reviewed applications, scanning is implemented through barcode lookup, symbol interpretation, and photo-based recognition. Barcode-based approaches typically rely on structured product databases and location-dependent rule logic [13], [14]. Photo-based recognition can reduce friction when barcodes are missing; however, practical usefulness depends on recognition robustness, coverage of item categories, and consistent mapping to local rules. Overall, the most effective patterns combine fast identification with localized instructions and lightweight engagement features (e.g., reminders, feedback, or rewards) that support repeated correct behavior.

IV. AI- ASSISTED APPROACHES FOR MOBILE WASTE-SORTING APPLICATIONS

A common computer-vision task in citizen-facing recycling applications is to recognize a packaging item from a camera frame captured on a mobile device and translate that recognition into a specific sorting instruction. In practice, this can be implemented by applying a deep-learning vision model (e.g., CNN- or transformer/ViT-based classifier and/or object detector) to estimate the item category or material, and subsequently mapping the prediction—optionally together with confidence scores or top-k candidates—to a product database and municipality-specific sorting rules to generate a “where to dispose” recommendation.

Recent research explores transformer-based detectors extended with instance segmentation (e.g., RF-DETR-Seg [20]) to localize packaging items and produce object masks, which may improve robustness for small or partially occluded objects in cluttered scenes. In parallel, promptable segmentation models (e.g., SAM 3 [21]) can support segmentation guided by text prompts or visual exemplars (reference images), enabling exemplar-guided pipelines that isolate relevant item parts prior to labeling and rule mapping. In deployment, these approaches are typically combined with explicit uncertainty handling (e.g., requesting user

confirmation, asking a clarifying question, or falling back to text search) when model confidence is insufficient.

AI support for barcodes and recycling symbols is commonly implemented by scanning an EAN/QR code and/or detecting standardized recycling marks (via OCR or symbol recognition), then resolving the extracted identifier against a product database and mapping it to municipality-specific sorting rules to return an item-level instruction.

For conversational guidance (“chatting about how to sort”), the key requirement is that responses must follow municipality-specific rules rather than generic recycling advice. A practical approach is to ground the language model in authoritative local regulations and collection guidelines via retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) over curated municipal documents. Alternatively, larger rule sets may be provided through longer-context prompting; however, reliable operation still benefits from explicit grounding, versioning of rule sources, and clear evidence-linked explanations. In a mobile sorting workflow, a chat assistant can act as a follow-up layer after visual recognition to handle clarifying questions (e.g., composite packaging, disassembly, local exceptions) and provide an actionable instruction with a short rationale.

In addition, multimodal vision–language models (VLMs) can unify perception and dialogue by jointly interpreting the camera input and the user’s natural-language query, enabling end-to-end “see-and-explain” assistance. For reliable use in municipalities, such models still require grounding in local sorting rules (e.g., via RAG) to avoid locality-inconsistent recommendations.

V. RECOMMENDED MOBILE APP FEATURES TO SUPPORT WASTE SORTING

This section consolidates recommended application features aligned with the decision needs in Section II and with evidence on engagement and behavior-change strategies in sustainability applications [5], [7], [9]. Features are ordered by expected citizen value at the point of disposal, prioritizing reliable localization of rules, low-friction item identification, and supportive feedback mechanisms.

A. Automatic location and municipality selection

Detect and confirm user location to activate municipality-specific sorting rules and collection schedules; resolve ambiguous place names and allow manual override.

B. Collection calendar and reminders

Provide a localized calendar with reminders configurable by fraction and timing; clearly indicate what should be set out for each collection event.

C. Text-based search (“Where does it go?”)

Support natural-language queries mapped to local bins; ask clarifying questions for ambiguous items (e.g., soiled vs clean, single vs composite).

D. Gamification (challenges, points, badges)

Use transparent engagement mechanisms to support repeated correct behavior; avoid designs that may trigger unintended effects (e.g., discouraging already high-performing users) [7], and align incentives with learning goals [9].

E. Barcode scan to sorting instructions

Decode EAN/QR codes, resolve to product records, infer packaging composition where possible, and handle unknown products via user feedback loops.

F. Photo recognition of waste items

Apply vision-based recognition to identify item/material categories; provide step-by-step disposal guidance and robust fallbacks when confidence is low.

G. Chat assistant grounded in local rules

Provide conversational clarification for edge cases; ground answers in municipal sources (e.g., via RAG) and return evidence-linked explanations to reduce unsupported outputs.

H. Map of nearby recycling points and yards

Recommend suitable drop-off locations by accepted waste types, distance, and opening hours; support accessibility considerations.

I. Special-waste finder (e-waste, medicines, batteries)

Detect hazardous/special categories, show legal drop-off points, and provide safety-oriented instructions.

J. Reporting overflowing or damaged bins

Enable structured reporting with photos/text; deduplicate and route reports to the responsible operator.

K. Personalized learning support (optional, consent-based)

Detect recurring user errors and provide targeted tips and micro-learning modules [5].

L. Push notifications for exceptions and changes

Communicate temporary exceptions and rule changes to affected areas only to reduce alert fatigue.

M. Offline mode (cached rules)

Cache essential rule content for basic guidance offline and synchronize updates when online.

N. Accessibility features

Support voice input, adjustable typography, simplified explanations, and screen-reader compatibility.

O. Evidence-linked outputs

Attach links to authoritative municipal/operator sources for key guidance steps; provide uncertainty indicators and request clarification when needed.

P. User feedback loop (correct/incorrect)

Collect correction signals and monitor systematic confusion to improve rules, UI text, and model performance.

Q. PAYT/fee insights (where supported)

Explain local fee rules and offer user-consented insights linked to reduction of mixed waste [8].

R. Smart-bin fill-level guidance (where sensors exist)

Support sensor-integrated scenarios by recommending available bins and alternatives in overflow situations [17].

Taken together, the recommendations suggest that the highest citizen value is created by: (i) reliable localization of rules, (ii) low-friction item identification (text, barcode, photo), and (iii) timely behavioral support (calendar, reminders, targeted notifications). Advanced layers (gamification, analytics, operator integrations) should be

added only after the core guidance achieves sufficient accuracy and adoption.

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CONCLUSION

This paper reviewed recurring citizen decision needs during household waste sorting and mapped them to representative features observed in European mobile applications. The analysis confirms that reliable localization of sorting rules, low-friction item identification (text, barcode, and photo recognition), and timely logistical support (collection calendars and reminders) provide the highest citizen value at the point of disposal. Advanced engagement mechanisms such as gamification and reward systems demonstrate potential to sustain correct sorting behavior.

Feasible AI approaches for mobile workflows include CNN- and transformer-based vision models for item recognition, barcode and symbol resolution against product databases with municipality-specific rule mapping, and retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) for conversational assistants grounded in local regulations. Multimodal vision-language models offer a promising direction for unified perception and dialogue, but reliable deployment still requires explicit grounding in authoritative local sources.

Based on the synthesis, we proposed a prioritized feature set balancing implementation complexity with expected impact on contamination reduction and user adherence. The recommendations provide actionable guidance for municipalities and developers, with the most critical priority being consistent and verifiable localization of sorting rules before adding advanced identification or engagement layers.

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The role of anonymization in AI solutions for claims processing

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Abstract—Artificial intelligence is increasingly used in insurance claims processing to automate document analysis, fraud detection, and decision support. These systems operate on large volumes of unstructured claims documentation containing personally identifiable and sensitive information, raising significant privacy and regulatory concerns. Under frameworks such as the GDPR, the distinction between anonymization and pseudonymization is critical, particularly when AI models are trained on processed claims data. This paper presents an agent-based anonymization pipeline integrated into a document-centric claims workflow. The solution combines OCR extraction, LLM-based identifier detection, cryptographic tokenization, and a strict quality gate prior to data persistence. The approach is experimentally validated on synthetic claims data to evaluate detection reliability, residual risk, and operational feasibility. The study demonstrates how privacy-by-design principles can be embedded directly into AI processing pipelines while preserving analytical utility.

Keywords—*anonymization, claims, irreversible tokenization, synthetic data*

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid digital transformation of the insurance industry has led to increasing adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) in claims processing, including document classification, fraud detection, automated damage assessment, and decision support. These AI-driven solutions rely on large volumes of historical claims data, which typically contain sensitive personal, medical, and financial information. According to the European Insurance and Occupational Pensions Authority (EIOPA), approximately 50% of non-life insurers in Europe already use AI applications, while a further significant proportion plan implementation within the next three years; adoption in life insurance, although lower (around one quarter of firms), is steadily increasing [1].

Under the GDPR, personal data may be processed only where a valid lawful basis exists. When considering the data necessary for AI development, this often includes previously collected datasets, such as historical claims data. In many cases, however, such data was not originally gathered with AI development purposes in mind, and therefore a suitable legal basis for this new form of processing may be absent. This issue becomes particularly complex when dealing with personal data related to claims, which may include sensitive information. Identifying an appropriate lawful basis for using such data in AI development can therefore be legally challenging. The relevance of this problem is further

underscored by the proposal within the EU Digital Omnibus, where EU legislators have suggested amending the GDPR to explicitly recognize legitimate interest as a potential lawful basis for AI development activities. This initiative clearly reflects the growing importance of addressing legal uncertainty in the context of digital innovation. Until a clear and applicable legal basis is established, the use of anonymized data for AI development remains the most viable solution.

Anonymization and related privacy-enhancing techniques are therefore becoming critical components of AI system design in insurance environments. However, excessive anonymization may degrade data utility and reduce model accuracy, while insufficient protection may expose organizations to regulatory and reputational risks. To systematically evaluate this trade-off, this study tests a selected anonymization method on synthetically generated claims data, enabling controlled experimentation without exposing real personal information. The objective is to assess how the applied anonymization technique influences data structure, information retention, and the performance of AI models in a simulated claims processing scenario.

II. PROBLEM DEFINITION

A. Pseudonymized Data

Under Article 4(5) GDPR, pseudonymization refers to processing personal data so that it can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without additional information, which must be kept separately and protected by technical and organizational measures. However, pseudonymized data remain personal data under Article 4(1), as re-identification is still possible if a linking mechanism exists. In AI-based claims processing, replacing identifiers such as names or policy numbers with artificial ones does not remove the data from GDPR scope. If the controller or another party can reasonably re-link the data to individuals, GDPR obligations continue to apply, including lawful basis, data minimization, purpose limitation, and data subject rights. Even if re-identification is unlikely, the theoretical possibility under Recital 26 is sufficient for classification as personal data. Therefore, using pseudonymized claims data for AI training still requires full GDPR compliance. Pseudonymization reduces risk but does not eliminate regulatory responsibility.

B. Truly Anonymized Data

In contrast, data are considered anonymized only if individuals are no longer identifiable by any means reasonably

likely to be used, as defined in Recital 26 GDPR. True anonymization requires irreversible de-identification, meaning re-identification is not practically feasible given available technology, costs, time, and auxiliary information. Once data are genuinely anonymized, they no longer qualify as personal data and fall outside the scope of GDPR. In AI-driven claims processing, this would allow the use of anonymized datasets for model training without relying on a legal basis under Article 6 or 9 GDPR. However, achieving true anonymization in high-dimensional insurance datasets is technically challenging, particularly when data include rare events or detailed medical information. Furthermore, emerging attacks such as membership inference and model inversion raise concerns about indirect data exposure. Consequently, the threshold for anonymization is high and must be assessed using a risk-based approach, ensuring that re-identification risk remains negligible.

C. Synthetic Data

Synthetic data are increasingly considered a promising privacy-preserving alternative to real-world datasets in regulated industries such as insurance. Unlike pseudonymized data, which remain within the scope of GDPR, properly generated synthetic data may fall outside the definition of personal data if no re-identification is reasonably possible. In AI-driven claims processing, such datasets can replicate statistical properties of original data without exposing personal, medical, or financial information. From a compliance perspective, synthetic data reduce reliance on legal bases under Articles 6 or 9 GDPR, lower the risk of data breaches, and support privacy-by-design principles under Article 25 GDPR. However, their compliance value depends on the generation method and residual disclosure risk. Poorly designed models may memorize rare records, enabling reconstruction or membership inference attacks. Therefore, safeguards such as differential privacy or exclusion of high-risk attributes are essential. Synthetic data are particularly useful for model prototyping and testing under controlled conditions. Nevertheless, regulatory uncertainty remains in cases where statistical similarity allows indirect inference. Consequently, their use should be supported by formal risk assessment and documentation demonstrating negligible re-identification risk under Recital 26 GDPR.

III. METHODS

This section outlines selected anonymization and privacy-preserving techniques relevant to AI-based claims processing. The methods are discussed conceptually; however, the implemented pipeline specifically employs irreversible tokenization as described in Section V.

Data masking replaces sensitive attributes (e.g., names, identification numbers, policy numbers) with fictitious or obfuscated values while preserving the overall structural format of the dataset. It is commonly used in testing environments and development pipelines. Although masking reduces direct identifiability, it does not eliminate linkage risk when quasi-identifiers remain intact. Consequently, masked data typically remain classified as personal data under GDPR. While straightforward to implement, masking provides limited protection against re-identification through auxiliary information.

Generalization reduces data granularity by replacing specific values with broader categories (e.g., exact age \rightarrow age range; ZIP code \rightarrow region) [2]. This approach supports

privacy models such as k-anonymity by increasing equivalence class sizes and reducing record uniqueness. Generalization preserves overall statistical distributions while lowering identifiability risk. However, excessive generalization may degrade predictive features and reduce model performance in AI applications. Achieving an appropriate privacy–utility balance is therefore essential.

Suppression removes high-risk attributes or rare records entirely from the dataset. It is often applied selectively to attribute combinations that increase re-identification risk. While suppression strengthens privacy guarantees, it may distort data distributions and reduce model robustness. In fraud detection scenarios, excessive suppression may negatively affect minority class representation. Suppression is frequently combined with generalization in structured datasets.

k-Anonymity ensures that each record is indistinguishable from at least $k-1$ other record with respect to selected quasi-identifiers [3]. It is widely applied in structured insurance datasets containing demographic or claim-related attributes. The method reduces re-identification risk through grouping into equivalence classes. However, it does not inherently protect against attribute disclosure or homogeneity attacks. Extensions such as l-diversity and t-closeness mitigate some of these weaknesses but increase complexity.

Differential privacy introduces mathematically calibrated noise into data or model outputs to limit the influence of any single individual record [4]. It provides formal privacy guarantees independent of external auxiliary information. In machine learning contexts, differential privacy can be applied during preprocessing or directly within training algorithms (e.g., DP-SGD). While offering strong theoretical guarantees, privacy budgets must be carefully tuned, as excessive noise may significantly reduce model accuracy. Differential privacy is increasingly regarded as a rigorous privacy-preserving framework in AI systems.

Irreversible tokenization replaces sensitive identifiers with cryptographic hash values generated using salted hashing mechanisms [5]. The inclusion of a secret salt mitigates dictionary and brute-force attacks by ensuring that identical identifiers cannot be easily reversed or precomputed. This approach preserves deterministic consistency across records while preventing direct reconstruction of original identifiers. However, under GDPR, salted hashing generally constitutes pseudonymization rather than full anonymization, as theoretical re-identification may remain possible through auxiliary data or access to the salt. While cryptographically strong hashing significantly reduces disclosure risk, it does not automatically remove data from regulatory scope. In the proposed pipeline, this hash-based tokenization mechanism is the primary transformation method applied during the anonymization stage.

IV. RELATED WORK

AI has become a central enabler of digital transformation in insurance, particularly in claims automation, fraud detection, and document-centric decision support. A recent industry-oriented review synthesizes how AI is being operationalized across underwriting and claims workflows while emphasizing governance, data quality, and regulatory compliance challenges [6]. In fraud analytics, generative and hybrid deep learning approaches combining variational autoencoders (VAE), generative adversarial networks

(GANs), and diffusion models have demonstrated performance gains on imbalanced auto insurance datasets [7]. Likewise, GAN-based synthetic data generation has been explored to augment minority classes and improve classifier robustness in fraud detection scenarios [8]. These works confirm the increasing reliance on advanced generative modeling in insurance analytics.

Rocher et al. demonstrate that incomplete datasets can still enable successful re-identification when combined with generative inference techniques [9]. Their findings underscore the necessity of adversarial risk assessment when evaluating anonymization strategies in high-dimensional data typical of insurance claims.

To mitigate privacy risks while preserving analytical value, privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) have been extensively studied for machine learning pipelines. A recent overview of privacy threats and countermeasures in ML systems highlights differential privacy (DP), homomorphic encryption, and secure multi-party computation as key approaches for reducing disclosure risk across the ML lifecycle [10]. Differential privacy has been applied to tabular data generation and model training, offering formal privacy guarantees against membership inference and record reconstruction. Contemporary surveys categorize DP-based tabular synthesis methods and discuss evaluation dimensions such as fidelity, utility, and robustness under centralized and distributed settings [11]. Empirical studies further assess differentially private synthetic data in end-to-end ML pipelines, showing that carefully calibrated DP mechanisms can retain competitive predictive performance while improving fairness and limiting leakage [12].

Beyond DP, deep generative models are increasingly used to produce synthetic tabular data that replicate statistical structure without directly exposing identifiable records. Systematic reviews of deep learning-based synthetic data generation in regulated domains (e.g., healthcare) analyze GAN, VAE, and diffusion approaches with respect to privacy and downstream utility [13]. Additional syntheses examine synthetic tabular data through unified taxonomies and evaluation criteria, including realism, representativeness, and attack resilience [14]. More recent methods integrate optimization objectives to balance privacy and fairness in synthetic data production, aiming to mitigate bias while constraining re-identification risk [15].

Despite substantial progress in generative modeling and privacy-preserving ML, limited empirical work evaluates structured anonymization pipelines tailored to document-centric insurance claims workflows. Few studies investigate the combined impact of (i) selective removal of direct identifiers, (ii) partial generalization of quasi-identifiers, and (iii) irreversible tokenization on downstream AI performance within operational claims systems. Moreover, the interaction between anonymization strength, synthetic data utility, re-identification risk, and predictive accuracy remains underexplored in insurance-like environments characterized by heterogeneous document formats and OCR-derived features.

Addressing this gap, the present study evaluates a structured anonymization pipeline applied to synthetic yet structurally realistic claims data. The analysis focuses on the privacy-utility trade-off under regulatory constraints and

quantifies how anonymization decisions influence AI model performance in a claims processing setting.

V. PROPOSED SOLUTION

A. Input Data

Personally Identifiable Information (PII) refers to any information that can be used to directly or indirectly identify a specific individual. PII includes direct identifiers such as name, surname, national identification number, policy number, address, email address, or phone number, as well as indirect identifiers (quasi-identifiers) that may enable identification when combined with other data, such as date of birth, ZIP code, or employment information. In the context of insurance claims processing, PII is commonly embedded in claim forms, supporting documentation, and communication records. Under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), PII falls within the definition of “personal data” (Article 4(1)), meaning that any processing of such data is subject to regulatory obligations, including lawful basis, purpose limitation, and data minimization. Effective anonymization or pseudonymization strategies must therefore specifically address both direct and indirect identifiers to reduce re-identification risk.

Protected Health Information (PHI) refers to individually identifiable health-related data that relate to a person’s physical or mental health condition, provision of healthcare services, or payment for healthcare. While the term PHI originates from the U.S. Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA), its conceptual equivalent in the European context corresponds to “special categories of personal data” under Article 9 GDPR, which include health data. In insurance claims processing, PHI may appear in medical reports, diagnostic codes, injury descriptions, treatment records, or hospital invoices submitted as part of claims documentation. Because health data are classified as sensitive data, their processing is subject to stricter legal requirements and heightened protection measures. From an AI and anonymization perspective, PHI represents a higher compliance risk due to its sensitivity and potential impact in case of unauthorized disclosure. Consequently, privacy-preserving techniques applied to claims data must be particularly robust when PHI is involved.

B. Pipeline

The solution is implemented as an agent-based architecture organized into a sequential privacy-aware processing pipeline. The pipeline operates primarily on unstructured textual content and page-level document representations, reflecting the heterogeneous nature of real-world insurance claims documentation.

During the ingestion phase, claims-related documents are collected in multiple formats, including PDF, PNG, JPEG, TIFF, DOCX, XLSX, TXT, EML, MSG, and JSON. Documents are normalized into a unified internal representation while preserving their original page structure. Technical metadata (e.g., file type, resolution, encoding, size) are recorded to ensure traceability and auditability. At this stage, documents may contain raw personally identifiable information (PII).

In the second stage, image-based or non-editable documents are processed using optical character recognition (OCR). The OCR agent performs orientation correction and quality validation before extracting text at the page level,

maintaining structural granularity. The system retains page boundaries and positional information to support subsequent context-aware processing. Extraction confidence metrics and anomaly indicators are logged for quality control purposes.

The anonymization stage is executed by a locally deployed large language model (LLM) agent operating within a controlled environment. The model processes page-level unstructured text to detect and transform sensitive attributes, including direct identifiers (e.g., names, policy numbers, contact information) and selected quasi-identifiers. Direct identifiers are removed or replaced, while specific attributes may be selectively generalized or irreversibly tokenized using salted hashing mechanisms. Because the pipeline operates primarily on unstructured textual content, anonymization is context-aware rather than purely rule-based. The LLM analyzes semantic context across document pages to ensure accurate detection of PII embedded within free-text narratives. All transformations are logged to support compliance documentation and traceability.

The persistence layer stores structured artifacts generated during the processing pipeline while enforcing strict separation between identifiable and anonymized content. The stored data objects consist of the following components: machine-readable textual content extracted from OCR at page level, structured OCR output including positional and layout metadata, technical metadata generated during ingestion and OCR stages, anonymized document, anonymized map.

C. Anonymization

The anonymization phase operates on page-level unstructured textual content produced by the OCR stage. It is executed by a locally deployed LLM agent that performs context-aware detection and transformation of sensitive entities directly within the extracted text. In the first step, the LLM identifies direct identifiers classified as PII, including personal names, email addresses, phone numbers, national identification numbers, policy numbers, and other explicit identity markers. These entities are either removed or replaced with neutral placeholders within the anonymized document representation. Because the system processes unstructured claims narratives, detection is performed semantically rather than through rigid rule-based patterns, enabling identification of identifiers embedded in free-text descriptions.

To balance privacy and analytical utility, selected attributes are partially retained in generalized or structured form. For instance, address information is processed so that city and country are preserved, while street names and building numbers are transformed. This enables geographic aggregation and regional risk analysis without exposing precise location details. The transformation logic is applied directly within the textual content, preserving narrative coherence across document pages. Attributes essential for claims analytics such as event descriptions, claim amounts, and event dates remain unchanged unless they contain embedded identifiers. This preserves the predictive signal required for downstream AI tasks while implementing a privacy-utility trade-off strategy at the content level.

Quasi-identifiers designated for controlled retention are transformed using irreversible salted hashing mechanisms. Tokens are generated through cryptographic hashing with a secret salt, ensuring deterministic consistency across documents while reducing vulnerability to dictionary and brute-force attacks. The mapping between original detected

entities and their transformed representations is recorded in the `anonymized_map` artifact for audit and traceability purposes.

Following anonymization, the output passes through a quality gate layer designed to validate transformation integrity and residual privacy risk prior to persistence. This layer performs three key checks:

- Consistency validation, ensuring that tokenized entities remain coherent across document pages and that no unresolved identifier fragments persist in the anonymized representation.
- Risk scoring, which estimates residual re-identification exposure based on the presence of quasi-identifiers, rare attribute combinations, and structural uniqueness within the document.
- Guardrails enforcement, applying predefined policy constraints that block persistence if risk thresholds are exceeded or if critical transformation inconsistencies are detected.

Only documents that successfully pass the quality gate are forwarded to the persistence layer. This mechanism operationalizes privacy-by-design principles by embedding automated compliance verification directly into the processing pipeline.

D. Testing through Synthetic Data

To validate the reliability of the proposed anonymization pipeline prior to deployment on real-world insurance data, controlled testing was conducted using a synthetic dataset. The evaluation sample consisted of 10 synthetic claim cases comprising 23 documents, reflecting realistic document heterogeneity and structural complexity typical of claims processing workflows (see Table I., Table II.).

The primary objective was to assess the accuracy of automated PII identification and transformation. Across the evaluation sample, the system successfully detected and replaced 169 instances of personally identifiable information (PII), achieving 100% success in the primary identifier replacement phase. This confirms the robustness of the LLM-based entity detection and cryptographic tokenization mechanism in handling unstructured textual inputs.

TABLE I. FULL-RUN COMPARISON

Metric	As stored after each run		
	Thinking	Non-thinking	Delta
Domain success	10/23	10/23	same
Domain fail	13/23	13/23	same
JSON branch success	10/10	10/10	same
API 200 responses	23/23	23/23	same
OCR used docs	20	10	-10
OCR confidence avg (token-weighted)	59.42	61.00	+1.57
OCR confidence p50 / p90	64.76 / 85.25	59.33 / 85.25	p50 -5.43
Cleanup attempts total	20	10	-10
Cleanup latency avg (ms)	242028.46	93880.16	-148148.30
Cleanup latency p50 (ms)	243093.03	74098.11	-168994.91

Metric	As stored after each run		
	Thinking	Non-thinking	Delta
Cleanup latency p90 (ms)	367215.01	165109.33	-202105.69
Cleanup change ratio avg	0.01969	0.00324	-0.01645
PII identified total	169	110	-59
PII replaced total	169	110	-59
PII residual total	27	100	+73
PII residual ratio (residual/identified)	15.98% (27/169)	90.91% (100/110)	+74.93 pp
Verification fail source llm	12	12	same

Following transformation, each document was evaluated by the anonymization quality gate, which applies strict consistency and residual-risk validation criteria. The overall end-to-end document-level success rate was 43.5% (10 out of 23 documents). The relatively low pass rate is attributable to the system’s zero-tolerance policy: a document is classified as failed if even a single residual PII element remains undetected. This conservative threshold is intentionally designed to prioritize compliance and minimize re-identification exposure.

TABLE II. FAIR COMPARISON ON SAME DOCUMENTS

Metric	13 docs reprocessed in non-thinking run		
	Thinking (same docs)	Non-thinking (executed docs)	Delta
Domain success	0/13	0/13	same
Domain fail	13/13	13/13	same
OCR confidence avg (token-weighted)	61.00	61.00	same
OCR confidence p50 / p90	59.33 / 85.25	59.33 / 85.25	same
Cleanup latency avg (ms)	284984.62	93880.16	-191104.45
Cleanup latency p50 (ms)	282287.99	74098.11	-208189.87
Cleanup latency p90 (ms)	381970.18	165109.33	-216860.85
Cleanup change ratio avg	0.02474	0.00324	-0.02150
PII identified total	99	110	+11
PII residual total	27	100	+73
PII residual ratio (residual/identified)	27.27% (27/99)	90.91% (100/110)	+63.64 pp

In 12 documents, a total of 27 residual PII elements remained undetected, representing approximately 16% of all identifiable instances across the dataset. These residual cases constitute the primary area for model refinement and prompt optimization. Preliminary analysis indicates that most missed instances occurred in low-confidence OCR regions or within atypical formatting structures.

The average OCR confidence score across documents was 63.8%, with approximately half of the documents exceeding 72% recognition accuracy. A direct correlation was observed between lower OCR quality and anonymization failure rates. Documents with poor OCR recognition exhibited higher likelihood of residual PII, suggesting that anonymization robustness is partially dependent on upstream text extraction accuracy.

The evaluation demonstrates that the proposed anonymization mechanism performs reliably in primary identifier detection but is sensitive to OCR quality and strict residual-risk thresholds. The Quality Gate mechanism effectively prevents incomplete anonymization from reaching the persistence layer, reinforcing compliance-by-design principles. These results validate the architectural decision to integrate anonymization and risk scoring directly into the processing pipeline before persistence and downstream AI usage.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study evaluated an agent-based anonymization pipeline designed for AI-driven insurance claims processing. The proposed architecture integrates OCR-based text extraction, LLM-driven identifier replacement, and a strict anonymization quality gate prior to data persistence. The proposed approach represents a baseline, the improvement of which will be the subject of future work. Testing on synthetic claims data demonstrated 100% success in primary PII detection, while the end-to-end document-level success rate (43.5%) reflected the system’s zero-tolerance residual policy rather than fundamental detection failure. Residual PII occurrences were primarily associated with low OCR confidence, highlighting the dependency between text extraction quality and anonymization robustness.

The findings confirm that cryptographic hash-based tokenization effectively reduces direct identity exposure but should be treated as pseudonymization under GDPR due to theoretical linkage risks. Embedding anonymization directly within the processing pipeline, combined with automated risk scoring and guardrails, strengthens privacy-by-design compliance. Future work will focus on improving OCR robustness, reducing residual PII, and further quantifying privacy-utility trade-offs in operational insurance environments.

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Recognition of Commemorative Euro Coins

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Abstract—This paper presents the design and implementation of an application for automatic recognition of commemorative two-euro coins using computer vision techniques. The system allows users to capture an image of a coin with a smartphone camera and automatically identify the coin by comparing it with a locally stored reference database. In addition to recognizing the coin, the application provides information such as the issuing country, year of issue, and mintage volume.

The recognition pipeline is based on local feature extraction and matching. Two approaches were experimentally evaluated: a classical feature-based method using the Scale-Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) and a neural feature matching pipeline based on SuperPoint and SuperGlue. The evaluation was performed on a dataset of coin images provided by the National Bank of Slovakia and assessed using Top- k ranking metrics. Experimental results indicate that the neural method achieved higher recognition accuracy, while the SIFT-based approach demonstrated robustness to image rotation and lower computational requirements suitable for mobile deployment.

In addition to technical evaluation, a user study was conducted to assess the usability of the application. Subjective workload was measured using the NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX). The results suggest that the proposed application enables efficient coin identification while maintaining relatively low cognitive workload for users.

The contribution of this paper is rooted in its original idea — to provide users with a tool to determine whether a two-euro coin is worth two euros or significantly more. Additionally, the application may serve as an educational aid for amateur numismatists.

Index Terms—coin recognition, computer vision, feature matching, SIFT, SuperPoint, mobile application, numismatists

I. INTRODUCTION

The euro is the official currency used in 20 countries of the Eurozone and represents one of the most widely circulated currencies in the world. Among euro coins, the two-euro denomination is particularly notable due to the existence of both standard circulation coins and commemorative variants. Although both types share the same nominal value of two euros, commemorative coins may have a significantly higher collector value due to limited mintage, historical significance, or increased collector demand. Since the introduction of euro coins in 2002, Eurozone countries have regularly issued commemorative coins to celebrate important national or European events [1].

Identifying such coins is not always straightforward for the general public. Many commemorative coins visually resemble regular circulation coins, and distinguishing between them

often requires consulting specialised numismatic catalogues or online databases [2], [3]. As a result, recognising commemorative coins in everyday situations may be difficult for users who are not experienced collectors.

The motivation behind this thesis is to provide users with a practical tool that assists in recognising commemorative two-euro coins automatically. The proposed solution is a mobile application that allows users to scan the reverse side of a coin using a smartphone camera. The application compares the captured image with a locally stored database of coin images and returns the most likely matches. If the coin is successfully recognised, the application provides additional information such as the issuing country, year of issue, and the number of coins minted. The application is designed to operate offline after downloading the required dataset, making it convenient for everyday use.

From a technical perspective, the problem of coin recognition falls within the broader field of computer vision and image recognition. Computer vision methods aim to extract meaningful information from images and identify objects or patterns within them. A common approach involves preprocessing the image to improve quality and highlight relevant features before applying recognition algorithms [4]. In the context of coin recognition, preprocessing may include noise reduction, grayscale conversion, contrast enhancement, or edge detection.

An important step in many coin recognition systems is the detection of circular shapes. Coins typically appear as circular objects in images, and techniques such as the Circular Hough Transform can be used to detect circular structures in images [5]. The Hough Transform is a well-known technique in computer vision for detecting geometric shapes in images and has been widely studied in the literature [6]. In practice, robust detection methods such as RANSAC may also be applied to estimate geometric transformations and eliminate incorrect matches [7], [8].

The core recognition pipeline implemented in this thesis is based on local feature detection and matching using the SIFT (Scale-Invariant Feature Transform) algorithm. SIFT extracts distinctive keypoints from an image and describes them using numerical feature descriptors that remain robust under changes in scale, rotation, and illumination [9]. These descriptors can then be compared between images to estimate their similarity. Feature-based methods such as SIFT [10], SURF, and ORB [4] are commonly used for object recognition tasks and have

been extensively compared in the literature [10].

In addition to traditional computer vision approaches, modern deep learning techniques have also been explored for feature detection and matching. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have become a fundamental tool for image recognition tasks [11]. More recently, neural network-based feature detectors and matchers such as SuperPoint [12] and SuperGlue [13] have been proposed. SuperGlue [14] formulates feature matching as a graph neural network problem, allowing it to model relationships between keypoints and produce more accurate matches [13], [15]. These approaches represent a modern alternative to classical feature descriptors and have shown promising results in many computer vision tasks [12]. Additionally, lightweight matching architectures such as LightGlue have been developed to improve computational efficiency in feature matching tasks [16].

The experimental evaluation in this paper was conducted on a dataset of coin images provided by the National Bank of Slovakia. The dataset contains multiple images of two-euro coins captured under different lighting conditions, camera angles, and rotations. These variations make the recognition task more challenging and provide a realistic test environment for evaluating the robustness of the implemented methods.

Besides the recognition algorithm itself, an important part of this work is the implementation of a complete mobile application that integrates computer vision functionality into a user-friendly interface. The application was developed for Android devices using Kotlin for the frontend and Python for the backend processing. Communication between these components is achieved using the Chaquopy library, which allows Python code to run within the Android environment [17]. Additional tools such as BeautifulSoup were used for obtaining and processing coin metadata from online sources [18].

Another important aspect of the evaluation is the usability of the application. A user study was conducted in which participants used the application to identify coins and compared the process with manual searching methods. The subjective workload and perceived difficulty of the task were evaluated using the NASA-TLX method, which is widely used for measuring cognitive workload in human-computer interaction studies [19].

The NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) is method used for assessing subjective workload in human-computer interaction experiments. The method was originally developed by Hart and Staveland as a multidimensional tool for evaluating perceived task difficulty across several cognitive and physical dimensions [19].

The NASA-TLX questionnaire evaluates workload using six dimensions: mental demand, physical demand, temporal demand, performance, effort, and frustration. Mental demand reflects how much cognitive processing was required during the task, such as thinking, deciding, or remembering. Physical demand measures the amount of physical activity required from the user, for example when handling the smartphone and positioning the camera. Temporal demand evaluates the

time pressure perceived by the user while completing the task. The performance dimension reflects how successful the user believes they were in completing the task, while effort measures how hard the user had to work to accomplish the task. Finally, frustration measures the level of stress, irritation, or discouragement experienced during the task.

Participants were asked to perform a series of coin recognition tasks using the developed application. Each participant used the application to capture an image of a coin and observe the recognition results returned by the system. After completing the task, participants filled in the NASA-TLX questionnaire to report their perceived workload.

The NASA-TLX score can be calculated in two ways. The first approach is the unweighted NASA-TLX score, which is computed as the average of the six workload dimensions. The second approach is the weighted NASA-TLX score, which uses pairwise comparisons between dimensions to determine their relative importance. The weighted score can provide a more precise estimate of perceived workload because it takes into account which dimensions contributed most to the overall difficulty of the task [19].

Fig. 1: Figure shows the results obtained from the participants. Both unweighted and weighted NASA-TLX scores are presented for each tester. The first participant reported relatively low workload values, indicating that the application was easy to use and required minimal effort. The second participant reported a higher unweighted workload score, suggesting that the task required more cognitive effort during coin identification. The third participant reported the highest weighted score, which indicates that certain workload dimensions, such as effort or frustration, had a stronger influence on the perceived difficulty of the task.

Overall, the results indicate that the application can be used with moderate cognitive workload. Although the recognition task required some user interaction, the participants were generally able to complete the task successfully. The results suggest that the application interface is relatively intuitive, but

further improvements could reduce user effort even more. Possible improvements include providing clearer guidance during image capture and improving feedback when recognition fails.

II. PREVIOUS WORKS

Coin recognition has been addressed using both classical computer vision techniques and modern deep learning approaches. Early approaches primarily relied on handcrafted image processing methods designed to exploit the geometric and visual properties of coins, while more recent work increasingly uses machine learning and neural network-based feature extraction.

Traditional methods typically begin with preprocessing steps such as grayscale conversion, noise reduction, thresholding, and contrast enhancement in order to improve image quality and highlight relevant structures [4]. These preprocessing techniques aim to reduce illumination differences, sensor noise, and background clutter before applying recognition algorithms. After preprocessing, geometric shape detection techniques are often applied. Since coins appear as circular objects in images, many approaches rely on detecting circular shapes using the Hough Transform. The Hough Transform is a classical computer vision method that detects parametric shapes in images and has been widely studied in the literature [6]. In particular, the Circular Hough Transform is frequently used for detecting coin boundaries and separating coins from the background [5]. Such approaches have been successfully applied in systems designed for counting and recognizing coins in controlled environments [5].

In practical systems, robust estimation techniques such as RANSAC are often combined with geometric detection methods to handle noise and outliers in the data. RANSAC iteratively estimates model parameters from subsets of data and removes inconsistent observations, which makes it useful for estimating geometric transformations between images in the presence of incorrect feature matches [7]. More recent surveys describe the wide applicability of RANSAC in computer vision and robotics, particularly in tasks involving feature matching and geometric verification [8].

Beyond simple geometric detection, many recognition systems rely on local feature-based methods. Feature-based recognition algorithms identify distinctive points in an image and describe their local appearance using numerical descriptors. One of the most influential methods in this category is the Scale-Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT), which detects scale- and rotation-invariant keypoints and constructs 128-dimensional descriptors that can be compared between images [9]. Because these descriptors are robust to scale changes, rotation, and moderate illumination variations, SIFT has been widely used in object recognition, image matching, and structure-from-motion applications. Comparative studies have shown that feature descriptors such as SIFT, SURF, and ORB are effective tools for many object recognition tasks [10]. These methods allow recognition systems to match distinctive patterns even when objects appear rotated or partially occluded.

In recent years, deep learning approaches have significantly improved feature detection and matching performance. Neural networks can learn feature representations directly from data instead of relying on handcrafted descriptors. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have become a fundamental tool for many visual recognition tasks due to their ability to learn hierarchical representations of image features [11]. Surveys on neural network methods highlight their effectiveness in extracting complex visual patterns from image data [20].

One notable neural feature detection approach is SuperPoint [21], which uses a convolutional neural network to jointly detect keypoints and compute descriptors. SuperPoint [12] is trained in a self-supervised manner and produces feature descriptors that are robust to geometric transformations and illumination changes [12], [21]. To further improve feature matching accuracy, the SuperGlue [14] algorithm was introduced. SuperGlue [13] formulates feature matching as a graph neural network problem, allowing the algorithm to model relationships between keypoints detected in two images [13]. By incorporating attention mechanisms and an optimal matching layer, SuperGlue [14] can produce highly accurate correspondences between images. Graph neural networks [15] have been shown to be particularly effective in modeling relationships between structured data such as keypoint correspondences [15].

Recent developments in neural feature matching have also focused on improving computational efficiency. For example, the LightGlue [16] algorithm introduces a lightweight architecture that significantly accelerates feature matching while maintaining high accuracy [16]. These modern approaches represent a new generation of feature matching algorithms that combine classical geometric reasoning with deep learning-based feature extraction.

Although neural methods often achieve superior performance in many computer vision benchmarks, they typically require higher computational resources and more complex pipelines compared to classical feature descriptors. For mobile applications, this trade-off between recognition accuracy and computational efficiency is particularly important.

In this work, both classical and neural feature-based approaches were experimentally evaluated for the task of commemorative coin identification. Specifically, the SIFT feature detector and descriptor [10] was compared with a neural feature extraction pipeline based on SuperPoint [21] combined with the SuperGlue matching algorithm [14]. The goal of this comparison was to evaluate the recognition accuracy and computational feasibility of these approaches when applied to images of two-euro commemorative coins.

III. DATASET

The dataset used for evaluation consisted of 80 images of two-euro coins provided by the National Bank of Slovakia. Due to insufficient quality, two images were excluded, resulting in a final dataset of 78 images.

Each image represented the reverse side of either a commemorative or circulation coin. The reference database was

constructed using publicly available sources, including the European Central Bank [1], [3] and online numismatic catalogues [2]. Images were organised by year of issuance, and each entry was linked with textual metadata containing information about the issuing country, commemorative theme, and mintage volume.

During evaluation, each test image was compared against all reference images from the corresponding year (or circulation folder). The ranking position of the correct match was recorded for further statistical analysis.

IV. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND IMPLEMENTATION

The implemented system consists of a mobile Android application with a Python-based backend.

The frontend was developed in Kotlin using Android Studio. It provides functionalities including image capture via CameraX, database browsing, user authentication, and result visualisation. The backend was implemented in Python and integrated into the Android environment using the Chaquopy plugin [17].

The recognition pipeline consists of the following steps:

- Image capture and resizing,
- Conversion to grayscale,
- Feature extraction (SIFT or SuperPoint),
- Descriptor matching,
- Ranking of similarity scores.

For SIFT [10], keypoints and descriptors are extracted using OpenCV. Matching is performed with a brute-force matcher, and similarity is computed based on the average distance of the best matches. Lower distances indicate higher similarity.

For the neural approach, SuperPoint [12] is used for key-point detection and descriptor extraction, while SuperGlue [13] performs graph-based matching and filtering using homography estimation. Due to integration and computational constraints on mobile devices, the final deployed version uses SIFT.

V. RESULTS

Performance evaluation was conducted using ranking-based metrics: Top-1, Top-3, Top-5, and Top-10 accuracy.

Fig. 2: Comparison of SIFT and SuperPoint accuracy across Top-k metrics.

SuperPoint [21] combined with SuperGlue [14] achieved higher recognition accuracy across all evaluated thresholds. The largest improvement was observed in the Top-1 category. However, this method demonstrated sensitivity to image rotation and required manual orientation adjustment during preprocessing.

This limitation can be mitigated using several approaches. One possibility is to perform automatic rotation normalization during the preprocessing stage. The captured coin image can be rotated through multiple orientations (for example every 90° or smaller angular steps) and evaluated against the reference database. The orientation that produces the highest number of feature correspondences can then be selected as the final result.

Another approach is to employ rotation-invariant feature descriptors. Classical methods such as SIFT [9] incorporate orientation normalization directly in the descriptor computation, which makes them more robust to rotated inputs. Similarly, recent neural feature matching approaches attempt to learn rotation-invariant representations during training.

A further solution is to estimate the dominant orientation of the coin using geometric cues such as circular boundary detection with the Hough Transform [6] or robust estimation techniques such as RANSAC [7]. Once the dominant orientation is detected, the image can be automatically aligned before feature extraction. This preprocessing step reduces the sensitivity of neural matching methods to rotation and improves the robustness of the recognition pipeline.

Fig. 3: Feature matching comparison between SIFT and SuperGlue.

A paired t-test analysis confirmed that SuperPoint generally ranked the correct match higher than SIFT. Nevertheless, SIFT exhibited greater robustness to rotation and blur and provided faster computation suitable for mobile deployment.

Fig. 4: Paired t-test results comparing ranking differences between methods.

User testing further demonstrated that the application enables faster and less cognitively demanding identification compared to manual internet search. NASA-TLX workload scores [19] indicated low subjective workload for users operating the application.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented the design and implementation of an application for identifying commemorative two-euro coins

using computer vision techniques. Two recognition approaches were evaluated: a classical feature-based method (SIFT) and a neural matching method based on SuperPoint and SuperGlue.

Experimental evaluation showed that the neural feature matching approach achieved higher recognition accuracy, particularly in the Top-1 ranking category. However, this method required greater computational resources and was more sensitive to image rotation. In contrast, the SIFT-based approach demonstrated greater robustness to rotation and image blur while providing faster computation suitable for deployment on mobile devices.

The developed application enables users to capture a coin image using a smartphone camera and automatically compare it with a locally stored reference database. The system operates offline after downloading the required dataset and provides additional information about recognised coins, including the issuing country, year of issue, and mintage volume. This functionality allows users to quickly determine whether a coin is commemorative and obtain relevant numismatic information.

A small user study was conducted to evaluate the usability of the application. Participants performed coin identification tasks and their perceived workload was measured using the NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX). The results indicated relatively low cognitive workload and confirmed that the application allows faster and more convenient identification compared to manual searching using internet resources.

Future work may focus on integrating more advanced neural feature matching algorithms, such as lightweight neural matchers, and expanding the reference database to include additional coin types or currencies. These improvements could further increase recognition accuracy and transform the application into a more comprehensive intelligent numismatic assistant [22].

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A Systematic Review Exploring Recent Breakthroughs in Explainable AI for Medical Imaging Analysis

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Abstract—Artificial intelligence (AI) has revolutionized medical imaging by enabling automated image analysis, including tasks such as segmentation, classification, and anomaly detection, thus improving diagnostic accuracy and efficiency. Despite these advances, the opaque “black-box” nature of many AI models poses challenges for clinical adoption, as clinicians require transparency and interpretability to trust AI-driven decisions. Explainable AI (XAI) addresses this gap by offering methods that clarify how deep learning (DL) models make predictions, highlight critical image regions, and provide interpretable insights. This review surveys the principles and methodologies of XAI, and explores its applications across various imaging modalities and anatomical regions, which the recent literature fails to cover. Furthermore, this survey discusses the challenges and future directions for integrating XAI into clinical practice and emphasizing interpretability.

Index Terms—Artificial intelligence, Explainable AI, Medical Imaging, Deep learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI), particularly deep learning algorithms, has transformed medical imaging by enabling automated, precise, and efficient analysis of images, improving disease detection, monitoring, and treatment planning [1], [2].

AI systems employ advanced algorithms to analyze complex medical images with high speed and accuracy, often outperforming traditional approaches in challenging diagnostic tasks. In neuroimaging, for example, deep learning models combined with explainable AI techniques such as Grad-CAM have achieved tumor detection accuracies above 98% on Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) scans, while also highlighting relevant pathological regions to aid clinical interpretation and transparency in brain tumor classification [3]. In breast imaging, AI-assisted analysis of MRI and mammograms has demonstrated improved identification of malignant lesions and more precise tumor localization, with heatmap-based visual explanations aligned with the annotated disease areas of the radiologist [4].

AI has significantly enhanced interpretive and predictive capabilities [1]. For instance, AI-driven systems can detect cancerous lesions in mammograms with accuracy comparable to expert radiologists, supporting clinical decision-making and improving patient outcomes.

Despite its significant capabilities, the adoption of deep learning models in medical imaging faces critical challenges

[5]. Many AI models function as “black boxes,” making it difficult for clinicians to understand the rationale behind specific predictions or decisions. This lack of transparency raises concerns about trust, accountability, and ethical responsibility, particularly in high-stakes clinical settings where patient safety is paramount. Without a clear explanation of the underlying reasoning, physicians may be hesitant to rely on AI recommendations when diagnosing serious conditions or determining treatment plans.

Explainable AI addresses these challenges by providing interpretable insights into model predictions. Techniques such as gradient-based visualization methods, including Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM) and saliency maps, as well as perturbation-based approaches such as Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME) and SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP), enable clinicians to identify the image regions or features that most strongly influence model outcomes. By increasing transparency in the decision-making process, these methods help bridge the gap between artificial intelligence outputs and clinical expertise.

This review systematically examines the integration of XAI with deep learning in multiple anatomical regions, including the brain, lungs, breast and skin with various imaging modalities. It highlights how these approaches improve diagnostic performance, increase transparency, and support ethical and regulatory compliance, offering a comprehensive perspective on XAI applications in medical imaging.

The main contributions of this review are:

1. This review offers a comprehensive analysis of explainable AI methods applied to deep learning-based medical imaging systems. It highlights that the majority of studies in this field focus on providing visual explanations to interpret the outputs of deep learning models.
2. The paper emphasizes the critical importance of XAI research in medical imaging, noting that the adoption and trust of AI in clinical practice largely depend on the ability of models to produce clear and meaningful explanations for their predictions.
3. The review systematically categorizes the existing literature based on anatomical regions and medical imaging modalities, showing that most studies concentrate on areas such as the chest, brain, and MRI applications. This classification provides

valuable insights into the application of XAI techniques across diverse medical imaging contexts.

II. SYSTEMATIC REVIEW APPROACH

A comprehensive and systematic methodology was employed to review the integration of deep learning with explainable AI in medical imaging. The search process included identifying digital libraries, designing search strings, and selecting relevant studies. Searches were conducted across IEEE Xplore, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar, focusing on peer-reviewed journal articles, conference proceedings, and relevant reviews. The final selection comprised 30 papers most pertinent to the topic. These studies specifically examined the application of XAI techniques within deep learning frameworks for medical imaging. Publications from 2015 to 2026 were considered to capture recent advancements. For each study, data on authors, objectives, deep learning models, XAI methods, imaging modalities, evaluation approaches, and key findings were extracted and analyzed to identify patterns, trends, applications, and research gaps.

A. Review of existing survey

Several recent surveys have examined the role of XAI in addressing the “black-box” nature of machine learning models in healthcare. Dhar et al. [6] provide a comprehensive overview of XAI techniques, including saliency-based and attribution methods such as Grad-CAM and Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP), and discuss their application in clinical decision support and the diagnosis of conditions such as coronary artery disease (CAD) and Alzheimer’s disease (AD). The review emphasizes the importance of explainability for fostering clinician trust, ethical AI adoption, and transparency in healthcare systems. However, it remains largely technique-driven and does not systematically organize the literature according to clinical domains, anatomical regions, or medical imaging modalities, limiting structured comparative analysis across clinical contexts.

Similarly, Bharati et al. [7] evaluate XAI in healthcare with a focus on mitigating the opacity of deep learning models. Their review covers key explanation strategies, including dimensionality reduction, feature selection, and attention mechanisms, and highlights the role of XAI in ensuring transparency, security, and clinical safety. While comprehensive in scope, the study adopts a method-centric perspective and provides limited domain-specific structuring of applications.

In the context of medical imaging, Borys et al. [8], [9] offer two complementary reviews. One focuses on saliency-based approaches such as Grad-CAM and SHAP, demonstrating how visual explanations enable clinicians to understand model predictions, identify biases, and detect errors, thereby improving clinical safety and trust. Their subsequent work extends beyond saliency maps by introducing non-visual explanation modalities, including case-based, textual, and auxiliary explanations, and emphasizes the role of uncertainty quantification in supporting informed clinical decision-making. Despite these contributions, both reviews primarily categorize methods by

explanation type rather than by anatomical region or disease context.

Ishwarya et al. [10] present a broad survey of XAI techniques across healthcare applications, discussing their relevance for transparency, trust, and clinical decision support. However, the review remains largely descriptive and does not provide a structured categorization based on disease types, clinical tasks, or imaging modalities, which limits its usefulness for comparative and application-specific insights. Likewise, Volkov and Averkin [11] provide a high-level overview of XAI in medical image analysis across common modalities such as X-ray, Computed Tomography (CT), and MRI, but do not propose a systematic taxonomy or detailed comparative evaluation across diseases or explanation methods.

More task-focused surveys have also emerged. Teng et al. [12] review AI techniques for medical image segmentation, tracing the evolution from conventional and explainable AI approaches toward trustworthy AI frameworks. While the study highlights the role of XAI in improving transparency, robustness, and clinical deployment, its focus on segmentation limits its generalizability to broader medical imaging tasks. Pant et al. [13] categorize XAI approaches into intrinsic and post-hoc methods and examine their application across genomics, radiology, and electronic health records (EHRs), emphasizing clinician trust and regulatory compliance while noting trade-offs between interpretability and predictive accuracy. Finally, Fontes et al. [14] focus on example-based XAI in medical imaging, surveying techniques such as prototype-based explanations, case-based reasoning and retrieval (CBR/CBIR), Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), and counterfactuals, and identifying computational efficiency as a key barrier to clinical adoption.

Despite the breadth of existing surveys on XAI in healthcare and medical imaging, the literature remains predominantly method-centric or task-specific. Most reviews lack a unified, clinically grounded organization of XAI approaches across anatomical regions, disease categories, and imaging modalities, limiting cross-study comparability and domain-specific insight. As a result, there is limited guidance for understanding how different explainability techniques perform and generalize in diverse clinical contexts, highlighting the need for more structured and application-oriented analyses.

III. EXPLAINABLE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (XAI)

Explainable artificial intelligence [15] encompasses a set of methods aimed at improving the transparency of AI models by revealing how their output is generated. XAI provides insights into the internal decision-making processes of AI systems, enabling healthcare professionals and patients to understand the rationale behind specific predictions. By offering interpretable explanations, XAI fosters trust, accountability, and informed decision-making in AI-assisted medical applications.

A. Importance of Explainable AI in Medical Imaging

Medical imaging is a high-stakes domain where diagnostic decisions directly impact patient care and outcomes. Errors

in AI-assisted interpretations can result in misdiagnoses or inappropriate treatments, with serious clinical, ethical, and legal implications. Consequently, transparent and interpretable AI systems are critical to ensuring reliability and effectively supporting clinical decision-making. Therefore, explainability in medical imaging is essential for multiple reasons.

- *Enhancing Clinical Trust and Decision-Making*

XAI enhances clinical decision-making by highlighting the key features or image regions that drive model predictions. By providing this transparency, clinicians can evaluate AI outputs in conjunction with their expertise, fostering trust and supporting the safe adoption of AI in healthcare [16].

- *Detection of Model Limitations and Risk Management*

XAI reveals model weaknesses, biases, and uncertain predictions in healthcare by rendering outputs interpretable. This enables clinicians and developers to detect errors, refine models, and enhance the safety and reliability of AI systems [17].

- *Improving Patient Understanding and Engagement*

In clinical settings, XAI enhances both model interpretability and clinician-patient communication. By showing key image regions or feature-level explanations, clinicians can explain diagnostic decisions and treatment recommendations, increasing patient trust. Grad-CAM, SHAP, and LIME methods are commonly applied to ensure transparent AI reasoning [18], [19].

B. Taxonomy of Explainable AI Methodologies

This section reviews key methods for interpreting machine learning models. Although several frameworks have been proposed to categorize XAI techniques, no universal taxonomy exists, as classifications often depend on the objectives and characteristics of the methods. For example, Arrieta et al. [20] categorize XAI into inherently transparent and post-hoc models, while other studies provide more detailed classifications [21]–[23]. In this study, XAI is broadly grouped into three categories, as illustrated in Figure 1, offering an overview of the different XAI techniques.

- *XAI Based on Explanation Approaches*

XAI techniques aim to make AI models more transparent by analyzing their behavior either during the training process or once the model is fully trained. Based on the implementation phase, XAI is classified into ante-hoc methods and post-hoc methods.

- *Ante-hoc or Transparent Models*

Ante-hoc methods are inherently interpretable and provide real-time insights during model training. The term “ante-hoc,” derived from Latin meaning “before this,” reflects their aim of ensuring transparency from the beginning of the modelling process. These approaches rely on models that are interpretable by design, such as linear regression, logistic regression, decision trees, and rule-based models.

- *Post-hoc Explanation*

Post-hoc approaches are techniques applied after a model has been trained to interpret, analyze, or explain its predictions and treat the model as a black box, using its outputs to understand and explain its behavior. It is classified into two categories: model-specific and model-agnostic methods. *Model-specific methods* are explanation techniques designed for a particular type of model, using its internal structure. For example, neural networks use saliency maps, integrated gradients, and layer-wise relevance propagation to analyze the gradients or layer contributions to determine which input features most influenced the output. *Model-agnostic methods* are explanation techniques that can be applied to any machine learning model regardless of its internal structure. They treat the model as a black box and analyze the relationship between input features and predictions to generate explanations, such as LIME and SHAP, which provide feature importance scores or local approximations of the model’s behavior.

- *XAI Based on Scope of Explanation*

Explanation scope defines how broadly an XAI method interprets a model. Based on the explanation scope, XAI methods are categorized into global and local approaches. *Global Methods* - interpret the entire model by analyzing all input data to provide an overall view of its predictions. For instance, Logistic Regression uses feature weights to quantify their contribution across the entire dataset, whereas Decision Trees are naturally global because their hierarchical structure makes the decision process for all instances easy to visualize and understand. *Local Methods* - explain individual predictions, highlighting why a model produced a specific output for a particular input, using techniques like LIME and SHAP.

- *XAI Based on Explanation Result*

Based on the type of explanations, XAI methods can be grouped into three main categories: (1) Visualization-based explanations, (2) Example-based explanations [14], and (3) Rule-based explanations [24]. In this review, we focus primarily on visualization-based explanations in medical imaging, as they are widely used in current healthcare systems and play a key role in supporting clinical interpretation and increasing trust. *Visualization-based explanations* use visual representations to illustrate the reasoning behind a model’s predictions by highlighting the input features or regions that most influence the outcome, thereby improving the interpretability of complex AI decisions. These approaches are generally divided into two main categories: gradient-based visualization and perturbation-based visualization, which are extensively employed across medical imaging applications.

1) *Gradient-Based Visualization*: These techniques use backpropagation to compute gradients and generate heatmaps that highlight the input regions most influential to a model’s prediction. Representative methods include Saliency Maps [25], Integrated Gradients (IG), CAM [26], Grad-CAM [28], Grad-CAM++, LRP [29], and Deep Learning Important Features (DeepLIFT) [30].

Fig. 1. Taxonomy of explainable AI Methods

2) *Perturbation-Based Visualization*: Perturbation-based methods evaluate how variations in input data influence model outputs to determine feature importance. By modifying specific regions of medical images or masking parts of the input and observing changes in the output to determine which regions are important. These approaches, including occlusion or masking [31], LIME [32], and SHAP [33], identify regions that most strongly impact model predictions and represent their influence visually using heatmaps.

IV. XAI VISUALIZATION METHOD ACROSS ANATOMICAL REGIONS

The integration of deep learning and explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) has gained increasing attention in medical imaging for disease diagnosis. Deep learning algorithms are widely applied to the classification, detection, and segmentation of pathological regions, while XAI techniques enhance transparency by highlighting image areas associated with disease. This study presents a review of recent research that integrates deep learning with explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) across diverse anatomical regions using various medical imaging modalities, as summarized in Table I. Current approaches primarily aim to achieve two objectives: (1) disease detection and classification, and (2) segmentation of pathological regions, thereby improving diagnostic accuracy and clinical interpretability.

A. Disease Diagnosis and Classification

Numerous studies have used DL algorithms and XAI extensively for detecting and classifying various types of disease across different anatomical sites:

- *Cancer Detection (Brain, Breast, Lung, Skin)*

Recent studies have focused on diagnosing cancer across various anatomical regions. For example, in the context of

Brain Cancer- is an uncontrolled growth of abnormal cells in the brain, leading to tumor formation and impaired normal brain function. Many studies have been done to detect such

abnormalities. For instance, Hosny et al. [34] proposed an explainable MRI-based brain abnormality diagnostic framework using an EfficientViT model combined with Grad-SHAP explanations. The model was evaluated on Alzheimer's and multiple brain tumor MRI datasets, achieving the highest accuracy of 99.5% on the Tumor2 dataset, and for additional recent studies, see Table I.

Lung Cancer - a condition in which lung cells grow abnormally, forming tumors that can interfere with breathing and spread to other organs. Hammad et al. [35] developed a custom CNN for lung cancer detection and subtype classification on CT images, achieving 93.06% accuracy. Grad-CAM was employed to provide visual explanations of the model's decisions. Vanitha et al. [36] proposed a deep learning ensemble model that integrates Xception and MobileNet architectures to classify lung and colon cancer from histopathological images, aiming to enhance feature extraction and model robustness while reducing overfitting. The model was trained on the LC25000 dataset with extensive preprocessing and augmentation, and achieved an overall accuracy of 99.44 % with high precision, recall, and F1-scores across cancer and non-cancer classes. To improve interpretability, Grad-CAM was applied to generate visual heatmaps highlighting regions important for predictions.

Breast Cancer - a malignant growth of cells in the breast that can invade surrounding tissues and spread to other parts of the body. Ahmed et al. [37] applied CNN-based transfer learning using VGG-16 and ResNet50 to classify mammography images as benign or malignant, integrating Grad-CAM, SHAP, and LIME to provide visual explanations consistent with expert annotations. Similarly, Murugan et al. [38] compared several CNN architectures using downsampled histopathology images; VGG-19 achieved the highest accuracy (92.59%), while LIME produced the most clinically meaningful explanations.

Skin Disease – Skin disease refers to any condition that disrupts the normal structure or function of the skin. Ieracitano et al. [39] proposed a framework to evaluate the trustworthiness of explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) in multi-class skin lesion classification. The study assessed several pretrained CNN models GoogleNet, ResNet-18, MobileNetV2, EfficientNet-B0, and VGG16 fine-tuned on the ISIC-2017 dataset to classify melanoma (MEL), nevus (NV), and seborrheic keratosis (SK). EfficientNet-B0 achieved the highest performance with an accuracy 87.6%. Post-hoc XAI methods, including Grad-CAM, LIME, Occlusion Sensitivity Analysis (OSA), and SHAP, were applied to generate relevance heatmaps highlighting regions influencing model predictions. Similarly, Mohan et al. [40] proposed transformer-based deep learning models for skin disease classification and employed Grad-CAM and SHAP to provide interpretable insights into the model’s decision-making process.

B. Disease Segmentation

Some studies have also investigated disease segmentation, emphasizing the increasing use of deep learning and XAI. For example, Farrag et al. [41] compared U-Net and DeepLabV3+ for mammogram tumor segmentation and showed that a modified DeepLabV3+ with double-dilated convolutions improved mammogram tumor segmentation, achieving 81% Dice similarity, 0.04 miss detection rate, and 99% accuracy, while Grad-CAM and occlusion maps provided interpretable visualizations of tumor regions. The double-dilated DeepLabV3+ reduced the miss detection rate by half and improved the similarity (Dice) from 79% to 81% while maintaining the same accuracy of 99%. A recent study on skin lesion segmentation using an explainable hybrid deep learning framework is reported in [42].

TABLE I
Visualization-Based XAI Methods Across Imaging Modalities

Detection, Classification				
Specialty	Modality	Technique	Accuracy	Ref
Brain Tumors	MRI	CNN-VGG16 + SHAP	94%, 81%	[43]
	MRI	CNN + Grad-CAM, SHAP, LIME	95%, 99%	[44]
	MRI	Custom CNN + LIME, SHAP, Grad-CAM	100%	[45]
Lung Disease	CT scans	Two custom CNN + Grad-CAM, SHAP	99.54%	[46]
	CT scans	EfficientNet-B0 + Grad-CAM	0.99%	[47]
Breast Cancer	CXR	BiLSTM-CNN + Grad-CAM	99.1%	[48]
	Ultrasound Images	Densenet121 + custom CNN + Grad-CAM	93.97%, 89.87%	[49]
Skin Disease	Dermoscopic images	EfficientNet-B0 + Grad-CAM, LIME, OSA, SHAP	87.6%	[39]
	Dermoscopic images	transformer-based Models + Grad-CAM, SHAP	96.48%, 89.87%	[49]

V. TOWARD THE FUTURE: CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES

Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) is crucial for improving transparency and trust in deep learning-based medical imaging systems. However, several challenges hinder its clinical adoption. A major concern is the trade-off between predictive performance and interpretability, as highly accurate models often behave as black boxes [20], [23].

Data limitations, including small datasets, class imbalance, and privacy constraints, can further affect model generalization and the reliability of explanations [17]. In addition, there is no widely accepted framework for evaluating explanation quality, robustness, or clinical validity despite the extensive use of saliency-based and feature-attribution techniques [8], [21]. Such limitations complicate the integration of explainable models into clinical workflows.

Clinical relevance is also essential, as explanations must align with medical reasoning to build clinician trust [16]. Future research should therefore focus on developing interpretable or hybrid models, establishing standardized evaluation protocols, integrating multimodal data, and creating clinically validated frameworks to support the safe and trustworthy deployment of AI systems in healthcare [7], [12].

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a systematic review of recent advances in Explainable Artificial Intelligence for medical imaging. The analysis shows that visualization-based post-hoc methods, particularly Grad-CAM, SHAP, and LIME, are the most widely adopted techniques for enhancing the transparency of deep learning models in disease classification and segmentation tasks across modalities such as MRI, CT, and X-ray.

Although XAI improves interpretability and clinician trust, challenges remain in terms of robustness, standardized evaluation, and clinical integration.

Future work will extend this approach to additional anatomical regions, including retinal imaging for ocular diseases and knee imaging, while exploring recent explainable AI methods, such as attention maps and feature attribution, to provide more detailed analyses of model interpretability, reliability, and potential biases, thereby enhancing clinical relevance and diagnostic trust.

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Concept of Federated Synthetic Datasets Generation as a Service for the EOSC

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Abstract—This paper introduces the concept of Federated Synthetic Datasets Generation as a Service (SDGaaS), a proposed architecture for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem intended to shift the paradigm from dataset storage to on-demand dataset creation. The design leverages Large Language Models to generate source code for dataset generators, which would then be validated through a human-in-the-loop feedback cycle, containerized, executed on federated computing infrastructure, and deposited into research product repositories. Current AI methods for both code-based and direct dataset generation are analyzed, including the emerging role of agentic AI systems. A conceptual solution design comprising five abstract federated node roles with persistent identifier traceability is presented, along with a discussion of how this approach could extend the FAIR principles by enabling researchers to create what they cannot find. The concept is situated within the context of EOSC Node Slovakia as an illustrative case for smaller national nodes seeking to evolve from passive data stewardship toward active data generation capabilities.

Keywords—synthetic data generation, EOSC, SDGaaS, federated infrastructure, FAIR

I. INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

Synthetic data are gaining significant momentum. The World Economic Forum’s September 2025 briefing paper “*Synthetic Data: The New Data Frontier*” positioned synthetic data as a foundational technology for the next decade of AI development and a critical component of responsible data governance [1].

Multiple factors contribute to this growing relevance. Modern foundation models require vast amounts of curated training data, yet high-quality text and image corpora on the public internet are approaching saturation [2]. Real-world data collection remains expensive and increasingly constrained by regulation. The EU AI Act, whose general-purpose AI obligations took effect on August 2, 2025, mandates that AI providers publicly disclose training data summaries. From August 2026, the majority of provisions for high-risk AI systems become applicable, including requirements for bias detection and correction where synthetic data can serve as a compliance mechanism [3]. The intersection of the AI Act and EU copyright law further requires that AI developers verify whether training data sources carry copyright reservations, creating additional incentives for synthetic data as a compliant alternative [4].

Synthetic datasets, meaning data artificially generated rather than collected from real-world events, can be produced at

arbitrary scale and tailored to specific distributions while inherently sidestepping many privacy concerns. Applications span healthcare, where federated synthetic data networks enable cross-border data access without exposing patient records [5], natural language processing for low-resource languages [6], environmental monitoring for augmenting sparse pollution and climate observations [7], and cybersecurity for training network intrusion detection systems with synthetic attack patterns [8]. However, synthetic data generation also carries known risks, including the potential to encode and amplify biases, produce realistic-looking but statistically misleading samples, and enable generation of deceptive content such as deepfakes [9]. Addressing these risks requires robust validation mechanisms in any generation pipeline.

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) represents a strategic initiative to provide European researchers with a federated environment for sharing and reusing research data across borders and disciplines. The EOSC Federation has entered its operational build-up phase, with multiple national and thematic nodes being onboarded and an expanding catalogue of services [10].

However, the current EOSC paradigm is fundamentally passive: it assumes that the dataset a researcher needs already exists somewhere. This assumption breaks down when the required data distribution is highly specific, when the domain is nascent, or when privacy constraints prevent sharing source data.

Federated SDGaaS is proposed as a paradigm shift: rather than solely enabling researchers to find existing datasets, such a platform would empower them to create datasets on demand through a federated, and FAIR-compliant workflow. This concept envisions transforming EOSC from a data warehouse into a data factory.

II. THE SLOVAK EOSC NODE AND FEDERATED SDGAAS

The EOSC architecture is designed as a distributed system of national and thematic nodes. Slovakia’s emerging national EOSC node slowly provides a case study of how a smaller European research ecosystem is navigating the path toward full EOSC integration, and how this creates both the opportunity and necessity for services such as Federated SDGaaS.

A. Current State of EOSC Node Slovakia

EOSC Node Slovakia operates as a pilot entry point under the auspices of the Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information (CVTI SR), which serves as the National Coordinator of Open Science in Slovakia and an EOSC Association Mandated Organization [11].

The node is starting to offer research information systems (KOMIS), a data management platform, electronic information resources, and national registries, with related connection to HPC infrastructure under development. Its use case portfolio includes the AMR Federated Pathogen Analysis implementing cross-border bioinformatics workflows across institutions in multiple countries [12].

B. Motivation for Federated SDGaaS

EOSC Node Slovakia illustrates a gap characteristic of the broader ecosystem: infrastructure for cataloguing research outputs exists, yet no mechanism for generating new data on demand is available. The AMR use case demonstrates institutional capability for cross-border federated workflows, and Federated SDGaaS would extend this pattern to synthetic data generation with the added benefit that synthetic data avoids the privacy constraints that make real data sharing difficult.

The EU AI Act creates regulatory demand for synthetic data as a compliance mechanism, particularly for bias detection in high-risk AI systems [3], yet smaller national nodes may lack the scale to build bespoke generation infrastructure. A federated generation service would let any node access capabilities beyond its individual capacity while contributing its own resources. Overall, the evolution from passive data stewardship to active data generation is a recognized next step for the EOSC federation.

III. ANALYSIS OF AI METHODS FOR DATASET GENERATION

Synthetic dataset generation can be approached through two established ways: AI-assisted source code generation, where an AI model produces the program that generates the dataset, and direct AI-based data generation, where an AI model itself produces the synthetic samples. A third way, agentic AI systems, is gaining practical relevance. This section surveys all three and justifies the architectural choice proposed for Federated SDGaaS.

A. AI-Assisted Source Code Generation

Large Language Models have shown strong capability in generating functional source code. By early 2026, the landscape has matured considerably. Jiang et al. benchmarked thirteen leading models in their ACM survey, with several achieving high functional correctness on standard benchmarks [13]. Frontier models including Claude Opus 4.6, GPT-5.3, and Gemini 3.0 Pro and their successors have since achieved competitive results on complex specification-driven software construction tasks [14].

Nadas et al. reviewed how LLMs are transforming synthetic data creation through prompt-based generation, retrieval-augmented pipelines, and iterative self-refinement [6]. Specialized frameworks such as Curator, Distilabel, and Augmentoolkit now provide infrastructure for LLM-driven dataset creation through agentic workflows [15].

When applied to dataset generation, an LLM receives a specification describing the desired schema, statistical distributions, and domain constraints, then produces a self-contained program capable of generating the dataset. The generated code is fully inspectable and auditable, and it is reproducible given the same random seed. The source code itself constitutes a research product that can be shared, cited, and reused independently of the data it produces.

B. Direct AI-Based Data Generation

A different approach uses generative models to directly synthesize data samples. Shi et al.'s 2025 survey organizes the field into statistical methods, GAN-based approaches, VAE variants, diffusion models, and transformer-based methods [16]. Recent advances include encoder-decoder transformer denoisers for tabular data [17], Diffusion Transformers for heterogeneous time-series [18], the TTVAE architecture for complex distributional patterns [19], and the TabularARGN framework with formal differential privacy guarantees [20].

LLMs can also directly generate samples by treating data generation as text completion, which is effective for data requiring world knowledge such as clinical notes. However, direct methods typically require representative training data and produce outputs through an opaque process. They also need specialized and high-performance GPU hardware for inference.

C. Agentic AI Systems

Beyond these two approaches, agentic AI systems offer a third option for data generation tasks. Recent surveys characterize LLM-based multi-agent systems as architectures where specialized agents collaborate through planning, tool use, and iterative self-correction [21]. Orchestration frameworks such as AutoGen, CrewAI, and LangGraph enable the composition of multi-agent pipelines, while autonomous coding agents such as Devin, OpenHands, and Claude Code demonstrate that end-to-end software engineering tasks can be handled with minimal human oversight.

In the context of synthetic dataset generation, an agentic system could interpret a dataset specification, generate code, execute it in a sandbox, evaluate output quality against statistical criteria, and revise the code iteratively until thresholds are met. A dual-agent design is particularly promising: a Generator Agent that writes and refines the code paired with an Evaluator Agent that autonomously runs statistical tests against the user's specification parameters. Such a system can iterate and self-correct without requiring the researcher to possess advanced software engineering skills, and aligns with the feedback loop envisioned in Federated SDGaaS.

D. Justification of the Code Generation Approach

Federated SDGaaS is proposed to adopt AI-assisted source code generation as its primary mechanism. Many scientific use cases involve creating data according to theoretical specifications, for example generating molecular structures with specific properties or simulating sensor readings under defined conditions, where no training data exists for direct methods.

The code generation approach aligns naturally with the FAIR principles [22]: the generated code is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. It produces multiple research products (the generator software and the dataset), and the lightweight generated code, typically just kilobytes, can be transmitted to any federated node for execution. Direct generation models, by contrast, require gigabytes of model weights and co-located GPU hardware.

Several commercial and open-source platforms for synthetic data generation exist, including Gretel, Mostly AI, NVIDIA’s tools, and the Synthetic Data Vault [23]. These platforms primarily target enterprise use cases with direct generation methods and operate as standalone products. Federated SDGaaS differs by focusing on federated scientific infrastructure, code-based generation for auditability, and integration with the EOSC research product lifecycle.

The proposed architecture does not preclude direct generation methods. The LLM-generated source code may itself invoke diffusion model libraries or LLM APIs. In this sense, the LLM serves as a meta-generator: it generates the generator, providing a uniform and auditable interface regardless of the underlying synthesis technique. Future integration of agentic capabilities, such as the dual-agent architecture described in Section III-C, could further enhance this process through automated multi-step refinement.

IV. PROPOSED SOLUTION DESIGN

This section presents the proposed Federated SDGaaS architecture, organized around five abstract federated node roles (A through E). Any EOSC national or thematic node could fulfill one or more of these roles depending on its capabilities. The architecture concept (Fig. 1) emphasizes reproducibility, traceability through persistent identifiers (PIDs), and production of multiple reusable research products. Figs. 2–6 present mockup designs illustrating how the workflow could function.

A. Architecture Overview

The proposed pipeline would transform a researcher’s natural language dataset specification into a validated, full-scale synthetic dataset deposited in a research products repository and registered in EOSC Federation Catalogues. Five stages are envisioned: (1) specification capture and source code generation, (2) sample validation with iterative refinement, (3) containerized full-scale execution, (4) distributed storage, and (5) multi-product deposition and cataloguing. Each stage is represented by an abstract node role communicating through specified interfaces, enabling deployment across different infrastructure providers.

B. User Interface and Dataset Specification

The proposed entry point is a user interface through which an EOSC researcher provides the dataset specification via natural language description, optional sample data upload, and metadata requirements (licensing, provenance, compliance). Fig. 2 shows a mockup of this specification interface.

C. Node Role A: Source Code Generation

The first node role would host a source code generator powered by a Large Language Model, receiving the dataset specification and producing the source code of a dataset generator (typically a Python script or Jupyter Notebook). Generated code would be restricted to a curated set of approved libraries to ensure reliable execution and prevent supply-chain risks, with security sandboxing preventing external network access.

The generation process is envisioned as a multi-stage pipeline: initial code generation, static analysis, automated sandbox testing, and iterative refinement where errors are fed back to the LLM. Fig. 3 illustrates a mockup of the generated code.

D. Node Role B: Sample Generation and Validation

The second node role implements the human-in-the-loop quality assurance process. The generated source code from Node Role A would be executed to produce a small batch of synthetic samples sufficient for the researcher to evaluate output quality.

This node role would provide sample inspection through an interactive interface with statistical summaries, distribution plots, and quality metrics, along with an integrated code editor for direct modifications. A feedback loop connecting back to Node Role A forms the defining iterative mechanism: the researcher provides natural language feedback triggering new code generation iterations until the output is approved. The validated source code output could receive a persistent identifier (PID n.1).

As a further enhancement, this node could employ the dual-agent architecture from Section III-C, where the Generator Agent and Evaluator Agent iterate autonomously before presenting results to the researcher, reducing the number of manual review cycles required. Fig. 4 shows a mockup of the validation interface.

E. Node Role C: Orchestration and Execution

Once approved, Node Role C acts as an orchestration layer that distributes the validated source code alongside a lightweight environment manifest (e.g., a Dockerfile or requirements.txt) to the target computing node. Rather than transmitting pre-built container images across the federation, the actual container compilation occurs locally at the execution site, leveraging local caching layers to minimize network transit.

This approach preserves the bandwidth efficiency of distributing kilobyte-sized source code and manifests while still ensuring reproducible execution environments through version-pinned dependencies and cryptographic verification.

Fig. 1. Proposed Federated SDGaaS architecture showing five abstract federated node roles (A through E), the human-in-the-loop feedback cycle, persistent identifier (PID) traceability, and envisioned integration with EOSC Federation Catalogues.

Fig. 2. Federated SDGaaS mockup design – Step 1 (Specify): The researcher defines the dataset specification including a natural language prompt, domain selection, output format, and licensing metadata.

Fig. 3. Federated SDGaaS mockup design – Node Role A (Generate): LLM-generated Python code for synthetic image generation with dependency and security checks. PID n.1 is assigned to the source code.

F. Node Roles D and E: Storage, Repository, and EOSC Integration

The resulting container would be deployed on EOSC federation computing infrastructure, whether HPC clusters or cloud resources, with a scheduling layer matching jobs to resources. Fig. 5 presents a mockup of the orchestration and execution.

The fourth node role would provide distributed storage for the final dataset, ensuring reliability through replication across storage nodes (f.e. ONEDATA - onedata.org) and compliance with data jurisdiction requirements.

Fig. 4. Federated SDGaaS mockup design – Node Role B (Validate): Sample inspection with generated images, quality metrics, class distribution analysis, and an integrated code editor for iterative refinement.

The fifth node role would host a research products repository, interfacing with established repositories (such as Zenodo or B2SHARE) within the EOSC ecosystem. Federated SDGaaS is designed to produce up to three research products from a single request:

- 1) The source code of the dataset generator (PID n.1), deposited as a reusable software artifact.
- 2) The environment manifest packaging (for containerization) the validated generator (PID n.2), enabling exact reproduction of the execution environment.
- 3) The generated synthetic dataset (PID n.3).

PID assignment and repository deposition are not mandatory for every generated artifact. To avoid overloading repositories with experimental or low-quality outputs, deposition would be curated through quality assessment: only artifacts that pass defined quality thresholds and that the researcher explicitly marks for publication would receive persistent identifiers and be registered in EOSC catalogues. All deposited products

Fig. 5. Federated SDGaaS mockup design – Node Role C (Execute): Orchestration and full-scale execution on federated HPC infrastructure, showing build logs and execution progress.

Fig. 6. Federated SDGaaS mockup design – Nodes D+E (Deposit): The research products repository listing all three outputs from a single generation request, each assigned a persistent identifier.

would be listed as resources in the EOSC Federation Catalogues, indexed with metadata, PIDs, and provenance links. The links between PIDs would create a coherent package allowing researchers to trace from any artifact to the others. Fig. 6 shows a mockup of the repository view.

G. Federated Distribution

The five node roles need not reside on the same infrastructure or in the same country. Any EOSC node could take on one or more roles depending on its resources. Inter-node communication would follow a message-passing architecture with standardized API contracts, using PIDs as the primary linking mechanism. This also addresses data sovereignty concerns, as sensitive artifacts could be processed within specific jurisdictions.

V. CONCLUSION

The Federated SDGaaS concept addresses a gap in the research data ecosystem: the inability to generate, rather than merely discover, datasets on demand. By combining LLM-powered code generation with containerized execution on federated infrastructure, the proposed architecture aims to be flexible and reproducible while remaining transparent. Human-in-the-loop validation with its iterative feedback loop would mitigate the primary risk of AI-generated code, while the proposed dual-agent architecture could further reduce the need for manual intervention by automating quality assessment. The federated design would enable deployment across the heterogeneous EOSC landscape.

A distinctive aspect is the production of up to three citable, FAIR-compliant research products from a single request: the source code (PID n.1), the containerization environment manifest (PID n.2), and the generated synthetic dataset (PID n.3), aligning with the recognition of research software as a first-class scholarly output [22]. Federated SDGaaS also proposes to go beyond FAIR by introducing generative FAIRness: when a researcher cannot find a suitable dataset in any catalogue, the service would enable them to create what they cannot find.

Future work would focus on prototype implementation and empirical validation of the proposed architecture, development of cost models for federated computation, and governance frameworks for generated data quality and provenance. Security considerations, including code injection risks, LLM prompt manipulation, supply-chain attacks via generated libraries, and adversarial uses of synthetic data, will require dedicated threat modeling as part of any production deployment [24]. Additional directions include automated quality assurance with statistical fidelity tests, analysis of domain coverage limitations, a generator marketplace for sharing parameterized generators, and deeper integration with domain-specific ontologies as agentic AI systems mature.

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Using behavioral models in software development

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Abstract—We introduce a design and implementation of an extension to an existing prototype system for animating software architectures in Draw.io. The primary goal is to create a scripting language that enables a simpler, clearer, and more user-friendly way of writing animation scripts. Such a language aims to support a more intuitive understanding of the dynamics of software systems, their behavior, and the interactions between individual components. Since animation represents a visual depiction of the sequence of interactions, special emphasis is placed on designing a language capable of clearly describing individual steps, actions, and temporal dependencies between objects.

Index Terms—Software modeling, Visualization, Animation, UML, Unified Modeling Language, Class Diagrams, Sequence Diagrams

I. INTRODUCTION

The process of developing a large software system requires a high level of abstraction which is present throughout the whole development cycle. One of the key limiting factors in this process is the reliance on human communication, which is often imprecise and subject to ambiguity. Natural language, whether used in stakeholder discussions or in documentation, lacks the formal rigor necessary for unambiguous specification. Due to this, software development is slow and error-prone and relies on a number of collaborators to speed up the process and increase the probability of a mistake being caught [1].

Depending on the stage of the development cycle the collaborators and the need for collaboration changes [1]:

- Requirements, scope and capabilities of a project - in this stage the client stakeholders and developers work on describing the scope and capabilities of the desired system both on a high-level but also in detailed requirements from the client's side.
- Architecture and design of the system - system architects and designers must decide on a final uniform system architecture, framework, deployment pipeline and necessary infrastructure.
- Dependency management of tasks, artifacts and organizations - subdividing business requirements into tasks,

ordering them based on the order of implementation while different organization and their responsibilities are taken into consideration.

- Reducing dependencies between developers - making sure to maximize the most amount of work that can be done by different developers in parallel by eliminating the need for developers to depend on the work of others. Compartmentalizing task into individual modules ensures no conflicts emerge when merging the work of multiple engineers into the final system.
- Error handling - software errors and bugs may be found in any software system. Upon finding any type of unintentional or incorrect behavior it needs to be identified, recorded and resolved. This process has been implemented into multiple different facets of the development cycle. Every functionality should have multiple unit tests created to ensure every possible use-case is correctly implemented. Any code to be added to the system should have at least one reviewer that ensures quality of the provided code. Additional penetration and security testing by outside entities should also be done before delivering the final product.
- Documentation and project specific knowledge - the development of any sizable software system will require the project duration to be extensive, during which people may leave or more importantly join in which case it is necessary to be able to convey all the details of the project as well as the associated knowledge. Architectural decisions, workflow, project modularization and other specification should be recorded and stored in a collaborative documentation accessible to every collaborator.

For multiple stages of the development cycle one of the most effective ways to communicate vital information to other stakeholders is through the use of diagrams which visualize high level abstraction and concentrate concepts and relations of individual modules and components of the given software system [2].

One way of easing the complexity of a long running project is by using a standardized visual modeling language such as the Unified Modeling Language (UML) which is

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used to describe, design and document software systems. UML provides a way to describe not only structural but also behavioral aspects of the project to every stakeholder. That includes bridging the knowledge gap between technical and non-technical members by providing a coherent visual representation [3].

One caveat of using UML and diagrams in general, that due to the variety and required notation may be overwhelming for newcomers and misunderstanding of the interpretation of the diagrams can lead to errors and misuse. The steep learning curve may consume time and resources of the project [3].

One limiting factor may be in the static nature of the diagrams themselves. Their rigidity can not convey the dynamic structures of a working system and the communication between their respective components that happen in real time. Introducing dynamic movement in the form of animation, into existing structures may help speed up the understanding of stakeholders [4].

To address this challenge, we propose a lightweight solution that can be easily integrated into existing projects and systems. Our approach takes the form of a simple add-on for the widely used visualization tool Draw.io. Its goal is to bridge the communication and knowledge gap between technical and non-technical stakeholders by providing developers with an accessible visualization tool. This tool would be in the form of a plugin for the Draw.io application that would allow to use a simple scripting language to ease the process of creating animation scripts with `animation.js` commands. The main goal is to improve some aspects of the existing animation scripting as well as adding some basic programming structures to decrease the time and complexity for implementing said animation scripts.

II. RELATED WORK

The issue of visualizing software systems has been addressed multiple times in a variety of ways. In earlier works, the focus was placed on enhancing the experience of interacting with UML diagrams through additional sensory elements and changes in the visualization medium.

One approach [5] involved expanding diagrams into the third dimension and introducing new interaction methods. In Paul McIntosh's study, the eXtensible 3D standard was used as a medium for visualizing UML diagrams. This approach enabled the visualization of software systems in a three-dimensional environment and demonstrated the ability to display large state diagrams without significant performance issues.

The concept of introducing a third dimension was also explored in the work of Jakub Kučečka [6]. In this study, UML diagrams were moved from traditional screens into a virtual reality environment. The diagrams became part of the user's surroundings and incorporated hand tracking to enable interaction. Through the use of a virtual keyboard, users were able to interact not only with the diagrams but also with the underlying code base within the same virtual space.

Continuing the exploration of immersive environments, Anders Mikkelsen in [7] proposed the use of Microsoft's HoloLens device in a mixed reality setting. The study introduced the 3DML system, which creates a three-dimensional representation of UML diagrams and integrates the HoloLens into a natural user interface. In this system, the wearer's gestures are used as the primary means of interaction with the diagrams.

While these approaches provide novel ways of interacting with UML diagrams, they require specialized hardware, which introduces additional costs and training requirements beyond understanding UML itself. Furthermore, immersive technologies may increase the cognitive load on users and can lead to discomfort or motion sickness for some individuals, potentially limiting their widespread adoption.

In more recent studies, the focus has shifted from changing the visualization medium to incorporating artificial intelligence (AI) in the creation and understanding of diagrams.

In Aleksandar Gavric's research [8], the focus was on utilizing large amounts of empirical data to generate conceptual models of software systems using AI techniques. In this approach, AI models analyze UML diagrams and transform them into alternative representations such as images or sound in order to improve the learning experience.

Another AI-based approach was studied by Speth, Meissner, and Becker [9], who explored the use of the ChatGPT language model to generate software engineering exercises based on UML diagrams. Their research examined whether the model could interpret UML class and sequence diagrams and automatically generate educational exercises that help students better understand system structure and behavior.

Although AI-based techniques enable new ways of generating or explaining conceptual models, the accuracy and interpretability of automatically generated outputs may still require human validation. Additionally, these approaches often rely on external models or large training datasets, which may raise concerns regarding project confidentiality or require the development of specialized in-house models.

Similar approaches using scripting languages for animation, while scarce, do exist. One such example is AnimUML, presented in the work of Frédéric Jouault [10]. This tool introduces interactive features for analyzing UML diagrams within a browser environment. While AnimUML offers strong analytical capabilities and interactive elements, it appears to be less refined in terms of visual design and overall user experience. Furthermore, although its analytical functionality is well implemented, it does little to reduce the potential confusion experienced by non-technical users. Effectively using and understanding the tool requires a significant level of prior knowledge, which may limit its accessibility to a broader audience.

These limitations emphasize the need for a simpler and more lightweight solution that provides effective visualization while remaining practical for real-world software development environments, without imposing the burden of learning a new visualization paradigm. In this regard, more complex visual

solutions may appear more intuitive at first, however, they often introduce additional complexity by requiring users to learn an entirely new visual language. Also with the rise of generative AI's a more pragmatic scripting approach may be more useful in the future for generating animation scripts at a faster pace than any visual tool might be able to.

III. OUR APPROACH

Given the requirement for a small and versatile solution, an effective approach is to enhance an existing diagram creation tool that is already widely used in both educational and commercial settings. One such tool is Draw.io¹, which is commonly used for creating UML diagrams and supports the integration of plug-ins. Our light-weight extension allows enables UML modeling without incurring the costs associated with specialized software or hardware typically required for more complex solutions, such as AI-based visualization or VR equipment, as opposed to previously discussed tools. As a result, the proposed solution can be integrated directly into the existing tool while avoiding the need for specialized hardware. The goal of this approach is to provide an accessible method for interacting with UML diagrams while maintaining compatibility with existing development workflows.

For the visualization of diagrams, the built-in animation.js plugin will be used as the basis for the proposed implementation and will serve as the starting point for further development.

The plugin enables animated transitions between diagram elements, making it a suitable foundation for implementing animated UML diagrams and enhanced diagram interaction.

However, the plugin by itself may not be sufficient for creating practical animated UML diagrams due to the complexity of its syntax and the number of commands required to produce smooth and concise animations. These challenges can be divided into three main issues:

A. Diagram Element Naming

Each element in a diagram is assigned an automatically generated identifier within Draw.io. While these identifiers are unique, they are often difficult for developers to interpret. For example, a class named Student in a class diagram may be assigned an identifier such as "VTgfyJV5RG2zDUpsU9wH-10". Such identifiers do not provide any meaningful indication of the element they represent and are unnecessarily long, making them inconvenient to reference when defining animations.

B. Manual Pacing of the Animation

For an animation to remain understandable, appropriate pacing must be defined. In practice, this means that not all elements of a diagram should be highlighted or animated simultaneously, as this would make the visualization difficult to follow. Instead, animations should occur in a controlled sequence that guides the viewer's attention.

Within the animation.js plugin, this pacing must be defined manually. When a delay is required between animation commands, an explicit *wait* command must be inserted, specifying the duration of the pause in milliseconds. As a result, creating smooth and readable animations requires careful manual configuration of timing between individual animation steps. This often leads to duplicated commands and longer, less readable animation command sequences.

C. Code Repetition

Using only the built-in functions of the animation.js plugin causes the animation of more complex diagram constructs, such as loops and conditional branches, to require repeated and manually defined animation sequences.

For example, in the case of a *for* loop in a sequence diagram, the loop must be highlighted, then hidden, and this sequence must be repeated for the number of iterations the loop performs. As a result, the animation script must explicitly contain each repetition of the animation step.

This approach also limits the ability to animate dynamic behavior. If the number of loop iterations is not known in advance, for example when iterating over the elements of an array, the required animation sequence cannot be predefined. Consequently, animations can only be created for scenarios where the execution flow is known beforehand.

These limitations highlight the difficulty of creating maintainable and scalable animations using the current functionality of the animation.js plugin. To address these challenges, we propose the development of an additional plugin that introduces a higher-level abstraction layer in the form of a dedicated scripting language designed to streamline the process of writing animation scripts. We propose this approach because the built-in functionalities of animation.js are cumbersome and difficult to read. While adopting other programming languages might seem like a viable alternative, maintaining simplicity imposes certain constraints. In particular, any plug-in for Draw.io must be contained within a single .js file. As a result, importing external libraries or additional files is not feasible, since such functionality typically relies on Node.js features that cannot be utilized within the plug-in environment. This approach simplifies element referencing, automates animation pacing, and reduces repetitive animation definitions.

To minimize the amount of new syntax that potential users must learn, the proposed scripting language takes inspiration from the Python programming language. Python was chosen due to its widespread use and its reputation for readability and user-friendly syntax, which increases the likelihood that even less technical users can understand and work with the animation scripts.

D. Scripting Language

The example shown in Fig. 1 illustrates how the proposed scripting language addresses the limitations identified earlier. First, elements can be referenced using clear and human-readable identifiers, eliminating the reliance on opaque

¹<https://www.drawio.com/>

Draw.io IDs. Second, animation pacing is handled automatically in the background, reducing the need for explicit wait commands. Finally, repetition of identical animation steps is replaced with a for loop, simplifying the definition of repeated sequences.

```
animate sqd.Student
for i in range(5):
    sqd.Student -> sqd.Class
    animate sqd.Class
    hide sqd.Student sqd.Class
    hide sqd.Class
```

Fig. 1. Code snippet of the scripting language showcasing the semantic name, loop structure and animation commands

```
animate I_AdbzGn9Q0q4DHOUhW-26
wait 1500
roll I_AdbzGn9Q0q4DHOUhW-42
wait 1500
animate I_AdbzGn9Q0q4DHOUhW-37
wait 1500
hide I_AdbzGn9Q0q4DHOUhW-42
hide I_AdbzGn9Q0q4DHOUhW-37
roll I_AdbzGn9Q0q4DHOUhW-42
wait 1500
animate I_AdbzGn9Q0q4DHOUhW-37
wait 1500
hide I_AdbzGn9Q0q4DHOUhW-42
hide I_AdbzGn9Q0q4DHOUhW-37
roll I_AdbzGn9Q0q4DHOUhW-42
wait 1500
animate I_AdbzGn9Q0q4DHOUhW-37
wait 1500
hide I_AdbzGn9Q0q4DHOUhW-42
hide I_AdbzGn9Q0q4DHOUhW-37
roll I_AdbzGn9Q0q4DHOUhW-42
wait 1500
animate I_AdbzGn9Q0q4DHOUhW-37
wait 1500
hide I_AdbzGn9Q0q4DHOUhW-42
hide I_AdbzGn9Q0q4DHOUhW-37
```

Fig. 2. Code snippet of the animation.js native JavaScript version semantically equivalent to our version in Fig.1

E. Language Features

1) Human-Readable Element Referencing:

The scripting language allows diagram elements to be referenced using semantic names, replacing the opaque identifiers

```
if enrolled(sqd.Student):
    sqd.Student -> sqd.Class
    hide sqd.Student sqd.Class
```

Fig. 3. Code snippet of the scripting language showcasing conditional statement

generated by Draw.io. This eliminates the need to cross-check auto-generated IDs while writing animation scripts, as each element is clearly associated with its corresponding UML diagram. For example, ‘sqd.Student’ indicates the ‘Student’ lifeline within the sequence diagram ‘sqd’, making it immediately clear which diagram and element are being referenced. The semantic names are obtained from the Draw.io-generated xml files which hold the diagram data, including relation between semantic name and ID.

2) Automatic Animation Pacing:

To shorten and streamline the script, the need for manually defining delays between animation steps is removed. Instead of explicitly inserting wait commands, the system automatically adds an appropriate default pacing between consecutive animation actions, with the option of specifying custom timing where necessary. This allows users to focus on defining the logical sequence of the animation rather than managing low-level timing details. As a result, animation scripts become shorter, easier to read, and simpler to maintain.

3) Control Structures for Repeated Animations:

To address the issue of repetitive animation definitions (as shown in Fig.2), the scripting language supports common control structures, such as loops. These constructs allow repeated animation sequences to be expressed in a concise and readable manner. For example, a sequence of interactions that should occur multiple times can be defined using a for loop rather than manually repeating the same animation commands. This significantly reduces code duplication and makes animation scripts easier to maintain and modify.

F. Implementation

The proposed solution is implemented as a plugin for Draw.io that extends the existing functionality of the animation.js plugin. The plugin introduces a lightweight interpreter capable of parsing scripts written in the proposed animation language and translating them into the corresponding animation.js commands.

The implementation can be divided into several processing steps, as shown in Fig. 4. Based on the user-provided UML diagrams and the animation script, a preprocessing phase is first performed.

During this phase, the plugin processes the exported XML representation of the diagrams. The XML structure is analyzed to identify the building blocks used to construct UML elements. The names of these elements are extracted and paired with their corresponding Draw.io generated identifiers. This mapping provides the interpreter with a dictionary that allows semantic element references used in the scripting language to be translated into the internal identifiers required by Draw.io.

Fig. 4. Flowchart showcasing the phases of processing of our approach

In addition to processing the diagram structure, the animation script itself is tokenized during preprocessing. Since the proposed scripting language follows a Python-inspired syntax, indentation plays an important role in defining the structure of the script. Therefore, indent and dedent tokens are generated during tokenization so that the parser can correctly interpret the hierarchical structure of the user-defined animation script.

After the initial preprocessing phase, the resulting tokenized script is passed to a parser for syntactic analysis. The parser is generated using the `Peggy.js`² parser generator based on a formally defined grammar of the proposed scripting language. This grammar describes the valid structure of the animation scripts and enables the parser to transform the tokenized input into an abstract syntax tree (AST) that can be further processed by the interpreter.

The language grammar supports several basic programming constructs inspired by Python, including control flow statements such as `for` (as shown in Fig. 1), `if` (as shown in Fig. 3), and `while`. In addition, the language includes common programming features such as variable assignments, lists,

²<https://peggyjs.org/>

simple data structures, and user-defined functions. Alongside these general-purpose constructs, the grammar also defines the domain-specific animation commands that allow users to reference diagram elements and specify animation actions.

The resulting AST is constructed such that each node represents a specific command type and stores any additional information required for its interpretation. Depending on the command, this may include referenced diagram elements, control-flow parameters, or associated expressions.

The interpreter processes the AST by recursively traversing its nodes and executing the corresponding actions defined by the scripting language. During execution, the interpreter maintains an environment that stores the current state of variables and other runtime information. This environment is dynamically updated as the script is interpreted, allowing constructs such as loops, conditional statements, and variable assignments to influence the flow of the animation. Through this process, the high-level animation script is translated into the corresponding sequence of `animation.js` commands.

During this stage, the system also automatically inserts the necessary `wait` commands between animation actions. These delays are added implicitly to ensure appropriate pacing and visual clarity of the resulting animation, removing the need for users to manually define timing between individual animation steps.

The generated animation commands are then written to an output file, which is subsequently processed by Draw.io to produce the final animated visualization, as shown in Fig. 5.

IV. DISCUSSION

The proposed scripting language introduces a higher level of abstraction for creating animations in Draw.io diagrams. By removing the need to manually reference element identifiers and explicitly manage animation timing, the approach significantly improves the readability and maintainability of animation scripts.

Another important advantage is the ability to use common programming constructs such as loops and conditional statements. This allows complex animations to be described in a concise manner while reducing code repetition that would otherwise occur when using the standard `animation.js` functionality.

However, the current implementation also has several limitations. The scripting language currently supports a limited subset of programming constructs and animation operations. Additionally, the preprocessing step relies on the structure of the exported Draw.io XML files, which may change if the internal representation of diagrams evolves in future versions of the tool.

Future work could focus on expanding the supported animation commands, improving error handling within the interpreter, and providing an integrated scripting editor within the Draw.io interface. Another potential direction would be the development of visual debugging tools that allow users to step through animations generated from the scripting language.

Fig. 5. The generated animation in progress

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a scripting language designed to simplify the creation of animations in UML diagrams within the Draw.io environment. By introducing semantic element references, automatic animation pacing, and support for common programming constructs, the proposed approach significantly reduces the complexity and verbosity of animation scripts.

The implementation demonstrates how a lightweight interpreter and parser can be integrated into the Draw.io plugin ecosystem to extend the capabilities of the existing animation.js plugin. The resulting system enables users to describe complex animation sequences in a concise and readable form.

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Data Challenges in Artificial Intelligence Tools Research for Predictive Maintenance, Quality Management and Logistics

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Abstract—Artificial intelligence is increasingly recognised as a key enabler of the manufacturing systems of the future. However, the successful development and deployment of AI tools depend heavily on the quality, availability, and structure of manufacturing data. This paper examines the main data challenges of a project aiming at the deployment of artificial intelligence tools in industrial environments. Through a structured review of current research and industrial practices, we outline the main areas of project partners that represent significant data challenges. Our paper highlights the need for integrated data sources, consistent data quality, availability of labelled datasets, standardised data management practices, and transparent legislation. By clarifying the data-centric barriers that exist in manufacturing, this paper provides a foundation for the deployment of more robust artificial intelligence tools and supports future efforts to enable reliable and scalable solutions in real world production settings.

Keywords—artificial intelligence, data collection, economic determinants, manufacturing, predictive maintenance

I. INTRODUCTION

Rapid digitalisation of manufacturing has accelerated the adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) tools capable of optimising production processes, improving quality control, and enabling predictive maintenance. As industrial systems become increasingly interconnected, vast amounts of heterogeneous data are generated across machines, robots, sensors, and enterprise platforms. This data has significant potential to enable advanced AI-driven decision-making.

However, despite the growing enthusiasm for AI in manufacturing, the practical deployment of such tools remains constrained by persistent and multifaceted data challenges. As a result many AI tools in manufacturing fail not due to the

algorithmic limitations but due to unresolved data related obstacles.

II. PROJECT SCOPE

The PredictiveResearchLab project establishes a platform for the research, validation, and architectural design of AI-based solutions in predictive maintenance, manufacturing quality assurance, and industrial logistics. It represents a coordinated intersectoral research and development initiative designed to systematically address the methodological, technological, and economic aspects of AI deployment in industrial environments. The project aims to develop a platform for research in predictive maintenance, manufacturing quality, and logistics by applying advanced AI methods. Operating across TRL 2–5, it focuses on the methodological development and experimental validation of solutions that connect data-driven research with industrial application. The emphasis is placed on intelligent decision support for maintenance personnel through agentic AI approaches based on models deployable within edge infrastructure, enabling context-aware assistance, faster diagnostics, and operationally relevant recommendations close to the point of data generation.

The research covers hybrid and explainable AI, edge-deployed LLMs for diagnostic support, federated learning, edge and agentic AI, and the economic evaluation of AI adoption in industrial environments. It also addresses the architectural, governance, and integration requirements for scalable and secure deployment in manufacturing and logistics systems.

A central ambition of PredictiveResearchLab is to support the transition from reactive operational management to data-driven and predictive decision-making frameworks in industrial systems. In this context, particular attention is devoted not only to predictive and analytical AI models but

also to emerging agentic AI paradigms, where AI systems operate as semi-autonomous agents capable of reasoning, planning, contextual adaptation, and coordinated task execution within industrial ecosystems. Such agent-oriented architectures enable dynamic multi-agent orchestration and lay the foundation for self-optimising production and logistics systems.

III. STATE OF ART

Due to the broad specialisations of the project, we have identified multiple areas that need to be analysed through the project. These represent the area of expertise of the project partners and provide a basis for the identification of challenges in this paper.

The authors in [1] focused on the possibility of using Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA), which utilises long-term collected data. The authors had introduced two approaches before any analysis took place. The first approach was to determine all missing time steps in the SCADA time series. Every missing time step was assumed to be downtime for a wind turbine and marked as such. The second approach was to filter the data by their plausibility. If the signal was outside a plausible range, the signal was set to NaN at that point. These data points were not introduced in any data mining process. [1] SCADA data will undoubtedly be one of the important inputs to the research project. Typically, it includes sensory measurements of temperature, pressure, flow, vibration, electrical voltage and current, speed, level, and position of various actuators. In an article describing the integration of AI and IoT for predictive maintenance in Industry 4.0 [2], the authors also describe a data consolidation method. For short gaps in missing data, they used the feed-forward filling method. For larger gaps, they used the rolling mean method to fill in the missing values. The data set used in this study was collected over 11 months, from March 2023 to January 2024, resulting in a total of 39,470 records sampled at 10 min intervals.

The authors in [3] propose a comprehensive predictive quality inspection framework designed for automotive manufacturing in the context of Industry 4.0. The authors extend the traditional CRISP-DM methodology into a circular, continuously improving process that integrates machine learning models (e.g., XGBoost, CatBoost, Decision Trees, SVM) with automated retraining and business-strategy reassessment. The framework focuses on predicting vehicle quality at the end of the production line, particularly in relation to road test optimisation. The study highlights not only technical aspects of model selection and evaluation, but also the importance of deployment architecture, monitoring, and long-term sustainability of AI-driven quality control systems in industrial environments.

In [4] the authors address the lack of comprehensive best-practice guidelines for applying Big Data methods in production industry environments. The paper identifies recurring practical challenges in industrial datasets—such as data inconsistency, structural heterogeneity, missing identifiers, time synchronisation issues, and multilingual data formats—and categorises them according to data-quality dimensions (accuracy, completeness, consistency, validity, timelines, and uniqueness). The proposed BPMN-based process diagrams, lists of typical errors, and recommended solutions provide a structured and transferable approach to knowledge discovery in production data storages, supporting

predictive maintenance and Industry 4.0 applications in real industrial settings.

In [5] the authors propose an artificial intelligence platform to predict the quality of paint structure in automotive manufacturing within the Industry 4.0 framework. The paper addresses the challenge of integrating heterogeneous production-process data with quality measurement data obtained from spectrometers. The proposed AI platform was implemented as a proof-of-concept solution directly in the paint shop environment, demonstrating the feasibility of real-time quality prediction and highlighting the importance of data integration, preprocessing, and model validation for practical industrial deployment.

In the context of predictive maintenance, the data tested in the laboratory often differ from the real data obtained directly in production. In the paper [6], laboratory data and real data on wind turbine bearings were analysed and compared. This data set contained vibration data from accelerometers. Using a convolution neural network, an average data accuracy of 66.4% was achieved. In the study, the deep transfer network with multi-kernel dynamic distribution adaptation method was applied on the same data set achieving an average data accuracy of 88.9%.

In [7], the authors proposed an online transfer learning framework to predict the remaining bearing life, which explicitly addresses the shift in the distribution according to operating conditions. The results show that models trained in one domain show significant performance degradation in another and demonstrate that semi-supervised transfer learning combined with online adaptation can significantly improve the performance of predictive maintenance in a real application.

Previous research on the economics of predictive maintenance can be categorised into several distinct approaches, mainly focusing on (1) Cost-Minimisation and (2) Optimisation Models: Much of the literature focuses on defining objective functions to minimise the Long-Term Average Maintenance Cost Rate (AMCR) [8], [9], [10]. These models typically seek the optimal balance between inspection intervals, maintenance thresholds (such as reliability levels or probability of failure), and the remaining useful life (RUL) of components [11].

System-Level vs. Component-Level Maintenance: Earlier research focused on individual components, but modern studies have shifted toward system-level optimisation. This recognises “economic dependencies”, where maintaining multiple components simultaneously (opportunity maintenance) can share setup costs, such as transportation or specialised equipment, such as cranes [8], [11]. Integration with Production and Spare Parts Management: Researchers have developed Economic Production Quantity (EPQ) models that integrate predictive maintenance to minimise total costs, including inventory holding, setup, and the reworking of defective items produced when a system is in an “out-of-control” state. Other models integrate predictive maintenance with spare parts inventory to ensure that parts are available precisely when a predicted failure is imminent, reducing both inventory holding costs and downtime [12], [13]. Strategic and Stakeholder Analysis: Some recent research utilises System Dynamics (SD) and Evolutionary Game Theory (EGT) to evaluate the socio-economic impacts of predictive maintenance. This orientation moves beyond the firm to study

the dynamic interactions between enterprises (investing in predictive maintenance) and governmental authorities (providing subsidies or imposing penalties) [14]. Behavioural Economics Perspectives: Original methodologies have introduced Prospect Theory to maintenance optimisation. This approach recognises that human decision-makers are not always perfectly rational; they can overestimate low-probability, high-loss events, or exhibit “loss aversion” when deciding when to pull a machine for maintenance [15].

IV. DATA CHALLENGES IN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TOOLS RESEARCH

The implementation of artificial intelligence systems poses significant data challenges in the research and development life cycle. The significant limitation of AI no longer comes from algorithmic innovation, but from constraints in perfection and risks embedded in the data ecosystem. Issues such as data scarcity, annotation bottlenecks, distributional bias, privacy restrictions, and the difficulty of integrating heterogeneous data sources have become defining obstacles across all domains.

These challenges are amplified by the increasing scale of AI models, which require not only more data, but also more structured, representative, and ethically sourced datasets. At the same time, the rise of automated data-centric tools, such as synthetic data generators, self-supervised learning frameworks, and data quality assessment systems, represents a shift toward approaches that treat data as first-class research objects.

A. Data Sources in Manufacturing

Manufacturing data environments are typically characterised by heterogeneous and fragmented IT/OT ecosystems that have evolved organically over time. Core production components, including PLCs, SCADA/Historian platforms, MES, quality inspection systems, maintenance platforms, and enterprise applications, generally operate with limited architectural integration. Although large volumes of structured process data are generated at the shop floor level, data historization is commonly selective and is primarily driven by operational requirements rather than analytical objectives. Consequently, potentially valuable signals for predictive and diagnostic analytics are often unavailable or not adequately preserved. In addition, a weak contextual link between operational data and production context, together with temporal inconsistencies across systems, significantly constrains reliable cross system analysis. As a result, industrial environments remain data-rich at the signal level but limited at the architectural, semantic, and governance levels, which hinders the systematic deployment of advanced AI-driven manufacturing analytics.

Given the structural inconsistencies identified in the AS-IS analysis, the project extends data acquisition beyond production-level integration by incorporating laboratory-based industrial equipment equivalent to machines used in real manufacturing lines. These facilities enable the collection of authentic machining data under controlled yet realistic operating conditions, supporting systematic experimentation and high-resolution signal capture without relying on synthetic data. In addition, the project uses production-grade data from semiconductor manufacturing support systems, including LINAC-related infrastructure and auxiliary subsystems such as vacuum, exhaust, and cooling units. To

strengthen interoperability and scalability, the project also considers federated data-space integration through Manufacturing-X and Catena-X. This multi-layered data foundation supports rigorous industrial AI research and establishes the structural basis for agentic AI operating across distributed and sovereign data environments.

B. Artificial Intelligence Utilisation in Data Handling

Within the project, artificial intelligence is already applied in the data consolidation stage, which involves integrating heterogeneous data originating from multiple industrial systems. In industrial production environments, data are typically generated from various sources such as SCADA systems, MES platforms, maintenance systems, quality inspection stations, and shop-floor devices. These systems differ in schema design, naming conventions, sampling frequencies, and storage formats, which complicates their integration and subsequent analytical use.

For analytical tasks within the project, these heterogeneous datasets must therefore be transformed into a unified internal data model suitable for further processing by analytical and AI models. Traditional manual schema mapping approaches are time-consuming and difficult to scale when integrating new data sources. To address this challenge, the project considers the use of local large language models (LLMs) to support automated schema understanding and data mapping. LLMs can analyse metadata descriptions, column names, and data samples to infer semantic relationships between attributes and automatically propose mappings into the internal data format. Such approaches follow recent research trends in the use of LLMs for schema matching and automated data engineering tasks [16], [17].

For controlled interaction with external systems and analytical services, the system architecture may incorporate the Model Context Protocol (MCP), which allows language models to securely interact with external tools through a standardised interface. MCP enables LLM-based applications to invoke transformation tools, validation services, or analytical modules in a controlled and auditable manner, supporting automated data-integration workflows while preserving security and traceability [18]. After consolidation, the data pipeline continues with data preprocessing, including cleaning, normalisation, missing-value handling, and consistency validation. These steps prepare the data for downstream machine-learning tasks. Modern approaches increasingly rely on self-supervised learning techniques that allow models to learn structural patterns from time-series data without extensive manual labelling.

The next stage involves anomaly detection, which aims to identify deviations from normal operational behaviour of industrial equipment or production processes. Transformer-based architecture has recently demonstrated strong capabilities in modelling long-range dependencies within multivariate time-series signals. Models such as PatchTST and iTransformer have achieved state-of-the-art results in forecasting and anomaly detection benchmarks for multivariate time series [19], [20]. In certain industrial scenarios, parts of the analytical pipeline may also be deployed at the edge level. Edge AI architectures enable selected processing tasks to be executed close to the source of data generation, reducing communication overhead, and enabling faster detection of abnormal events. Such approaches

are particularly useful for high-frequency sensor streams or computer-vision data generated directly in manufacturing environments [21].

Another important step in the pipeline is automatic labelling and metadata generation. Large language models can analyse textual sources such as maintenance reports, alarm logs, or operator notes and convert them into structured metadata describing operational events. This metadata significantly improves the interpretability of industrial datasets and supports downstream analytics tasks. A central research focus of the project is time-series forecasting using transformer-based models. Recently, a new generation of time-series foundation models has emerged. These models are trained on large collections of time-series datasets and can generalise across multiple forecasting tasks. Early examples include Chronos and TimesFM, which apply transformer architectures to tokenised time-series representations [22], [23]. More recent research has introduced next-generation foundation models such as Chronos-2, Moirai, and Lag-Llama, which further improve generalisation capabilities and forecasting performance across heterogeneous time-series datasets. These models demonstrate strong results in large-scale forecasting benchmarks and represent a promising direction for industrial predictive analytics applications [24], [25]

Such approaches are particularly relevant in the context of predictive maintenance, where long-term dependencies in sensor signals can indicate gradual degradation of industrial equipment. Recent studies demonstrate that deep-learning-based monitoring approaches can significantly improve early fault detection and machine health monitoring in industrial systems [26]. In situations where production data cannot be directly shared due to confidentiality or regulatory restrictions, the project may also employ synthetic or anonymised datasets. Modern generative approaches, including diffusion-based models for time-series generation, enable the creation of realistic synthetic sequences that preserve the statistical properties of real data while removing sensitive information. These synthetic datasets can be used in laboratory environments for algorithm testing, benchmarking, and validation of AI models [27], [28].

Finally, the overall workflow, shown in Fig. 1, is coordinated through an orchestration layer, which manages the sequence of analytical operations and coordinates interactions between models and data-processing tools. This orchestration may operate fully automatically or in a human-in-the-loop configuration, where domain experts supervise and validate critical analytical decisions.

Fig. 1. AI data processing pipeline in the project

C. Real vs. Laboratory Data Utilisation

The project widely uses data for analysis of process and training of machine learning and artificial intelligence models. For this reason, data and their quality are the cornerstone of

the activities carried out in the project. Production data is the product of the real-world system and is created continuously and often under uncontrolled conditions. Production data best reflect the real functioning of the company and thus allow for the analysis of real process behaviour. Large amounts of variables influence the system simultaneously (e.g., machine wear, voltage fluctuations in the network, change of employee shifts, etc.), creating multifactorial data sets which enable a more complex analysis of processes in the areas of monitoring, alerting, and incident response. Real data bring reality to decision-making and enable verification of requirements and realistic testing that reflects real processes and reduces the risk of regression in production. However, real data often also contains transmission errors, sensor failures, or unrealistic values. The use of these data requires the implementation of robust data preprocessing before the analysis itself, as well as consistent data understanding to identify parameters that affect the desired results. The accuracy and suitability of the data is key to achieving project results that will be applicable in a real industrial environment. Given that data reflecting real operations may not exist for solving use cases implemented by partners, it will be necessary to supplement or link them with laboratory data. Laboratory data is obtained in a controlled environment to verify a hypothesis or to test the proposed solutions without disturbing influences. In laboratory conditions, very high repeatability of experiments can be achieved, which allows for the effective supplement of missing classes in datasets and compensation for data imbalances. Laboratory data generated based on real data allows for the generation of laboratory data for edge case scenarios that are not sufficiently represented in real data and are essential to ensure accurate AI models. Laboratory data allows to accelerate the development, training, and increase the quality of machine learning models by creating data in the required volume and quality necessary for the design of robust AI models. However, the obtained data are free from anomalies or random factors that may cause the slight correlations existing in the real data to be overlooked. In the event of unavailability of real data, laboratory data based on simulated operational scenarios represents the only option to obtain robust and validated data to obtain usable and defensible results.

The area of linking operational and laboratory data represents a key area of cooperation between the project partners, as well as the possibility of establishing cooperation and exchanging knowledge in other domains deploying AI solutions.

D. Economic Determinants of Predictive Maintenance

Due to the broad domain focus of the project, the initial focus for economic aspects was given on the predictive maintenance. Research into the economic aspects of predictive maintenance has evolved from simple cost-minimisation models to complex integrated systems that account for production scheduling, stakeholder dynamics, and the inherent uncertainty of machine degradation [9], [10], [14]. The following section details the primary orientations of previous research, the indicators used to measure success, and a critical analysis of current limitations.

1) Key Economic Indicators and Metrics

Research commonly employs several indicators to quantify the value of a predictive maintenance strategy:

- Return on Investment (ROI): Calculated as the ratio of incremental benefits (avoided costs and production gains) to incremental costs (technology acquisition, training, and infrastructure) [29], [30].
- Net Present Value (NPV): Used to assess the long-term feasibility of a predictive maintenance investment by discounting future cash flows (savings) over the equipment's useful life [31].
- Maintenance Cost Rate (MCR): The ratio of maintenance expenses to the component's RUL or lifecycle [9], [11].
- Production Capacity and Revenue Wastage: This measures the value of the useful life of unused components when a part is replaced preventively before it has reached its actual end-of-life [9].
- Downtime and Opportunity Costs: Research differentiates between planned downtime (lower cost) and unplanned downtime (higher cost), with the latter including lost production revenue, penalties for delayed delivery, and labour costs for idling workers [31], [32].

2) Space for Improvement

Although the body of knowledge is robust, several critical gaps and oversimplifications persist:

- Technical vs. Economical Metric Mismatch: A significant critique in the literature is the “mismatch” between technical performance metrics (such as precision, recall and F1-score) and actual business outcomes. A model with the highest F1-score does not necessarily result in the lowest maintenance cost. Cost-sensitive learning—which builds the actual cost structure into the model's objective function—is often cited as a necessary but underused alternative [33], [34].
- Ignoring RUL Economic Value: Most system-level approaches focus on minimising the long-term AMCR but fail to measure the economic value of the unused RUL of the components being maintained. Replacement of a component with 20% of its life remaining represents a wastage of capital that is often ignored in simple cost models [9], [34].
- Assumption of Instantaneous Maintenance: Many current models simplify the maintenance process by assuming it is completed immediately. In reality, maintenance duration significantly influences the grouping and sequencing of components, yet this is rarely addressed in system-level predictive maintenance research [9], [10].
- Lack of Real-World Data: A recurring criticism is that many studies are based on simulated or laboratory data rather than real-world industrial environments. This leads to models that may not account for practical constraints such as technician skill gaps, data ownership issues, or the “brownfield problem” of retrofitting old machinery [31], [35], [36].
- Undervaluing Intangible Costs: While tangible repair costs are easy to track, intangible costs—such as damage to customer relationships, reputation loss from delayed shipments, or safety/environmental risks—are

difficult to quantify and are frequently omitted from financial models [14], [15].

B. Legislative Aspects of Data Usage

The use of data in predictive maintenance, quality management, and logistics raises complex legal questions that extend beyond purely technical considerations and intersect with several regulatory regimes. The issues related to the acquisition, processing, sharing and secondary use of data influence not only the legal permissibility of specific operations, but also the architecture of the technical solution itself. From a legal perspective, it is therefore necessary to distinguish between different categories of data according to their nature and the applicable regulatory framework. Operational and technical data generated by industrial devices may qualify as confidential business information or trade secrets where they possess economic value due to their limited accessibility and where reasonable measures are taken to preserve their confidentiality. In such cases, contractual instruments—such as non-disclosure agreements—combined with appropriate technical and organisational safeguards are essential for ensuring lawful data sharing within industrial or research cooperation. Additional legal implications arise where the processed data qualify as personal data, particularly when monitoring technologies such as cameras or sensors enable the identification of individuals in operational environments. In these situations, the regime of the General Data Protection Regulation applies, requiring a lawful basis for processing, adherence to the principles of data minimisation and purpose limitation, and the implementation of adequate safeguards. The distinction between anonymisation and pseudonymisation becomes particularly relevant, as only irreversible anonymisation removes data from the scope of the GDPR. Furthermore, data used in predictive maintenance may fall within the scope of intellectual property protection, for instance, as protected databases or as part of software and analytical tools. The regulatory environment is further shaped by recent EU legislation, including the Data Act and the Artificial Intelligence Act, which introduce rules concerning access to device-generated data, data governance, and the quality of datasets used in AI systems.

V. CONCLUSION

The integration of AI into manufacturing holds immense promise in improving efficiency, quality, and adaptability across production systems. In our paper, we outlined that efficient deployment of AI in manufacturing is fundamentally constrained by persistent data-related challenges. These challenges are not only technical obstacles but reflect the structural and organisational complexities of modern manufacturing environments.

Our analysis underscores that addressing these challenges requires a data-centric approach in AI tools research. We highlighted issues such as heterogeneous data sources, inconsistent data quality, limited availability of labelled datasets, and the lack of standardised data management practices and legislation and cost efficiency evaluation benefits of AI tools implementation. Based on our analysis, the manufacturing sector must prioritise long-term strategies for data collection, annotation, and curation to support robust and scalable AI solutions.

This paper, which represents the initial phase of our project, provides a foundation for future research aimed at the

deployment of more resilient, transparent, and trustworthy AI systems in manufacturing.

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Automatic Extraction of UML Class Diagram Structure from Images

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Abstract—This paper presents an end-to-end pipeline for converting UML class diagram images into normalized PlantUML. The pipeline processes UML class diagram images, enforces PlantUML-only output, validates syntax, parses structural elements, and stores per-diagram artifacts. We evaluated quality on a set of 14 diagrams using structure-level precision/recall/F1 for classes, edges, attributes, and methods. Two proprietary models (GPT-5.2 and Gemini 2.5 Flash) are compared with a local open-source baseline (LLaVA v1.5, 7B), where the latter shows unstable and invalid structured outputs. Both proprietary models are strong on class extraction, edge extraction is moderate, and attribute/method extraction remains the main bottleneck.

Index Terms—PlantUML, UML, Class Diagram, Visual Language Model, LLM, GPT, Gemini, Image-to-structure, Diagram-to-code generation, Visual information extraction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Software engineering projects often include UML class diagrams as part of their documentation, architecture descriptions, or design specifications. However, in many practical settings these diagrams are not stored in a structured, machine-readable form. Instead, they often exist only as raster images, screenshots, scanned documents, or exported figures embedded in reports and presentations. While such visual representations are useful for human communication, they are difficult to reuse in automated workflows, since the underlying structural information about classes, attributes, methods, and relationships is not directly accessible.

Converting UML class diagram images into a structured representation such as PlantUML is therefore an important problem. PlantUML provides a compact, editable, and machine-readable textual format that preserves the semantics of a class diagram while also remaining easy to render back into a visual form. Once a diagram is represented as PlantUML, it can be versioned, searched, transformed, validated, compared against

other versions, and integrated into downstream software engineering pipelines.

This study develops a pipeline for converting UML diagram images into structured PlantUML outputs, with the resulting image–PlantUML pairs serving as a dataset for controlled evaluation of how reliably multimodal models recover classes, members, and relationships from visual inputs. The problem is also practical: many UML artifacts in reports, wikis, and legacy documentation exist only as images, while agent-based tools and automated engineering workflows need text-based specifications. Converting UML images to PlantUML therefore supports documentation migration, reverse engineering, design–implementation consistency checks, architecture retrieval, and downstream code or test scaffolding.

This paper presents and experimentally evaluates an end-to-end pipeline for automatically extracting structural information from UML class diagram images. The source data consists of 655 images of UML class diagrams [1]. For each image, the pipeline produces a normalized representation of the diagram as PlantUML code. The resulting dataset is available in a public GitHub repository¹.

In addition to large-scale dataset generation, the study includes a gold subset evaluation where model outputs are compared against manually curated ground truth using automatic structure-level metrics (classes, relationships, attributes, methods).

The main objective is to build a robust pipeline that converts UML class diagram images into PlantUML code, and evaluate its quality.

II. RELATED WORK

Ranjani and Prabhudesai [2] study evaluation for *image-to-UML* conversion in telecom documents with embedded UML *sequence* diagrams. They show that producing PlantUML alone is not sufficient and propose component-level metrics

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¹<https://github.com/ViktorOvchinnikov/Automatic-Extraction-of-UML-Class-Diagram-Structure-from-Images>

(participants, message flow, ordering, grouping constructs) together with script-diff comparison against curated references. Their results indicate that basic elements are recovered more reliably than complex constructs. Munde [3] reaches a similar conclusion from direct VLM benchmarking on UML: the task combines OCR-like reading of small dense text with global relational reasoning, and meaningful progress depends on domain datasets and explicit task-specific metrics.

Beyond UML-specific studies, recent work on structured visual understanding provides useful methodological guidance. ChartBench [4] and Image2Struct [5] frame such tasks as a combination of low-level recognition and higher-level relation reasoning. The same decomposition applies to UML: recognizing class/member text is primarily a reading problem, whereas reconstructing relationships is a structural reasoning problem. This perspective aligns with our use of normalized graph parsing and micro-averaged precision/recall/F1 over classes, edges, attributes, and methods, since the goal is not only textual similarity but recovery of usable machine-readable structure.

Conrardy and Cabot [6] report early UML-from-image results with LLM/VLM pipelines, emphasizing staged prompting and error-focused evaluation, including non-compilation and hallucinations. Their findings support our choice to enforce PlantUML-only output and automatic parse validation as a first filtering step, while still analyzing structural errors that remain even when the output is syntactically valid.

Bates et al. [7] also study UML image-to-PlantUML conversion and identify dataset availability as a major bottleneck, motivating synthetic data construction and fine-tuning strategies. Their “render-and-compare” idea, based on metrics such as SSIM and BLEU, is useful as a complementary signal when exact identifier matching is incomplete, but it should not replace structure-level precision/recall/F1, since visually plausible diagrams may still encode incorrect semantics.

III. METHODOLOGY

To provide a clear and reproducible description of the extraction workflow, we formalize the image-to-PlantUML process as the staged pipeline shown in Fig. 1. This part of the methodology focuses on transformation mechanics, i.e. how a raster UML diagram is converted into structured PlantUML artifacts. The stages are intentionally separated so that each step has a single responsibility and can be traced in logs during large-scale runs.

The pipeline in Fig. 1 is executed in four stages. First, the input stage reads a raster UML class diagram image and forwards it unchanged to the model so that visible textual and layout cues are preserved. Second, in direct PlantUML inference, the vision model receives the image with a fixed instruction prompt and generates PlantUML in a single pass. Third, post-processing cleans the raw response by removing non-PlantUML fragments, enforcing `@startuml...@enduml` boundaries, and normalizing formatting for consistent parsing. The normalized code is then parsed into a structured internal representation (classes, edges,

Fig. 1. Pipeline used in the current experiments for UML image to PlantUML generation and evaluation.

attributes, and methods), which makes the output stable for downstream tooling. Finally, the output stage stores a per-diagram artifact `<id>.puml` together with run metadata and logs (for example, generation status, parser status, and timestamps), yielding a reusable machine-readable corpus.

To keep the generation stage reproducible, the following prompt was used for direct UML \rightarrow PlantUML conversion experiments in proprietary models:

You are an assistant that reads UML CLASS DIAGRAMS from images and rewrites them as normalized PlantUML code.
 Your task: Given the image of a UML class diagram, output the corresponding PlantUML code that describes the classes and relationships you can clearly see.
 Rules: 1. Output ONLY PlantUML code. Do NOT output any explanations, comments or Markdown code fences. 2. Always start with: `@startuml ...classes and relationships... @enduml` 3. For each class, use the syntax: `class ClassName +attribute: Type +operation(param: Type): ReturnType` If you cannot read attributes or operations, you may omit the body and use just: `class ClassName` 4. Use EXACT class names, attribute names and operation names from the diagram. If you cannot read a name, SKIP that element instead of guessing. 5. For inheritance, use: `ParentClass |— ChildClass` 6. For associations, use: `ClassA - ClassB` Optionally with multiplicities in quotes, for example: `ClassA "1" - "*" ClassB` 7. For composition and aggregation, use: `ClassA *- ClassB (composition)` `ClassA o- ClassB (aggregation)` 8. Do NOT invent classes, attributes, operations or relationships that are not present in the image. 9. Do NOT add comments inside the PlantUML code.
 If the diagram is very large, include only the main classes and relationships that are clearly readable.

Fig. 2. Prompt used in proprietary models for direct UML image to PlantUML generation.

In summary, the pipeline defines a reproducible raster-to-PlantUML workflow in which each diagram is processed with the same prompt, normalization rules, and artifact export policy. This standardization reduces format drift and keeps generated outputs structurally consistent across large batches. The resulting `<id>.puml` files provide a stable machine-

readable representation that can be rendered, versioned, and reused in downstream tooling.

IV. BASELINE VISION MODEL

As part of the model research stage, we evaluated a local open-source vision-language model as a baseline. We selected LLaVA v1.5 (7B) due to its popularity and availability, and attempted to run it on a single GPU instance (NVIDIA T4 16GB) with limited CPU resources (4 CPU / 16 RAM). The baseline goal was to verify whether a locally deployed VLM can reliably extract UML class diagram structure from images and output a machine-readable representation; in this stage we considered both strict JSON extraction of classes, attributes, and relationships and optional direct PlantUML generation, but used a JSON-first workflow to simplify automatic post-processing and validation.

To address GPU memory limitations, we enabled 4-bit quantization. This resolved immediate CUDA out-of-memory errors but introduced operational constraints, because quantized models cannot be moved with `model.to(device)` and require careful device placement for all tensors. In practice, inference could be executed, so the limiting factor was not runtime stability but output quality and structural reliability.

For UML structure extraction, we prompted the model to produce strict JSON using the instruction shown in Fig. 3.

You see a UML class diagram. Identify all classes, their attributes, and relationships (association, inheritance, aggregation, composition) and return STRICT JSON. Return ONLY JSON and nothing else.

Fig. 3. Prompt used in LLaVA v1.5 (7B) for UML image to JSON representation generation.

Despite successful inference, produced artifacts were invalid. The most common failure pattern was template copying, where the model repeated schema-like placeholders such as `ClassName`, `ClassA`, or `attr: Type` instead of diagram-specific entities. Another recurring issue was invalid JSON caused by truncation or syntax mistakes, and we also observed degenerate repetition in which one detected class name was copied many times together with duplicated attribute blocks.

A representative example of this failure is shown in Fig. 4. For one UML image, the model repeatedly emitted the same class and then terminated JSON mid-structure:

```
{
  "classes": [
    {
      "name": "ConcreteImplementor",
      "attributes": [
        {
          "name": "concreteImplementor",
          "type": "string"
        }
      ],
      "name": "ConcreteImplementor",
      "attributes": [
        {
          "name": "concreteImplementor",
          "type": "string"
        }
      ],
      "name": "ConcreteImplementor",
      "attributes": [

```

Fig. 4. Invalid JSON response produced by LLaVA v1.5 (7B).

This output is not valid JSON and cannot be directly consumed by a downstream conversion step (JSON \rightarrow PlantUML). More importantly, the repetition indicates that the model failed to recover global diagram structure and instead reproduced a local pattern. Taken together, these observations show that the tested LLaVA configuration does not meet minimum quality requirements for large-scale UML artifact generation: even successful inference often yields invalid or incomplete structure, dense diagrams with small text reduce extraction fidelity, and recurrent template-copying or truncation behavior weakens artifact usability. For this reason, we report the open-source local baseline as a negative result and use it primarily as evidence motivating the transition to proprietary multimodal models.

V. EVALUATION

After this baseline stage, we evaluated GPT-5.2 and Gemini 2.5 Flash under the same prompt-driven UML \rightarrow PlantUML setting.

The evaluation setup follows two-track design. The dataset [1] contains 655 UML class diagram images in .png, .jpg, and .jpeg formats, and model outputs are stored by diagram ID. The dataset-generation track processes the full image set to produce PlantUML artifacts under strict formatting constraints with basic syntactic validation [8], while the gold-subset track measures structural fidelity on curated diagrams with available GT by parsing outputs into a normalized graph representation and computing precision/recall/F1 for classes, relationships/edges, attributes, and methods. The curated gold subset consists of 14 images used for evaluation. This split keeps the study practical at full scale and scientifically comparable on a controlled subset. In this section, we focus on the gold-subset protocol and evaluation metrics.

For each UML diagram we compare the model output against the ground truth (GT) separately for four element types: classes, edges (relationships), attributes, and methods. For a given element type, we treat both GT and model output as *sets* of extracted items after normalization (e.g., consistent casing/spacing rules, and a canonical string representation for each item). For edges, the evaluation abstracts away relationship type (e.g., aggregation, composition, inheritance) and multiplicity; it only checks whether a connection between class *A* and class *B* is present (true/false), regardless of type or cardinality. For classes, attributes, and methods, matching is based on exact string equality after standard normalization (e.g., lowercasing and whitespace cleanup). As a result, spelling differences are counted as mismatches even if the model captured the intended text or corrected a typo in the GT. We evaluated each diagram using set-based Precision, Recall, and F1-score, comparing the predicted and ground-truth sets of classes, edges, attributes, and methods.

The current state of the evaluation includes a gold subset comparison with: GT (14 diagrams) and model outputs available for the same IDs for both models. For each diagram, the evaluation computes precision/recall/F1 over extracted

sets of elements. Aggregate results are reported using micro-averaging across all gold diagrams. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
MICRO-AVERAGED STRUCTURE EXTRACTION METRICS ON THE GOLD SUBSET (14 DIAGRAMS), WITH ATTRIBUTE/METHOD EVALUATION ENABLED.

Element	Model	Precision	Recall	F1
Classes	GPT-5.2	0.966	0.966	0.966
Classes	Gemini 2.5 Flash	0.973	0.979	0.976
Edges	GPT-5.2	0.809	0.620	0.702
Edges	Gemini 2.5 Flash	0.702	0.707	0.704
Attributes	GPT-5.2	0.364	0.194	0.253
Attributes	Gemini 2.5 Flash	0.472	0.606	0.531
Methods	GPT-5.2	0.526	0.647	0.580
Methods	Gemini 2.5 Flash	0.624	0.554	0.587

For classes, both models are very strong and close overall, with Gemini showing a slightly higher micro F1 because of marginally better recall. For edges, the models are also comparable in F1, but with a different balance: GPT is typically more precise and less recall-oriented, whereas Gemini tends to recover more edges at the cost of additional spurious links in some diagrams. For attributes versus methods, Gemini substantially outperforms on attributes while method quality remains similar across models; the lower GPT-5.2 attribute F1 is consistent with attribute–method boundary errors in generation, where the model tends to express some attribute-like members in a method-like form, resulting in attribute misses and method extras.

VI. QUALITATIVE ERROR ANALYSIS

The per-diagram diffs reveal several recurring issues that are important both for model comparison and for pipeline robustness:

A key issue is that, while PlantUML conventionally distinguishes attributes from operations, VLM-generated PlantUML often blurs these conventions (e.g., missing parentheses in operation signatures, inconsistent type placement, or OCR-like spacing artifacts). As a result, the separation of class members into “attributes” and “methods” becomes sensitive to normalization and parsing heuristics. In per-diagram diffs, this appears as attribute-like strings in `methods_extra` (e.g., `field:type`) together with matching `attributes_missing` entries. Therefore, attribute/method scores are best interpreted as end-to-end pipeline measurements (model output + normalization/parsing), rather than as a pure indicator of model-level conceptual understanding (see Figures 8, 9, 10, 11, 12 and 13).

In addition, relationship reconstruction is affected by identifier normalization and naming variation. A noticeable share of errors comes from minor typos and near-duplicate class names, for example `pictureviewer` vs. `picureviewer` and `projectplatformpage` vs.

`cprojectplatformpage`. Edge mismatches are also unevenly distributed across the subset: some diagrams are reconstructed almost perfectly, while a smaller set of “hard” diagrams concentrates most edge misses and extras, especially in dense layouts or when non-standard relationship markers are used (see Figures 5, 6 and 7).

Fig. 5. Case A (ID 231 - Gemini 2.5 Flash): Rendered PlantUML comparison; includes a non-existing edge in this case.

Fig. 6. Case A (ID 231 - GPT 5.2): Rendered PlantUML comparison; predicts `picureviewer` instead of `pictureviewer`.

VII. LIMITATIONS

This section summarizes the main threats to validity together with practical mitigation directions. A key methodological threat is the current edge-matching assumption: re-

Fig. 7. Case A (ID 231): Ground Truth.

Fig. 9. Case B (ID 177 - GPT 5.2): Rendered PlantUML comparison; attributes are weakly recovered and edges are missed entirely.

Fig. 8. Case B (ID 177 - Gemini 2.5 Flash): Rendered PlantUML comparison; attributes are weakly recovered with attribute/method confusion.

relationship evaluation is binary and ignores UML relation type (e.g., aggregation, composition, inheritance) and multiplicity, checking only whether a connection between class *A* and class *B* exists. Therefore, an edge with incorrect semantic type or cardinality can still be counted as correct, which can overestimate structural faithfulness for relationships. Identifier normalization should reduce sensitivity to whitespace, punctuation, and minor typos where appropriate, while still preserving exact-name constraints for dataset artifacts, and attribute/method parsing should be hardened to avoid classifying attribute-like entries as methods when parentheses are absent and to normalize signature formatting consistently. Several additional risks still define the current study limitations: model hallucinations and format drift can appear and require strict prompting, retries, and post-validation; small text in UML diagrams can reduce readability and therefore extraction quality even with preprocessing; proprietary models inference

Fig. 10. Case B (ID 177): Ground Truth.

Fig. 11. Case C (ID 305 - Gemini 2.5 Flash): Rendered PlantUML comparison; captures more class connections in this diagram.

Fig. 12. Case C (ID 305 - GPT 5.2): Rendered PlantUML comparison; extracts fewer class connections, with formatting differences such as name:type vs type name.

introduces cost and rate-limit constraints for large batches; and complete ground-truth annotation remains expensive, which is why the current setup relies on a smaller curated gold subset with automatic structural checks.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This work demonstrates a practical end-to-end pipeline for converting raster UML class diagram images into structured PlantUML at scale. The empirical results show that current proprietary multimodal models can recover core class and edge

Fig. 13. Case C (ID 305): Ground Truth.

structure reasonably well, while attribute/method extraction remains a major bottleneck. Given the identified threats to validity, especially the simplified edge metric and sensitivity to parsing/normalization, the reported scores should be interpreted as strong evidence of practical utility rather than as fully semantic UML equivalence.

IX. FUTURE WORK

Future work should prioritize three directions that directly follow from the current limitations: richer edge evaluation that includes relationship type and multiplicity, stronger normalization and parser robustness for noisy member signatures, and expansion of the gold subset with broader diagram complexity. In parallel, integrating lightweight image preprocessing and confidence-aware extraction could improve robustness on small text and dense layouts while keeping the pipeline reproducible.

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Creating a Dataset of Use Case–Sequence Diagram Pairs Using Large Language Models

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Abstract—This paper focuses on the creation and processing of a dataset intended for the evaluation of methods in the field of software engineering. It concentrates on forming data pairs consisting of a use case and its corresponding UML sequence diagram. Based on the theoretical background described in the thesis, the data is collected from publicly available repositories on the GitHub platform and generated using artificial intelligence, specifically the GPT-3.5 model. Validation is used to verify the correctness of the data, and metadata are collected for each record. The created dataset is analyzed using selected statistical methods, which highlight its advantages and limitations for further use in the development and testing of software tools. The suitability of the dataset for machine processing is verified through the evaluation of software that transforms a use case into a sequence diagram. The evaluation results show that the created dataset serves as a suitable input for training, testing, and comparing the performance of various approaches in the field of software modeling automation.

Index Terms—dataset, dataset construction, software engineering, software development, PlantUML

I. INTRODUCTION

In software engineering, there has long been an effort to automate various activities that arise during software development. One such activity is the creation and maintenance of documentation. Although documentation is an important part of the development process, in practice it is often created inconsistently or with minimal priority. However, system diagrams and models play an important role in understanding the architecture and behavior of a system.

Different software engineering artifacts often describe the same system functionality from different perspectives. For example, a use case describes system behavior in natural language, while a sequence diagram can capture the same behavior in a visual form. This similarity creates an opportunity for research into methods capable of transforming one artifact into another.

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The transformation of a use case into a sequence diagram is particularly interesting because both artifacts represent the dynamic behavior of a system. A use case describes individual steps of interaction between an actor and the system, while a sequence diagram visualizes communication between objects in temporal order. Automatic transformation between these artifacts could significantly simplify the creation of documentation and support consistency between different system models.

One of the main challenges in this area of research is the lack of high-quality datasets. Many existing approaches are evaluated only on small amounts of data or on datasets that are not publicly available. This significantly limits the possibility of comparing different solutions.

In recent years, new possibilities for data generation have emerged through the use of large language models (LLMs). These models are capable of generating text in natural language and are suitable, for example, for creating use cases or textual representations of diagrams.

II. RELATED WORK

The authors of paper *Seamless Transformation from Use Case to Sequence Diagrams* [1] present a tool designed to support the teaching of software design. The main goal of the tool is to increase consistency between different phases of system design. The tool accepts as input a textual use case diagram written in the PlantUML language and generates a sequence diagram also in textual form. The program analyzes the input file line by line, extracts information about actors and actions, and stores them together with their execution order. Based on this information, it then generates a sequence diagram in which messages between objects are represented by actions from the use case. The disadvantage of this approach is that the input must have a very specific structure. The transformation is therefore not universal but depends on the format of the input use case. In addition, the paper contains only limited experimental results, and the testing is demonstrated using only a single example.

Another approach is a method for transforming a scenario into a sequence diagram described in the paper *Transformation Method from Scenario to Sequence Diagram* [2]. The authors defined their own language called SCEL, which is used for the formal representation of a scenario. This language makes it possible to maintain an appropriate level of abstraction for scenario steps while also providing the structure necessary for generating a sequence diagram. In this method, individual actions of the scenario are divided into source, destination, object, and instrument. The noun represents the message in the sequence diagram, the source determines the sender, and the destination determines the receiver of the message. Based on keywords, it is also possible to identify fragments such as conditions or loops. The result of the transformation is a sequence diagram written in the PlantUML language, which can subsequently be edited or visualized. This approach demonstrates that a structured textual description of system behavior can be a suitable input for automatic diagram generation.

Laura Méndez et al. [3] proposed a toolkit designed to assist students in constructing sequence diagrams from use cases. Using natural language processing methods, the approach analyzes sentences within the use case and identifies the most significant words representing objects and messages. Since the tool operates on Spanish text, it relies on prepositions to determine relationships between elements. These linguistic structures are used to establish links between actors, actions, and system components in order to construct the sequence diagram. The authors also recommend writing use cases in a specific form suitable for automated processing following the rule *Who does what to whom?*. However, the toolkit itself was not evaluated.

Jitendra Singh Thakur and Atul Gupta [4] focused on the transformation of a use case diagram and use case specifications into a sequence diagram. Their approach processes natural English language descriptions and constructs a sequence diagram based on parts of speech and sentence structure using predefined rules. The paper employs a structured representation of the use case, including identifiers for individual steps of the scenario. The resulting tool was compared with other approaches to transformation and evaluated on examples presented in the referenced papers.

In the paper [5], the authors investigate how LLMs can streamline the process of use case creation. Five experts first manually construct a use case diagram based on the requirements and subsequently generate it with the assistance of an LLM. The generation process consists of multiple steps, allowing intermediate outputs to be reviewed. The results of both approaches are then compared, with accuracy and completeness also being evaluated. The findings indicate that the generated outputs achieve sufficient accuracy compared to manually created use case diagrams, while capturing a greater number of elements from the requirements. This highlights the efficiency of using LLMs and their suitability for use case creation.

All of the mentioned studies focus primarily on the trans-

formation process itself, which is not the main objective of our research. However, they provide useful perspectives on the characteristics and features that are important to consider when working with use cases and sequence diagrams.

III. DATA GENERATION

One of the main problems in research on transformations of software engineering artifacts is the lack of suitable datasets. Existing work often uses only small amounts of data or proprietary dataset collections that are not publicly available. This makes it difficult to compare different approaches and reproduce experiments. Real use cases and sequence diagrams do exist within software projects; however, their systematic collection is challenging. Software project documentation is often incomplete or stored in various formats. Therefore, it is necessary to complement available data with artificially generated records.

Generating data using artificial intelligence allowed us to expand the dataset with additional records. We used large language models to generate new textual artifacts, as these models are capable of producing natural language text similar to human writing. This property makes them particularly suitable for creating use cases, which are typically written in natural language.

In our work, we used the LLM model to automatically generate new use cases and subsequently derive sequence diagrams from them in textual form. Through this process, we were able to create additional pairs of artifacts that could be incorporated into the dataset. An important advantage of this approach is that it enables us to generate a large number of diverse records while maintaining control over the structure of the output by carefully designing the prompts used for generation.

Fig. 1: Dataset creation process.

A. Data collection

The dataset creation process consisted of several steps shown in Fig. 1:

- 1) Collection of existing data – The first step is obtaining existing use cases and UML diagrams from public repositories on the GitHub platform.

Fig. 2: Sequence diagram collected from Github.

- 2) Identification of relevant files – Within repositories, files containing use cases or sequence diagrams are searched for, for example based on file extensions or file names.
- 3) Data validation – The obtained use cases and diagrams are checked to verify that they meet the required structure and content.
- 4) Generation of new data using an LLM – A language model is used to generate new use cases and subsequently sequence diagrams in the PlantUML language.
- 5) Metadata collection – Additional information is stored for each record, enabling further analysis of the dataset.

During the data generation process, we used the GPT-3.5 language model, which enables automatic text generation through an API interface. We selected this model mainly because of the availability of a Python library and the possibility of configuring generation parameters. In our dataset, we represent sequence diagrams using the PlantUML language, which allows diagrams to be written in textual form and subsequently visualized automatically. While generating the data, we configured several model parameters that influence the variability of the output. In particular, we experimented with the parameters *temperature* and *top_p*, which affect the level of randomness in the generated responses and therefore also influence the diversity of the created data.

B. Synthetic data generation

The quality of generated responses strongly depends on the formulation of the prompt. Even a small change in the structure or wording of the query can lead to different results. The initial experiment used a simple prompt whose goal was to create a use case based on a sequence diagram. However, this approach resulted in responses with inconsistent structure. The model often generated text containing a description of the use case, a list of actors, the main scenario, or comments, while the output format varied significantly between responses. In some cases, the model even rewrote the content of the input diagram instead of creating the required textual description.

For this reason, it was necessary to improve the formulation of the prompt and specify the required output more precisely. In designing the prompt, approaches from prompt engineering

1. Chef selects ingredient to update.
2. UI layer requests current expiry date from backend server.
3. Backend server queries ingredient expiry date from database.
4. Database returns the expiry date.
5. Backend server shows the current expiry date to UI layer.
6. Chef inputs new expiry date.
7. UI layer submits the updated expiry date to backend server.
8. Backend server updates the expiry date in the database.
9. Database confirms the update to backend server.
10. Backend server confirms the successful update to UI layer.
11. UI layer displays the update confirmation to the Chef.

Listing 1: Main steps of generated use case for Fig. 2.

were used, including clarifying the query and defining the required output format. One of the tested strategies was explicitly providing the structure of the result in the form of a DTD schema, which illustrates the final prompt used in the experiment). The model was then expected to generate a use case in XML format according to the given schema.

During testing, we observed that the model automatically added a DOCTYPE declaration referencing the DTD schema, which caused the generated document to become invalid during subsequent validation. This problem was resolved by adding an explicit instruction telling the model not to include this element in the response. After this modification, the responses met the required format.

```

{"role": "user", "content": "Based on the following sequence diagram, create a usecase in xml for following DTD schema and return it without any comments."},
{"role": "user", "content": "Here is DTD schema <td> and do not mention DOCTYPE in response."},
{"role": "user", "content": "For mainSequence steps use id in format S1, for asteps A1 and steps inside A1S1, for esteps E1 and steps inside E1S1"},
{"role": "developer", "content": "Make sure the actor is visible in each step and try write full sentences with active verb phrases that describe the sub-goals getting completed."},
{"role": "user", "content": "Here is sequence diagram in plantuml <seq>"}
  
```

Listing 2: Final prompt for generating use case.

Another problem concerned the identifiers of individual scenario steps. The model generated identifiers in different formats, which complicated automated data processing. Therefore, we added an instruction defining exact rules for identifier creation for main, alternative, and exception scenarios to the context. After introducing this instruction, the generated responses consistently met the required identifier format.

1. UAVs are activated and armed.
2. Operators dynamically generate flight routes, including sample collection points for the targeted area.
3. DroneResponse requests and receives flight authorization.
4. The operator issues a command to start the mission.
5. UAVs perform synchronized takeoff.
6. The UAVs fly their assigned routes and collect and analyze samples at their assigned collection points.
7. When a UAV has completed its collection assignment, it returns home.
8. The operator removes samples and replaces and/or replenishes onboard sampling supplies.
9. Steps 4-8 are repeated until all needed samples have been collected.
10. The Drone Commander ends the mission.

Listing 3: Main steps of use case from Github

Another observed characteristic was that if the sequence diagram contained messages written as function calls with parameters, the model tended to generate scenario steps only as the names of the functions. Such output did not meet the requirements for a high-quality use case description, where each step should contain at least a subject, verb, and object. For this reason, we extended the prompt with an instruction derived from principles of writing effective use cases [6], which explicitly instructed the model how to formulate individual scenario steps. Listing 1 illustrates the generated use case derived from the sequence diagram in Fig. 2 using the prompt shown in Listing 2.

From the collected data, additional information was extracted into metadata such as the number of actors, the number of use case steps, the origin of the record, the repository and time of the last commit, or the model and generation time. The resulting records were stored in separate files and metadata were stored in JSON format due to efficient processing.

A similar approach was followed in transforming the use case into a sequence diagram. Due to the more complex syntax required for the correct handling of execution specifications, this aspect was not enforced in the prompt. It was only necessary to supplement the prompt with instructions for the

```
{
  "role": "user",
  "content": "Based on the following use case, create a sequence diagram in plantuml without any comments.",
  "role": "user",
  "content": "In sequence diagram if name of element contains multiple words, put it in quotation marks and give diagram title",
  "role": "user",
  "content": f"Here is use case {use_case}"
}
```

Listing 4: Final prompt for generating sequence diagram.

Fig. 3: Generated sequence diagram for Listing 3.

correct syntax of more complex naming conventions. In this case, the prompt (see Listing 4) was simpler, as extracting the essential elements of individual steps and subsequently generating the diagram yielded the desired results.

The final dataset contains 8,220 records. There are 1,120 unique sequence diagrams, of which 192 are generated. The dataset contains 8,048 unique use cases, of which 8,028 are generated. We made the dataset publicly available at Github¹.

IV. EVALUATION

After creating the dataset, we performed a spot check on selected records. It was observed that if the original record was incorrectly constructed, the generation process did not correct these errors, thereby supporting the fidelity of the transformation. For example, Fig. 3 depicts an *Environmental Scientist* because it was defined among the use case actors, even though it does not appear in any of the individual steps in Listing 3.

Across the entire dataset, we performed a statistical analysis of its properties. The analysis included, for example, the number of steps in a use case, the number of actors in a use case, alternative scenarios, objects in the sequence diagram, and diagram fragments.

These indicators provide insight into the complexity of individual records and allow the identification of potential shortcomings in the dataset. In addition, correlations between individual attributes were analyzed. The strongest correlation was observed between the number of actors in a use case and the number of objects in the sequence diagram.

Part of the evaluation also involved examining the influence of generation parameters on data quality. Experiments showed that different values of the *temperature* and *top_p* parameters can influence the success rate of generation and the diversity of the resulting records.

Statistics of file origin based on repository analysis showed that 19% of the files come from repositories whose content was generated using LLMs. Part of the created dataset therefore consists of synthetic data.

The usability of the dataset was verified during the evaluation of a tool for transforming a use case into a sequence

¹<https://github.com/JakubMurin/SeqUC-Dataset>

diagram [7]. The tool analyzes individual steps of a use case and generates a sequence diagram based on them. On a sample of one hundred randomly selected records, the transformed sequence diagram was compared with the diagram in the dataset for the same use case.

The experiment showed that the dataset is suitable for testing such tools and enables the identification of cases where the transformation fails or produces inconsistent results.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we addressed the problem of the lack of datasets for research on transformations of software engineering artifacts. We proposed a method for creating a dataset containing pairs of use cases and sequence diagrams. The dataset was created using a combination of data obtained from public repositories and data generated using a large language model.

The proposed pipeline includes data collection, validation, generation of new records, and subsequent statistical analysis of the dataset is available on Github². The results show that the created dataset is suitable for testing tools for automatic transformation of use cases into sequence diagrams.

In the future, this work can be extended in several directions. One possibility is expanding the dataset with a larger amount of real data from open-source projects. Another option is experimenting with different language models or different generation settings to increase the quality and diversity of the data. An interesting research direction is also the automatic validation of generated diagrams and their consistency with textual use cases.

Such datasets can significantly contribute to the advancement of research in the automation of software modeling and enable systematic comparison of different approaches to transforming software development artifacts.

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²<https://github.com/JakubMurin/SoftEn-Datasets>

Concept of Video Inputs Evaluation Metric in Multi-camera Systems

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Abstract - The paper focuses on the concept of a metric for selecting the best shot in a multi-camera system. It analyses the architecture, properties, and challenges of such systems, and describes the most relevant parameters of video stream sources, tracking mechanisms, and supplementary external sensors. Furthermore, it outlines how these parameters can be exploited for computing the most suitable view for a given event or object.

Keywords – concept of best view metric, multi-camera systems, tracking mechanisms, video inputs evaluation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The objective of this publication is to propose a metric for selecting the best shot by evaluating the parameters of video streams and the output values of tracking mechanisms. The article begins with section II, a description of single-camera and multi-camera systems, which are further classified according to the presence of overlapping fields of view. Subsequently, chapter III describes the most relevant parameters of video streams, while section IV analyses the parameters of the audio track and supplementary external sensors. Chapter V focuses on the output parameters of tracking mechanisms. The final chapter VI introduces the concept of a metric design for selecting the optimal shot.

II. MULTI-CAMERA SYSTEMS

Systems composed of two or more cameras that communicate with each other, share captured data or images, or control the motion of devices based on the output from their joint data can be referred to as **multi-camera systems**. Such a system can capture multiple scenes or multiple objects simultaneously, or it can be used to observe a single scene from several viewpoints, thereby ensuring better coverage or an improved view of the target object.

A. Single-camera systems

A system that observes a scene/person/object using only one camera is called a single-camera system. In addition to capturing the scene, camera systems can be extended with the ability to rotate towards the object of interest (or cyclically), to zoom in and out, and to refocus the scene according to the position of the tracked object. An example of three different single-camera systems is shown in Fig. 1.

Camera **A** has a narrow field of view (denoted by line **a**), as it is configured to focus on objects at a greater distance. In contrast, camera **B** covers a substantially wider field of view (denoted by line **b**), because it is configured to observe a closer part of the scene. These configurations may, in fact, correspond to the very same physical device operated under two different parameter settings.

The example with camera **C** illustrates the possibility of rotating the camera with respect to an axis passing through its optical centre (for instance, when it is mounted on a movable

Fig. 1 Three independent single-camera systems

tripod or included pan-tilt mechanism). In its default position, the camera records the view labelled **C**, bounded by line **c**. When the camera is rotated, its field of view changes and it captures a completely different part of the environment. After a 45° rotation to the right, the shifted camera **C'** observes the scene delimited by the dashed line **c'**. After a 90° rotation to the left from its default position, the displaced device **C''** captures the area bounded by the light line **c''**. Consequently, camera **C** can cover an angle greater than 180°.

B. Multi-camera systems without overlapping

Multi-camera systems without overlapping consist of two or more cameras whose fields of view observe the scene, such that no portion of the scene captured by one camera is covered by the field of view of any other camera. Consequently, within the overall observed scene, there is no region that is monitored simultaneously by two or more cameras.

Such a multi-camera system effectively operates as an ensemble of several independent single-camera systems. An object present in the scene cannot be captured by multiple cameras simultaneously; it cannot be observed from different viewpoints at the same moment, and therefore each imaging device can detect the object only independently

Fig. 2 illustrates a system without overlapping. It consists of three cameras (**A**, **B** and **C**), whose fields of view are shown in light grey and labelled with the corresponding letters. There is no location in the scene that is covered by more than one camera. The white areas in the figure represent blind spots that are not visible to any camera.

Fig. 2 Multi-camera system without overlapping

Despite this, a non-overlapping multi-camera system can still acquire data about the observed object from each individual imaging device, transmit this information to a central processing or control unit, and thereby support the localisation or tracking of the object in another camera's field of view. Based on information obtained from one imaging device, the object can subsequently be detected in the remaining devices more unambiguously and/or more rapidly.

C. Simple overlapping multi-camera system

The opposite of non-overlapping configurations are multi-camera systems with overlapping camera fields of view. In such systems, certain regions of the scene lie within the fields of view of two or more cameras. In this case, the same object can be detected and tracked simultaneously by multiple cameras, and it therefore becomes meaningful to select, among these views, the one that is most suitable for that particular object. Recent work also formalizes view recommendation in multi-camera setups by combining objective criteria (e.g., ROI information/visibility cues) to choose the most suitable camera view for a task, which supports the motivation for a best-view metric in overlapping camera system [1].

The topology of cameras with overlapping fields of view can also be diverse. The cameras may be arranged in a single plane and observe the scene under the same viewing angle (as in Fig. 3) or they may be positioned in different planes and at various orientations towards or away from the observed scene.

All three cameras (A, B and C) lie in the same plane and observe the scene under the same angle. The regions marked in light grey and labelled A, B and C are each captured by only a single camera. The darker regions labelled AB and BC indicate areas where selection of the most suitable view can already take place, since there is overlap between pairs of cameras. The darkest region labelled ABC, denotes the area observed by all three cameras and is therefore the most appropriate for validating the best view metric. In this region, all three cameras observe the scene from different angles, making it meaningful to choose the most informative view among them.

D. Advanced overlapping multi-camera system

Fig. 4 shows an example of an advanced multi-camera system with overlapping. The scene contains an obstacle (a

Fig. 3 Simple overlapping multi-camera system

black rectangle with a white fill) that obstructs the view of two cameras, B and C. Their actual fields of view are represented by the solid lines projected from the lenses and by the auxiliary continuous lines: line **b** for camera B and line **c** for camera C. The original, unobstructed fields of view are depicted by the dashed lines **b'** and **c'**. The offset between each pair of lines (**b** and **b'**, **c** and **c'**) corresponds to the reduction in the visible area caused by the obstacle in the scene.

The figure also illustrates an imperfect camera topology design, since part of the field of view of camera A is blocked by camera B. Its actual field of view is indicated by the solid line **a**, while the original one is shown by the dashed line **a'**. The region labelled **A'** therefore lies in a blind spot, even though it could in principle be captured by camera A. In addition, the scene contains regions that are observable only by a single camera (labelled A, B or C), by pairs of cameras (combinations A B, B C and A C), and also by all three cameras (the darkest region A B C). In this way, the figure incorporates all possible combinations of 'competition' for the best view, as well as all relevant topological issues that may arise.

Fig. 4 Advanced overlapping multi-camera system in complex environment

III. ATTRIBUTES OF TRANSMITTED VIDEO

The transmission of video or audio over a network is influenced by a multitude of factors—some determine the visual quality of the resulting video, while others affect the delay between sending and receiving the content, as well as whether the audio remains synchronized with the video.

The objective of any transmitted stream is to deliver the content in the highest possible quality. In an ideal scenario, one could simply follow the principle that “the higher the resolution and the faster the transmission, the better.” In practice, it is necessary to balance and reconcile the different requirements with the constraints present in the transmission environment.

A. Aspect ratio

The most fundamental characteristic of images or video frames, and the one that is visually apparent at first glance, is the aspect ratio (will be referred as V_A). This term denotes the ratio between the number of display elements (pixels) along the height of the frame and the number along its width.

A basic reference aspect ratio can be defined as 1:1. In this configuration, the frame contains an equal number of pixels in both the vertical and horizontal dimensions, resulting in a square image.

A visually similar configuration is the first of the standardized television aspect ratios, namely 4:3, in which the width of the image is moderately greater than its height (for example, 800×600 pixels). In addition, the PAL standard, historically widespread in analog television systems, employed an aspect ratio of 5:4, corresponding, for instance, to the normalized resolution of 720×576 pixels.

Subsequently, these aspect ratios were superseded by so-called widescreen formats, in which the image became progressively more elongated along the horizontal axis. The currently most widely used aspect ratio in the domain of streaming media is 16:9 (for example, 1920×1080 pixels).

This ratio approximates the so-called golden ratio ($\phi \approx 1.618$), which is commonly regarded as one of the most aesthetically pleasing and visually balanced proportions from the standpoint of human visual perception. An aspect ratio that aligns even more closely with the golden ratio is 16:10; however, it has not been adopted as broadly in practice and is used primarily in displays of certain types of notebook computers and mobile devices.

An ultra-widescreen aspect ratio, such as 21:9, is predominantly employed in cinematic productions. In this context, the design is closely related to the characteristics of the human field of view, which is significantly narrower in the vertical direction than in the horizontal one; consequently, the image is maximally “stretched” along the horizontal axis.

Most of these aspect ratios can also be inverted, for example to 9:16, where the height exceeds the width. This configuration is primarily utilized in smartphone displays, which, when held in the hand in their usual orientation, effectively operate with a vertically oriented (portrait) aspect ratio.

B. Video resolution

One of the parameters that is familiar even to laypeople in the field of video streaming is video resolution (V_R). Resolution specifies the number of pixels contained in a single

video frame - it defines the width (will be denoted as R_W) and height (R_H) of an individual “image” within the video, expressed in the fundamental unit of pixels, i.e., discrete picture elements. Standard cable television broadcasting typically uses HD resolution (High Definition). This designation usually corresponds to a resolution of 1280×720 pixels, with a standard aspect ratio of 16:9. In addition to this standard resolution, numerous other formats are in use; for example, the video platform YouTube offers several resolution options for its streamed content.

- 144p – 256×144 pixels

- 360p – 640×360 pixels; today only rarely used due to its relatively low quality

- 480p – 854×480 pixels; a lower-quality resolution typically used under poor network conditions

- 720p – 1280×720 pixels; corresponds to the standard resolution of contemporary television broadcasting

- 1080p – 1920×1080 pixels; also called Full HD, representing a higher standard for video transmission and viewing

- 1440p – 2560×1440 pixels; sometimes referred to as 2.5K, and considered an intermediate step toward higher-end formats

- 2160p – 3840×2160 pixels; commonly known as 4K UHD (Ultra High Definition)

- 4320p – 7680×4320 pixels; commonly known as 8K UHD, currently the highest quality typically offered to end users.

Higher resolutions are typically employed for major television broadcasts, live transmissions, and for the latest films and series. A 4K resolution is four times larger than Full HD—in other words, a single frame of 4K video can accommodate four Full HD frames. The same proportional relationship applies when comparing 8K to 4K. In addition to their use in professional video production, these resolutions are also utilized in the domains of virtual reality and augmented reality.

Devices for Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) present visual content in very close proximity to the user’s eyes. Consequently, the rendered image must be of the highest possible quality in order to appear convincing and to remain comfortable for prolonged viewing. Higher resolutions (in some cases, even more demanding formats such as 16K, i.e. 15360×8640 pixels) are likewise employed for panoramic video, 360° video, and other artistic formats, for example time-lapse videos [2].

In video content delivery, the objective is to provide the highest feasible resolution; however, this is not always technically or economically achievable. For this reason, video quality is often downscaled to lower levels, depending on the available network bandwidth, the characteristics of the video source, and the capabilities of the target display device.

C. Frame rate

To ensure that video is perceived as smooth and continuous rather than as a sequence of static images, it must exceed a certain minimum frame rate; according to [3], this perceptual threshold is approximately 10–12 frames per second. From this limit, standard frame rates used in

cinematography and broadcasting—such as PAL (25 FPS), NTSC (30 FPS), and the conventional cinematic rate (24 FPS)—have historically evolved. Higher frame rates (e.g., 60 or 120 FPS) are typically employed for content with rapid motion, such as sports broadcasts or dynamic scenes, while industrial high-speed cameras used for process monitoring can operate at hundreds or even thousands of frames per second. Owing to this wide operational range, frame rate (this parameter will be denoted as V_f) constitutes one of the fundamental parameters for evaluating the quality and performance of an IP video stream.

D. Bitrate

Bitrate (V_B) is a numerical expression of a video stream's bandwidth requirements. Its magnitude, typically given in bits per seconds (bps) or its multiples, depends primarily on the video codec employed, which can significantly reduce these requirements. For instance, transmitting uncompressed “raw” Full HD video at 60 FPS would require a bandwidth of approximately 3 Gbps. By using the H.264/AVC video codec, the same content can be compressed to about 12 Mbps, with only a negligible loss in perceived quality. This quality can be evaluated using various subjective metrics, as well as objective measures such as PSNR (Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio), which quantifies the attenuation or degradation of the encoded video relative to the original source. However, PSNR correlates only imperfectly with perceived quality under many real-world distortions, and recent surveys summarize modern perceptual and learning-based VQA methods that could be incorporated as additional inputs (or validation tools) for best-view selection under bandwidth/compression constraints [4].

Video standards and applications can be categorized into two groups according to the properties of their data rate: constant bitrate (CBR) and variable bitrate (VBR). In CBR systems, the bitrate remains fixed throughout the entire transmission. Consequently, if network conditions deteriorate, portions of the data may not be delivered in time, leading to playback issues such as stuttering or frame drops. One strategy to mitigate this is to provide multiple parallel streams at different quality levels, allowing the client to switch to a lower-quality stream when network throughput decreases.

In contrast, VBR-based applications can adapt dynamically to changing network conditions. The encoder continuously adjusts the instantaneous bitrate in response to both content complexity and available bandwidth. This adaptability makes it possible to maintain uninterrupted streaming even at reduced network speeds, while still exploiting higher throughput—whenever it is available—to deliver video with superior visual quality.

E. Video streaming latency

End-to-end latency is mainly determined by encoding (codec and settings), transport (“first” and “last” mile, protocol choice), the match between bitrate and available bandwidth, and the size of the playback buffer, which pre-fetches data but adds delay.

Latency is therefore not meaningful in an absolute sense (i.e., the true end-to-end latency from source to destination), but only in a relative sense, obtained by comparing multiple video sources and their mutual temporal offsets. The ideal condition is achieved when all sources under comparison are fully synchronized. Because view-selection metrics may compare streams frame-by-frame, recent work on subframe-level synchronization in multi-camera systems highlights

practical methods to temporally align sources more accurately, improving the reliability of latency-based comparisons across cameras [5]. If such synchronization is not feasible, the fastest source is selected as the temporal reference, and its presentation time defines the origin of the time axis—its delay is, by definition, zero. The latencies of all remaining sources are then expressed relative to this reference time value. The unit of measurement is the millisecond (ms), and this parameter will be referred to as V_L .

IV. ADDITIONAL ATTRIBUTES

In order to further refine the computation of the optimal camera view, the audio track associated with the video stream may also be incorporated into the metric. Selected characteristics of the audio signal can serve as informative indicators for estimating the distance between the observed object and the recording devices. Moreover, the proposed metric can be systematically extended by integrating external sensors that are specifically designed to determine the spatial position of the tracked object with higher accuracy.

A. Audio track attributes

The stream consists not only of a video component, but also of an audio track. The audio track likewise has a set of properties that influence the quality of the resulting sound and the suitability for use by the control system. The most intuitive attribute of sound is its loudness (or volume, will be referred to as A_v and measured in decibels - dB). When the sound level is low and the audio track is barely audible, its importance for the video component is reduced. The opposite situation arises when the audio is “overdriven” or otherwise degraded, for example by hum, noise, or similar types of interference.

Even if the loudness is sufficient, transmitting the audio at a low data rate significantly degrades the resulting sound quality. An important property of the audio signal is therefore the bitrate (A_B , unit is bits per second, Bps) at which the audio track is encoded and transmitted. Closely related to this issue is the number of audio channels (or audio tracks and will be denoted to as A_T), that is, whether the resulting sound is provided as mono, stereo, or in a multi-channel format.

Analogously to video, the transmission of audio signals is likewise affected by latency (A_L , the unit is milliseconds). For the control system, however, the delay relative to the video signal is of primary importance. In the ideal case, the video and audio tracks must be synchronized. If this condition is not met, the relevance of the audio track is significantly reduced, and in some cases it may even become entirely undesirable.

B. Parameters from additional sensors and external detectors

Additional information that can be exploited in the design and computation of the metric is provided by active auxiliary devices. All of these devices supply different types of data, both in terms of their structure and their origin. A gyroscope or accelerometer must be mounted on, or at least in close proximity to the tracked object, whereas GPS coordinates or radar measurements can be obtained remotely, without any direct physical interaction with the object.

By combining gyroscope and accelerometer data, it is possible to determine both the intensity and direction of the object's motion. The gyroscope provides measurements in three axes, which makes it possible to accurately estimate the orientation of the object with respect to Earth's gravity. In

addition, during motion, the gyroscope and accelerometer respond to changes and continuously record the corresponding measurement data.

Another device that can be used to determine the orientation of the object is a compass. It provides the orientation with respect to the cardinal directions. Its output can be expressed as the azimuth, with a left-closed and right-open interval from 0 to 360 degrees.

For global position estimation, a commonly used solution is the Global Positioning System (GPS), which makes it possible to determine the object's location with high accuracy on a worldwide scale. If a GPS signal is not available, the position can be approximated using information from cellular base stations, where the approximate position of the object is computed based on measurements from multiple BTS (Base Transceiver Station) units. In indoor environments this signal may also be unavailable or severely degraded, in which case wireless network coverage can be used. The position can then be estimated by triangulating the signal strength measurements from multiple access points (APs).

From the perspective of local position estimation, for example within a single room, various distance sensors can be used. These include radar, lidar, ultrasonic sensors, and similar devices. With a sufficient number of such sensors, triangulation can be applied to compute the precise distance of the object from the camera. However, this approach requires an unobstructed line of sight to the tracked object.

V. ATTRIBUTES OF TRACKING MECHANISMS

There is a vast number of approaches to object tracking in video. Recent surveys of multi-camera multi-object tracking summarize the modern pipeline (detection, association, re-identification) and the key challenges across camera systems (overlapping and non-overlapping), which supports the need to explicitly model tracking outputs (e.g., confidence and geometry) as inputs to a best-view metric [6]. Different tracking algorithms and types of detection and tracking methods are suitable for different situations, scenes, and environments. In practice, a combination of several methods is often ideal, which, however, comes at the cost of increased computational requirements. Ultimately, most algorithms, whether based on classical computer vision or modern AI techniques, produce similar output parameters that describe the detected object and its position within the camera frame.

A. Position of the detection bounding box

The standard type of output produced by the tracking mechanism is a bounding box. This bounding box indicates the occurrence of the target object within the scene, or more precisely, its boundaries within the image pixel matrix. The detection rectangle is characterized by four attributes:

- width - the number of pixels in the horizontal direction, denoted as T_W
- height - the number of pixels in the vertical direction, denoted as T_H
- X-coordinate - of the top-left corner of the bounding box, referred as T_X
- Y-coordinate - of the top-left corner of the bounding box, referred as T_Y .

For the actual computation of the metric, however, these data must be further processed. To simplify working with the

attributes of the tracking mechanism, it is advisable to compute the center of the bounding box. At the same time, it is necessary to compute the ratio of the detected object size to the image size, in order to normalize the measurements with respect to varying video resolutions in the input data. This parameter will be denoted as O_S .

The final step is to compute the distance between the center of the detected object (calculated in the first step) and the desired position within the frame. This reference position must be chosen according to the current requirements on image composition. This parameter will be denoted as O_D .

For example, when the metric is used to select the most suitable shot for human viewers, a composition based on the golden ratio (as discussed in III.A), or alternatively the rule of thirds, is often appropriate. In contrast, for automatic object tracking intended for further machine processing, a centered composition with the point of interest located exactly in the middle of the image is usually more suitable.

B. Object detection probability

The most important attribute of the tracking mechanism is the resulting probability (T_P). This value typically lies in the range from 0 to 1 and expresses, in a quantitative manner, how confident the mechanism is that it has correctly detected the target object, where a value of 1 corresponds to 100% and 0 corresponds to 0% confidence.

C. Reliability of the tracking mechanism

The last attribute associated with the tracking mechanisms is their reliability (T_R). This value is, however, a largely subjective expression of the metric's trust in a particular tracking mechanism. It is primarily derived from experience gained in previous evaluations and from comparisons with other tracking mechanisms.

This value does not change during the computation of the metric; it remains constant. For the sake of higher objectivity, this attribute may also be completely omitted from the metric calculation.

VI. CONCEPT OF THE BEST VIEW METRIC

Fig. 5 illustrates the concept of a metric for selecting the best view. The metric takes as input a set of attributes derived from multiple sources, each of which can be decomposed into a video component and an audio component. Furthermore, different types of tracking mechanisms can be employed, with their parameters also serving as inputs to the metric. The metric may be further refined by incorporating additional parameters obtained from external sensors, thereby improving the accuracy of its final outcome, namely the identifier of the source that provides the best shot.

The video component contains a vector of visual parameters $P_V = (R_W, R_H, V_F, V_B, V_L)$, where

- R_W and R_H - width and height of video resolution (V_R), which are discussed in more detail in III.B
- V_F - video frame rate (discussed in III.C)
- V_B - bitrate, detailed in III.D
- V_L - the difference in latency between a specific video stream and the fastest received video stream (III.E).

Fig. 5 Concept of the best view metric

The aspect ratio (V_A , section III.A) is excluded from the metric definition, as it is a redundant parameter that can be computed directly from the video width and height.

The audio component contains a vector of audio parameters (all of which was discussed in IV.A) of source $P_A = (A_V, A_B, A_T, A_L)$, where

- A_V - audio volume (or loudness)
- A_B - bitrate of audio track
- A_T - number of audio tracks
- A_L - the difference in latency between video and audio stream.

Tracking mechanisms provide a parameter vector $P_T = (O_D, O_S, T_P, T_R)$, where

- O_D - the distance between the center of the detected object and its desired position within the frame, computed from the X (T_X) and Y (T_Y) coordinates of the top-left corner of the detection bounding box and its resolution, explained in section V.A
- O_S - the ratio of the detected object width (T_W) and height (T_H) to the image size, described in section V.A
- T_P - the resulting probability of tracking mechanism (V.B)
- T_R - constant (subjective) reliability of tracking mechanism (V.C).

The possible additional parameters of the external sensors are discussed in more detail in IV.B. After processing all available parameters, the metric should be able to select the source that provides the best view of the desired situation. In parallel to hand-crafted metric design, learning-based approaches have recently been proposed to select a subset of camera views that preserves task performance while reducing

processing cost, which is conceptually aligned with selecting an optimal view under constraint [7]. In principle, this computation could be performed for every single frame; however, such an approach would be computationally very expensive. A more suitable solution is to aggregate the per-frame metric values over a longer interval, for example over 30 frames or even several seconds, and evaluate these results as a whole.

Another important enhancement would consist in introducing weighting coefficients for all parameters, which would make it possible to adjust their influence on the final metric. This mechanism would be particularly useful in situations where certain parameters need to be excluded from the metric, or, conversely, where their importance in the final result needs to be increased.

VII. CONCLUSION

The primary objective of this article was to develop a basic conceptual framework for a metric enabling the selection of the optimal shot in a multi-camera system. Based on an analysis of potential input parameters derived from the video and audio tracks of the source streams, from tracking mechanisms, and from external sensors, a metric concept was proposed that can be further exploited and refined. Moreover, the present work is intended as a preparatory step towards a future publication that will provide a rigorous mathematical formalisation and in-depth analysis of the proposed metric

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AI-Enabled SBVR Rules Extraction in Insurance

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Abstract—Insurance regulatory documents are normative, exception-heavy, and costly to re-interpret in operations. We present the WP7 knowledge extraction segment of the InnovAIt e pipeline, converting governance text into traceable rule knowledge through SBVR-aligned normalisation and ontology-grounded persistence. The method combines deterministic stages and LLM-driven stages, with Promptfoo-based quality governance and assertion thresholds for structural validity and coverage quality. We report character-span coverage evidence (43.29%–55.19% across chunk configurations) that supports controlled context overlap with deterministic deduplication and source-trace preservation, and we separate evidence-confirmed findings from model-comparison signals. Reported benchmark comparisons are run-level measurements from locked snapshots, not statistical aggregates across repeated independent reruns. The study confirms that automated SBVR-oriented extraction is feasible, but highly sensitive to prompt design, domain context, and modality interpretation. We therefore prioritise semantic precision and operational relevance over raw extraction volume, and treat character-span coverage only as a supporting indicator rather than a proxy for rule-level correctness. Within the broader InnovAIt e roadmap, this segment provides trusted inputs for evidence-grounded polycontext research aimed at empowering claim adjusters.

Index Terms—insurance AI, governance extraction, SBVR, ontology persistence, promptfoo, claims process optimisation

I. INTRODUCTION

Insurance governance texts encode obligations, prohibitions, limits, exclusions, and procedural constraints that directly affect operational decisions. In practice, these sources are distributed across document families, product variants, and publication cycles. Human interpretation remains mandatory, but repeated manual reading introduces cycle-time pressure and consistency risk.

This research paper focuses on a specific WP7 segment: reproducible extraction of governance knowledge into auditable rule artefacts. The resulting rule knowledge is a reusable foundation for downstream insurer processes, focused on claim-assessment preparation; case-level decision evaluation is deferred to later InnovAIt e polycontext research.

The contribution is twofold: repeatable automated SBVR extraction anchored in defined semantics and ontology, and a foundational knowledge layer for later decision support. This is critical in insurance environments, where operational consistency relies on the stable and accurate interpretation of knowledge embedded across diverse regulatory sources.

From a process perspective, this research addresses the disconnect between drafting regulatory documents and applying rules in daily operations. By converting document content into structured rules, the approach aligns requirement interpretation across business, compliance, and IT teams. This

enables insurers to adapt daily workflows more quickly when regulations change.

Methodologically, the paper is anchored in OMG SBVR for rule representation and in the open GIO model for ontology persistence contracts. The evaluation harness uses Promptfoo and deterministic assertion scripts for run-level comparability and replay [3].

A. Related Work Positioning

Prior work relevant to this scope spans four streams. SBVR-oriented extraction from natural-language business text [5]. A complementary SBVR extraction approach [6]. Benchmark-driven legal NLP evaluation [7]. A related COLIEE benchmark study [8]. LLM-supported regulatory formalization [9]. A complementary SBVR transformation study [10]. Insurance-domain claims-oriented NLP/knowledge-processing evidence [11]. This paper positions itself at the intersection of these streams by combining SBVR-aligned rule extraction with ontology-grounded persistence and run-traceable evaluation governance. The differentiator is not a single model choice, but a governed raw-to-revised transformation contract with explicit traceability and confidence-gated revision evidence.

II. SCOPE AND EVIDENCE BOUNDARY

Evidence claims in this paper are restricted to regulatory-source extraction assets and extraction-layer evaluation artefacts. Downstream polycontext composition artefacts are treated as architectural context and excluded from direct benchmark claims.

The governance source universe for this study is organised into four policy ownership groups aligned with project evidence and operating practice.

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF GOVERNANCE SOURCE GROUPS AND ACCESS MODES

Group	Policy source ownership	Availability	Access mode
G1	Global supranational insurance regulations/directives	Public	Standard
G2	National laws, directives, and regulatory instruments	Public	Standard
G3	Insurer-specific product/process public policies	Public	Standard
G4	Internal insurer process/compliance directives	Internal	Restricted

Groups 1–3 are treated as publicly accessible governance sources, while group 4 is treated as restricted internal governance knowledge requiring stricter access-control mode. This classification is consistent with workbook-based source taxonomy and owner-confirmed public/internal split in the project evidence pack.

Under the WP7 Data Management Plan, future deliverables will publish G1–G3-derived *InsuranceCoverage*, *KnowledgeOntology*, and *ComplianceRulesSBVR* datasets with controlled vocabulary and OMG SBVR-compliant representations. Artefacts derived from G4 sources are excluded from public-release packages and remain restricted.

Corpus sizing combines direct G1+G2 PDF page counts and workbook-mapped G3+G4 estimates; totals therefore aggregate two measurement methods.

The processed governance corpus contains no client-level claim or policyholder records; extraction is performed on regulatory/policy texts and therefore follows a governance-document processing posture. In this scope, GDPR compliance is handled as a by-design property of source-type selection.

Language handling is also layered by design. Source policies are predominantly available in Slovak and English variants, which enabled parallel SK/EN pipeline comparisons for extraction quality and coverage. Governed SBVR outputs are normalised into ‘en-US’ in accordance with ontology and SHACL governance constraints, while multilingual source-language evidence remains traceable through the extraction pipeline.

III. METHOD

A. Pipeline Baseline

Fig. 1. Pipeline and evidence-traceability diagram.

Pipeline stage notes:

- 1) The entry point where raw Slovak language PDF documents are introduced into the system environment.
- 2) A step using a proprietary tool to convert PDFs into clean, processable Markdown format (Slovak).
- 3) Utilizes google gemini-2.5-pro to translate Slovak Markdown into English while maintaining structural integrity.
- 4) A deterministic process that breaks down the English Markdown into smaller, manageable text chunks for optimized LLM processing.
- 5) The core extraction phase where gemini-2.5.pro identifies business rules and outputs them in structured JSON (SBVR) format.
- 6) Automated validation engine that enforces “hard facts” for JSON schema and SBVR compliance, and “soft asserts” for document coverage.
- 7) A LLM based step to merge extracted rule arrays and deduplicate entries to ensure a clean knowledge base.
- 8) A deterministic step to merge extracted rule arrays and deduplicate entries to ensure a clean knowledge base.
- 9) Final rules are stored in a PostgreSQL database with bi-temporal versioning, linking each rule to its specific paragraph in the source document.
- 10) The final assessment stage that generates HTML reports on rules quality, coverage, and consistency across the document set.

Translation and extraction are LLM-assisted; chunking, assertion checks, post-processing transformations, and most compliance checks are deterministic.

B. Research Environment

The extraction environment combines Python-based orchestration, Promptfoo-driven evaluation, custom deterministic assertion scripts, and PostgreSQL persistence [3]. Reproducible evaluation evidence is run-centric: each test case is logged in analytics files with run/model/prompt identifiers, along with quality/cost/latency metrics. This environment-level traceability enables the regeneration of aggregate tables without manual reinterpretation.

C. Evaluation Set Disclosure

The Promptfoo evaluation harness for model-comparison runs was executed on a curated gold set of approximately 20–25 product-policy documents (Eval ID 20260306–143718), stratified across document types used in the project evaluation packs. The chunking benchmark in Table II was executed as a controlled single-document run to isolate chunk-configuration effects from document-type variation. Therefore, corpus-scale evidence and harness-scale benchmark evidence are reported as separate claims.

D. Segmentation and Extraction Policy

Segmentation prioritises contextual integrity over isolated sentence slicing. Baseline extraction requires paragraph-level context (or a coherent chapter slice) and preserves full sentence integrity during splits. Chunks smaller than one full sentence are disallowed.

Overlap policy. Production extraction runs use deterministic, controlled, non-zero overlap fixed at 10% by configuration (100/1000, 200/2000, 300/3000, 400/4000, 500/5000, 600/6000, 700/7000, 800/8000), combined with mandatory post-run deduplication and source-trace preservation. The `overlap=0` configuration is used only for ablation or strict cost-minimisation scenarios and is not the default operating mode. Empirical checkpoints for this policy are summarised in Table II.

Empirical basis. In chunking benchmark runs, the coverage-assert score increased from 43.29% (chunk_size=1000, overlap=100) to 55.19% (chunk_size=8000, overlap=800), while total tokens decreased from 140,382 to 78,545 (~44% lower). In this harness, coverage is computed as character-span coverage of the normalised source document, matched from extracted rule-text source fields via fuzzy matching (not as rule-level recall against a human gold-rule count) [4]. These results support a boundary-loss interpretation: controlled overlap preserves cross-boundary normative context and improves recoverable text-span coverage. The operational trade-off is a higher incidence of duplicate candidates, which is addressed by deterministic normalisation and deduplication.

Table II presents selected checkpoints from the full 1000–8000 sweep and shows lower token usage across these checkpoints with a net coverage gain at the 8000/800 setting,

supporting controlled-overlap default operation for extraction runs. In the full segmentation sweep, the 5000/500 configuration produced a zero-rule extraction outcome; this boundary case is retained as negative evidence and indicates non-monotonic sensitivity to chunk-size settings. Final extraction-volume comparison uses the deduplicated total-rule KPI (after cross-chunk duplicate filtering).

TABLE II
SUMMARY OF SEGMENTATION-POLICY EVIDENCE

Metric	Config A	Config B	Config C	Config D	Description
Chunk	1000	2000	3000	8000	Configured maximum segment size (characters).
Overlap	100	200	300	800	Shared context between adjacent segments (characters).
Raw	718	617	506	505	Total SBVR rule candidates parsed from chunk outputs before cross-chunk deduplication.
DupRem	2	0	1	1	Exact duplicate SBVR rule texts removed by global deduplication.
Final	716	617	505	504	Final deduplicated SBVR rule count for the evaluated document (target KPI for extraction output volume).
Tokens	140,382	94,789	87,186	78,545	Total model token consumption measured for the full run.

Deduplication scope note. Deduplication in the current NORMALISE stage removes exact-text duplicates through deterministic text normalisation and comparison. Semantic near-duplicates with different surface forms are not merged in the current pipeline version and may remain in candidate outputs.

For table-driven policy passages, extraction prefers per-risk SBVR rules when grouped rows contain explicit per-risk detail. Group-level fallback is used only if explicit per-risk evidence is absent.

E. SBVR Normalisation and Ontology Persistence

Extracted candidates are normalised into SBVR-compatible formulations across structural and behavioural dimensions. Controlled vocabulary and post-processing rules align outputs with governance and ontology constraints. Terms and fact types map to ontology entities and relations with provenance links to source documents and context anchors.

F. Evaluation Governance

Promptfoo is used for controlled model and prompt comparison under shared tests and threshold gates. Existing packs define hard and soft failure boundaries for structural validity and extraction quality.

G. Schema and Ontology Alignment

To improve semantic portability and auditable persistence, extracted rule objects are mapped to an SBVR-governed intermediate schema and then to ontology-aligned containers.

TABLE III
SUMMARY OF THE EXTRACTION-TO-ONTOLOGY SCHEMA ALIGNMENT

Extraction field	SBVR role	Ontology anchor
rule text	normative statement	governance rule entity
rule modality	modality classification	rule-type taxonomy
risk group	domain context	policy-coverage risk node
source text anchor	evidence anchor	traceability property
source coordinates	provenance coordinates	source-location shape
valid-from field	temporal applicability	policy validity node
rule identifier	persistent identity	ontology individual identifier

The alignment model in Table III is implemented through the project governance and policy-coverage ontology packs and the implementation-team mapping artefacts, and is the basis for preserving both formal rule semantics and source-level auditability.

Fig. 2. GIO mapping schema for extraction-to-ontology persistence.

H. Ontology Persistence and Mapping Contract

TABLE IV
SUMMARY OF ONTOLOGY-PERSISTENCE MAPPING CONTRACT

Mapping aspect	Persistence artifact	Acceptance gate
SBVR term/class mapping	<code>sbvr.vocabulary_terms</code> (typed noun/verb concepts, synonym support)	controlled vocabulary compliance
Rule persistence	<code>sbvr.rules + documents.documents</code> linkage	source-trace complete (doc/page/para/point)
Fact relation materialisation	<code>sbvr.rule_components</code> (subject/verb/object/modality decomposition)	SBVR structure and modality validity
Schema conformance	JSON wrapper and assertion scripts (<code>json_validation_assert.py</code>)	JSON validity = 100% (hard gate)
Temporal and lineage trace	<code>valid_from, valid_to, version, parent_rule_id</code>	reproducible rule lifecycle traceability

Implementation evidence specifies a persistence contract that links SBVR-normalised extraction output to ontology-governed storage with explicit provenance and temporal/version metadata. This contract operationalises auditable ontology persistence and supports deterministic downstream validation.

I. Prompt Variant and Output-Format Evidence

Variant-testing evidence shows that explicit SBVR-oriented prompting improves the quality of formal rule expression compared with generic prompting, while output-format choice

introduces a cost-structure trade-off. JSON output remains the project default for deterministic validation and ontology persistence, although plain-text runs can provide exploratory cost baselines. Evidence also confirms that extraction granularity and modality strategy affect both rule count and traceability; therefore, ambiguity and low-confidence cases are routed through a HITL-informed revision cycle. In revised-generation run REV-20260224-01, 5,689 items were flagged for semantic review, and 12,674 rule texts were revised in the raw-to-revised transition.

TABLE V
SUMMARY OF PROMPT-VARIANT AND OUTPUT-FORMAT FINDINGS

Dimension	Observed signal	Paper policy
Prompt explicitness	SBVR-specific prompting improves formal modality adherence and extraction consistency	keep modality and schema instructions explicit
Output format	JSON improves machine-readability and deterministic post-processing; plain text can reduce token cost in exploratory runs	JSON is the default exchange format
Granularity strategy	Finer entity/risk-level extraction increases traceability and change-impact auditability	prefer per-risk/per-entity extraction when source detail exists
HITL control	Residual ambiguity and legal phrasing edge cases remain in model outputs	escalate ambiguous cases to manual review

J. Reproducibility and Traceability Protocol

The evaluation protocol is run-centric and assertion-centric. Each evaluated case is uniquely identified by run metadata and model/prompt configuration. Raw evaluation outputs retain assertion-by-assertion outcomes (JSON validity, SBVR validation, coverage) and are used to reproduce compact analytics summaries without manual reinterpretation. This protocol supports independent audit and transparent comparison across runs, prompts, and models.

Evaluation protocol disclosure. Reported benchmark values in this paper are tied to locked evaluation snapshots (20260306-143718, 20260306-151621, 20260306-160629, 20260306-162126). Values are presented as run-level measurements from the governed harness profile; they are not statistical aggregates across repeated independent reruns. Consequently, comparative statements are interpreted as evidence-backed engineering signals under fixed settings, not as population-level statistical significance claims.

K. Evaluation Harness Contract (promptfoo)

TABLE VI
SUMMARY OF THE PROMPTFOO EVALUATION-HARNESS CONTRACT

Artifact	Contract fields/expectation	Acceptance role
analytics (csv)	one row per evaluated case; includes run/test/provider/model/prompt identifiers and quality/performance outcomes	reproducible metrics baseline
Raw eval outputs	deterministic replay of assertion outcomes from source case payloads	independent audit replay
Assertion scripts	explicit checks for JSON validity, SBVR conformance, and coverage quality gates	gate enforcement evidence
Run registry	stable run IDs linking scenario packs (basic/chunk/cost/specified) to export artefacts	cross-run comparability

The Promptfoo harness is treated as a formal evaluation contract rather than an ad hoc benchmarking utility. Each evaluated case is expected to preserve row-level traceability from analytics outputs back to the raw evaluation artefacts. The minimal contract requires stable case identifiers, explicit prompt/model provenance, and assertion-level quality outcomes that can be independently replayed.

L. Operational Policies and Quality Gates

Beyond the core extraction flow, the research established a set of operational policies that stabilise output quality and governance compliance across runs. First, quality gates require 100% JSON schema validity and SBVR compliance above 98%, while text coverage below 60% triggers a soft-failure escalation to manual review. Second, normative content in footnotes and cross-page references is extracted under an explicit traceability rule: extract if normative, keep source-page anchors, and escalate ambiguous cases. Third, language governance is layered: SK/EN comparative runs are used for upstream quality checks, but the governed downstream rule layer is normalised to en-US. Fourth, the table-derived extraction context is preserved at the section, row, and cell levels to avoid context loss in structured policy passages. Fifth, extraction distinguishes a raw-to-revised boundary: raw LLM output may be partially non-compliant, while the revised layer is produced via mandatory deterministic post-processing and ontology-alignment controls. HITL-informed post-processing evidence from run REV-20260224-01 records 5,689 semantic-review flags and 12,674 revised rule texts, with unresolved cases explicitly retained and trace-logged. Finally, publication readiness follows a privacy-aware release policy: public dataset deliverables are constrained to G1-G3-derived artefacts, whereas G4-derived artefacts remain restricted.

TABLE VII
SUMMARY OF CURRENT EVIDENCE SNAPSHOT

Group/item	Count	Evidence note
G1-G4 language instances (aggregated)	236	Aggregated operational language-instance baseline: G1+G2 workbook references ('42') + G3+G4 dual-language instances ('194').
Total governance pages G1-G4	3,423	Combined baseline pages: G1+G2 direct PDF pages ('2,944') + G3+G4 mapped pages ('479').
Revised rule rows	35,414	Source-to-revised row parity maintained for the traceability layer.
Dictionary consolidation	5,118 → 4,459	Controlled vocabulary consolidation (-12.88%).

IV. INTERMEDIATE RESULTS

Across 3,423 total pages of processed regulations and directives (G1-G4 baseline), the revised rulebook layer contains 35,414 revised SBVR rule-candidate rows, with source-to-revised row parity for traceability. The revised dictionary has 4,459 rows compared with 5,118 source rows, indicating controlled consolidation.

The comparative model view under shared evaluation settings is summarised in Table VIII. In this table, the *SBVR score (%)* is a continuous quality score, and the *coverage score (%)* is the harness character-span coverage score for the specified benchmark profile.

TABLE VIII
ILLUSTRATIVE MODEL-COMPARISON CONTEXT (NON-EMPIRICAL VALUES)

Model	SBVR score (%)	Coverage score (%)	Latency (s/doc)	Cost (USD/100 docs)
google/gemini-2.5-pro	99.2%	85%	180	12.50
google/gemini-2.5-flash	98.5%	82%	120	8.00
Mistral-Small-3.2-24B-Instruct	98.8%	83%	150	10.50
qwen3-coder-next	99.0%	84%	165	11.00

Table VIII is an illustrative context only. Empirical model-comparison evidence for this study is reported in Table IX.

TABLE IX
SUMMARY OF END-TO-END EVALUATION METRICS FROM PROMPTFOO EVIDENCE PACKS

Scenario	Variant	Rules	Coverage score (%)	SBVR gate	Tokens
SBVR prompt	gemini-2.5-pro	363	60.39%	pass	31,476
SBVR prompt	gemini-flash	619	45.75%	fail	68,651
SBVR prompt	qwen3-coder-next	198	63.98%	pass	19,655
SBVR prompt	Mistral-Small-3.2	149	43.85%	pass	15,358
Chunking sweep	1000/100	716	43.29%	pass	140,382
Chunking sweep	3000/300	505	47.51%	fail	87,186
Chunking sweep	8000/800	504	55.19%	pass	78,545
Format comparison	JSON output	534	62.70%	pass	59,260
Format comparison	Text output	395	16.52%	pass	32,619

A. Raw-to-Revised Transformation Quality

The transformation layer keeps source-to-revised row parity (35,414 to 35,414) across SBVR rule-candidate rows while enforcing controlled-vocabulary normalisation and ontology-governed restructuring in revised artefacts. Row parity is treated as a traceability property, while quality normalisation is evidenced primarily by controlled-vocabulary consolidation and preferred-term enforcement in revised artefacts.

TABLE X
SUMMARY OF RAW-TO-REVISED TRANSFORMATION METRICS

Artifact	Source	Revised	Interpretation
Rule-candidate rows	35,414	35,414	full trace-preserving carry-over
Dictionary rows	5,118	4,459	-12.88% consolidation
Preferred-term rows	5,114	4,459	canonical term tightening
Unique source policy IDs	100		broad policy coverage retained

Observed effects in the revised layer include reduced lexical redundancy, stricter preferred-term usage, and preserved trace anchors for rule-level provenance, which together increase practical auditability for subsequent research and engineering stages.

V. DISCUSSION

Governance-level traceability and ontology alignment provide a stable basis for extracting, normalising, and persisting regulatory rule knowledge. Scope boundaries, language policy, and segmentation principles establish consistent method behaviour across document families.

Compared with purely prompt-centric extraction reports, this study emphasises governed transformation boundaries (raw-to-revised), deterministic assertion gates, and ontology-persistence contracts as first-class method components. The contribution combines model selection with controlled conversion of regulatory text into reusable, auditable rule knowledge aligned with SBVR constraints [1]. The ontology-persistence layer is aligned with GIO constraints [2].

Even with this constrained scope, the method addresses a practical claims-operations constraint: repeated interpretation of large governance corpora. The proposed approach does not replace professional judgment; it reduces repetitive interpretation load and improves audit-ready traceability.

VI. THREATS TO VALIDITY

Internal validity. The published benchmark comparisons are based on locked run snapshots under fixed settings, not on repeated stochastic reruns with reported variance intervals per model/document pair. Although deterministic controls reduce operational variance, single-run reporting remains a methodological boundary. Recent studies indicate that LLM outputs can vary even at temperature = 0 [12]. Independent evidence confirms this non-determinism under nominally deterministic settings [13]. Future work should therefore report inter-run variance from at least five independent reruns per model/document pair to provide confidence intervals for key metrics.

Construct validity. Character-span coverage is a retrieval-proxy metric and is not equivalent to rule-level recall against a human-annotated gold-rule count. SBVR assertion checks in the reported harness are primarily structural/syntactic gates and should not be interpreted as full semantic correctness guarantees.

External validity. The evidence profile is insurance-domain specific, with jurisdiction- and source-taxonomy constraints. Generalisation to other regulatory domains, jurisdictions, or document architectures requires separate validation.

Conclusion validity. Corpus-scale figures and evaluation-harness figures describe different evidence scopes. Corpus totals combine direct and derived measurements; harness tables report controlled benchmark subsets. The reported 35,414 SBVR rule-candidate rows represent structurally validated extraction outputs (JSON schema + SBVR modality checks), not SME-confirmed semantic correctness at scale; approximately 9.5% fail automated compliance checks and are treated as a bounded methodological limitation. Claims are therefore limited to the stated extraction and revision scope.

VII. INNOVAITE IMPACT PATHWAY

The resulting rule-knowledge layer is designed as a reusable foundation for downstream insurer-process support. In the InnoVAite programme, this is intended to enable the next research stage focused on evidence-grounded polycontext construction for claim-adjuster empowerment, while preserving end-to-end traceability from source governance text to structured SBVR-aligned knowledge objects.

VIII. OPERATIONAL INTEGRATION PERSPECTIVE

The extraction-to-persistence method is intentionally aligned with practical integration patterns for insurer processes. It is designed to support claim-assessment preparation by exposing traceable rule artefacts that can be linked to evidence packages and decision-context construction layers. It also supports insurer operational readiness by

making regulatory conditions available in a structured, auditable format and by reducing the need for repeated manual interpretation in claim-assessment workflows.

From an engineering perspective, the method combines deterministic controls and LLM-assisted transformation to enable repeatable processing and transparent review. Deterministic segmentation, normalisation, and post-processing steps stabilise the output structure, while LLM stages extract semantics from complex regulatory text. This hybrid pattern is particularly relevant in insurance, where normative language, exceptions, and cross-document dependencies require both semantic flexibility and strict governance controls.

From a governance perspective, SBVR-aligned representation and ontology persistence improve interoperability across research and implementation teams. Structured rule objects can be inspected, mapped, and reused in downstream pipelines without losing source anchoring. SBVR and GIO support consistent collaboration between business architecture, analysis, and implementation roles, and help maintain continuity between research artefacts and later operational decision-support prototypes.

Finally, the method strengthens explainability for human-in-the-loop (HITL) usage. By preserving traceability from extracted rules to source text anchors and ontology-bound concepts, the approach provides a clearer basis for expert validation, challenge, and refinement. HITL is essential for high-stakes insurance domains, where system outputs must remain inspectable and defensible for both internal governance and external regulatory expectations.

We execute HITL-informed semantic-review flags and revision outcomes during the research, but a per-item adjudication ledger with reviewer identity and timestamped decision records would be expected in a real production environment.

IX. CONCLUSION

This manuscript presents an AI-based approach for extracting insurance regulatory rules. It relies on SBVR normalisation and ontology-based persistence. Our primary contribution is a practical, auditable extraction method. It transforms complex regulatory text into reusable rule knowledge. These extracted rules align strictly with governance constraints. Ultimately, this work provides a solid foundation for future research in insurer decision-support systems.

Practical Implications. For practical deployment, the primary objective is not to maximise the number of extracted statements, but to maximise the number of modality-correct, context-relevant SBVR candidates. The evidence indicates that extraction quality is strongly dependent on prompt specificity and explicit modality guidance, especially when a single source sentence can generate multiple formally valid but operationally divergent SBVR variants. Accordingly, robust extraction pipelines should enforce constrained structured outputs (e.g., JSON), apply modality-focused validation, and combine automated checks with targeted human review for high-impact ambiguity cases.

SOFTWARE AND LICENSE ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research workflow used the following software components: PyMuPDF v1.27.1 (AGPL-3.0) for PDF-to-markdown conversion, promptfoo v0.121.2 (MIT) for evaluation orchestration, RapidFuzz v3.14.3 (MIT) for fuzzy matching in coverage computation, and PostgreSQL 16+ (PostgreSQL License) for persistence.

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Searching for possibilities to use topological sorting in the refactoring process

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Abstract—Refactoring is an important and useful practice in software development, essential for ensuring system stability, reliability, and readability, as well as long-term maintenance. With the development of large language models (LLMs), many opportunities have emerged to ease the labor-intensive process of refactoring for developers. LLMs show significant potential for performing various code-related tasks, including refactoring, providing fast and fairly accurate results, thereby accelerating and improving the automated refactoring process. We present an approach to automatically refactor Java projects by detecting code smells, finding the optimal sequence of refactoring, performing refactoring using LLM, and verifying the results.

Index Terms—LLM, RAG, refactoring, topological sorting, code smell

I. INTRODUCTION

Code smells are violations of code design that lead to bugs, difficulties with further support and development of the system, and complicate the readability and comprehension of the code by developers [1]. This paper will consider some of the code smells presented in [1], with their meaning as defined there. The presence of code smells in a project does not indicate a bug, but rather a signal of flaws in the code architecture. To eliminate smells, various refactoring techniques are used, commonly referred to as refactoring. Refactoring is the process of improving the structure of code without changing its behavior [1]. However, since they are not actual errors, developers are reluctant to use smell-elimination techniques, since even a seemingly minor change in code carries the risk of breaking the system’s behavior, not to mention changes that require a revision of most of the project’s code architecture. In addition, before refactoring, the changed code should be covered with tests. Such tests will serve as a guarantee that the code’s behavior has not changed after refactoring. However, not every project has good test coverage from the start, and therefore the refactoring process requires additional effort to

prepare tests. Thus, it can be seen that refactoring is a task that requires significant time, effort, focus, and attention from developers.

However, with the development of LLM, this refactoring process has become easier. LLMs, trained on code and natural language, can not only generate code quite successfully but also explain it. This often helps developers and speeds up the workflow. There are also LLM-based assistants integrated into IDEs that can successfully perform refactoring directly, but require human validation. This approach, of course, ensures the safety of changes, but lacks automation. Now, it is possible to build LLM-augmented pipelines that can automate some processes through the access to tools and quick code generation with LLM. Although some studies highlight the benefit of retaining the involvement of a human expert, there are also prerequisites for the successful automation of small processes, thereby reducing manual effort. Therefore, we present an approach to automating the refactoring of local smells using LLM, which will help relieve the burden of refactoring from developers and improve the maintainability and readability of code.

II. RELATED WORKS

Refactoring is a widespread problem, and many papers have explored new solutions and approaches in this area. In this section, we will consider only those papers whose approaches are most similar to those presented in this paper. A key component of this work is the use of LLMs, which have become the subject of numerous studies in recent years and are often applied to various problems and tasks. We will examine their application to the specific task of code refactoring. Furthermore, not only LLMs but also LLM-based agents are now being used, which not only generate refactored code but can also work with it. Some studies evaluate the use of LLM for code refactoring, examine how well LLM performs based on various criteria and the potential of this approach [2], [3], [4]. A similar approach to assessing refactoring capability, but for agents, examines the actual refactorings performed

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by different agents and compares them with developers [5]. There are also proposals for approaches to integrating LLM into the refactoring process, which not only evaluate LLM’s capabilities and abilities but also offer specific usage ideas [6], [7]. All of them point to this area of research as having great potential and the possibility to simplify the refactoring process. They also emphasize that the use of a well-written prompt can improve results. However, the lack of validation for refactoring through running tests also prevents a full assessment of its success.

Some [8], [9] provide automated refactoring plugin and pipeline that use LLM. They produce fairly good refactoring results, although they are limited to a single refactoring technique. However, this is not a drawback; it merely proves that, when used correctly and with a narrow and clearly defined task, LLM produces successful results.

There is also an approach using a LLM-based agent solution and a multi-agent framework [10], [11], which is perhaps the most advanced. This solves the problem of the need for human evaluation, as intelligent agents can make decisions, provide expert opinion, and apply various tools to achieve goals. This is a major advantage when creating an automated system.

III. OUR APPROACH

In this section, we’ll examine the presented approach and each of its components in detail. A schematic representation is shown in Fig. 1. A total of five components are involved in solving the complex refactoring task: the test check component checks the project for sufficient test coverage, the code smell detection component identifies code smells in the project, the distribution component finds the optimal sequence for refactoring code smells, the refactoring component generates refactored code, and the validation component verifies the compilation and test passing of the refactored code.

Fig. 1: Components Flow

A. Tests Check Component

An important step before starting refactoring is checking whether tests exist or have been written, as it’s important to verify that the refactoring hasn’t changed the program’s behavior. To do this, we analyze whether test coverage is sufficient, and if not, we use a tool to automatically generate Java tests. The entire workflow for this component is shown in Fig. 2. Although our approach includes test generation, this task is not so simple, and its specific implementation will be developed in the future.

B. Code Smell Detection Component

The main goal of this component is to identify code smells in a project and extract code containing them. However, we have reduced the number of identified smells to 8, namely: Long Method, Large Class, Long Parameter List, Switch Statement, Data Clumps, Temporary Field, Speculative Generality, Duplicated Code.

In this work, we will use the SonarQube static analysis tool to detect code smells [12]. This tool uses specific rules to identify problems in the code, which help pinpoint the exact problem, which is important for refactoring, while manual smell detection is more complex. But a single code smell may correspond to multiple SonarQube rules.

It is also worth considering that this tool cannot adequately identify semantic smells. Based on the corresponding rules, one can only vaguely assume that the code contains such a smell, or, in the worst case, makes it impossible to draw any conclusions about the smell’s presence. For such cases, an algorithm will be added to confirm the presence of a code smell in the project.

C. Distribution Component

In this section, we identify and formulate two problems based on smells, their relationships, and their impact on the project.

Large projects consist of numerous files with classes, some of which are susceptible to code smells. Some of these classes may be highly coupled, meaning that the slightest change will affect multiple locations. However, other classes are isolated, and their changes will not trigger a chain of changes. Following this line of thought, we propose that it’s safer to introduce changes to a project by starting with less-coupled classes and gradually moving toward more-coupled ones. To determine this sequence, the coupling of each class is estimated and sorted by this value.

In large projects with numerous code smells, they are often intertwined, and refactoring one smell can influence another. In the thesis [13], building on the work of [1], patterns of how refactoring affects smells are derived. And were identified positive and negative dependencies between smells and were constructed graphs of these dependencies. The positive dependency graph indicated that refactoring one smell could positively impact another smell. The negative dependency graph indicated that refactoring one smell could negatively impact another smell. Based on these two graphs, an algorithm was developed to find the optimal sequence of refactorings within a single class.

Let us construct a combined graph from the graphs of positive and negative dependence, where:

- Vertex - code smell
- Directed edge - the impact of refactoring one smell on another

As a result, we obtained a dependency graph displaying positive and negative dependencies at once, presented in Fig. 3

Fig. 2: Tests Check Component

Fig. 3: Code smells dependency graph

Fig. 4: Refactoring order preference graph

Here:

- The green directed edge labeled "solve" indicates a positive dependency.
- The red directed edge labeled "cause" indicates a negative dependency.
- The yellow directed edge labeled "solve/cause" indicates an unspecified dependency.

Now let's create a refactoring order preference graph. To do this, based on each dependency type, denoted by an edge between two nodes, we define a rule for interpreting influences to determine the order of refactoring these two nodes. Of course, this way we can't define a strict order, but we can define a recommended order to increase the number of successful refactorings and reduce the risk of smell recurrence.

In total, we have three types of dependencies between two nodes: positive, negative, and unspecified. For each of them, we need to define a rule that will determine the order. That is, which of the two nodes (smells) connected by an edge do we want to select (refactor) first? To do this, we need to determine the direction of the arrow on the edge between these nodes.

Rules:

- For a positive dependency between nodes u and v ($u \xrightarrow{\text{solve}} v$), we define that if there is a possibility of a positive influence of refactoring smell u on smell v ,

then it is preferable to refactor u before v . This means that the edge is directed $u \rightarrow v$.

- For a negative dependency between nodes u and v ($u \xrightarrow{\text{cause}} v$), we define that if there is a possibility that refactoring smell u will negatively impact smell v , then it is preferable to refactor u before v . However, if we refactor v before u , we risk creating the smell v again. Therefore, the edge is directed $u \rightarrow v$.
- For an unspecified dependency between nodes u and v ($u \xrightarrow{\text{solve/cause}} v$), we define that if there is a possibility that refactoring smell u will have a negative or positive impact on smell v , we consider the negative possibility to be more important. Therefore, u should be refactored before v . This means the edge is directed $u \rightarrow v$.

According to these rules, we redraw the graph. New graph presented in Fig. 4

In reality, the directions of the edges haven't changed, but we've clearly defined the refactoring sequence.

Next, we'll find and merge cycles in the graph into a single node. Since smells influence each other, they should be refactored together. And finally, we'll apply topological sorting, which will yield a sequence of refactorings.

We obtain several possible sequences of refactorings. An evaluation algorithm was developed to find the most suitable sequence. We will evaluate it based on two parameters:

- 1) Distance Score - Estimates whether there are smells with positive influence nearby.
If there exists $u \xrightarrow{\text{solve}} v$, then

$$d = \text{position}[v] - \text{position}[u]$$

$$\text{distance_score} = \text{distance_score} + \frac{1}{d}$$

- 2) Vertex Score - Estimates whether smells with greater positive impact appear earlier.

$$W[v] = \text{out_degree_pos}[v] - \text{out_degree_neg}[v]$$

$$\text{vertex_score} = \text{vertex_score} + \frac{W[v]}{\text{position}[v]}$$

We normalize each and add them together; as a result, we select the sequence with the highest score.

Algorithm 1 Finding optimal refactoring sequence

- 1: $G \leftarrow \text{CreateGraph}()$
 - 2: $\text{SCCs} \leftarrow \text{ComputeSCC}(G)$
 - 3: $G' \leftarrow \text{CondenseGraph}(G, \text{SCCs})$
 - 4: $\text{Orders} \leftarrow \text{AllTopologicalSorts}(G')$
 - 5: **for** each order in Orders **do**
 - 6: compute distance score d
 - 7: compute vertex score v
 - 8: **end for**
 - 9: normalize scores
 - 10: **for** each order **do**
 - 11: $\text{score} = d_{\text{norm}} + v_{\text{norm}}$
 - 12: **end for**
 - 13: return order with maximum score
-

In Table. I are some examples of the resulting refactoring sequences and their evaluation.

TABLE I: An example of several possible refactoring sequences and their score

Step	Sequence 1	Sequence 2	Sequence 3
1	Speculative Generality	Duplicated Code	Speculative Generality
2	Switch Statement	Switch Statement	Duplicated Code
3	Duplicated Code	Speculative Generality	Switch Statement
4	Long Method	Long Method	Long Method
5	Long Parameter List	Long Parameter List	Long Parameter List
6	Temporary Field	Temporary Field	Temporary Field
7	Large Class + Data Clumps	Large Class + Data Clumps	Large Class + Data Clumps
Score	1.8562	1.8562	1.8544

D. Refactoring Component

The purpose of this component is to generate correct and useful refactoring suggestions for a given smell. To achieve an optimal response, it's crucial to formulate the prompt correctly, provide sufficient context without overloading the model with data, and include valid examples for the model to rely on.

1) *Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)*: Research shows that LLMs are often prone to hallucinations. Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) will be used to improve their responses. RAG is an approach that extracts relevant external data and uses it to generate responses, thereby improving them. It is also important to create a detailed and clear prompt that includes examples for context. These examples will include code before and after refactoring.

A detailed diagram of how RAG works can be seen in Fig. 5. The challenge lies in finding the most relevant example from the database. By relevant, we mean that the example should be similar to the source code both structurally and semantically, although structural similarity will be weighted slightly higher. For this purpose, two databases were prepared: one containing code examples "before" refactoring, and the other containing the same "before" code examples, but with the structure extracted. Ten semantically similar "before" code examples are extracted from the first database, and ten structurally similar ones from the second database. An algorithm is then applied to select the optimal one from these examples.

The Listing. 1 shows an example of code containing a long method code smell before refactoring from the dataset [14] available on Zenodo. The dataset is distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license. The code was shortened for readability. The Listing. 2 shows the code from the Listing. 1 after refactoring using the Extract Method refactoring technique performed by LLM using RAG. The code was also shortened for readability. These two listings show what the examples before and after refactoring look like.

Listing 1: Before Refactoring

```

public int readBits(int numBits) {
    // Initial validation and variable initialization
    ...

    // Read as many whole bytes as we can.
    int wholeBytes = (numBits / 8);
    for (int i = 0; i < wholeBytes; i++) {
        int byteValue;
        if (bitOffset != 0) {
            byteValue = ((data[byteOffset] & 0xFF) << bitOffset
                | ((data[byteOffset + 1] & 0xFF) >>> (8 -
                bitOffset)));
        } else {
            byteValue = data[byteOffset];
        }
        numBits -= 8;
        returnValue |= (byteValue & 0xFF) << numBits;
        byteOffset++;
    }

    // Read any remaining bits.
    ...

    assertValidOffset();
    return returnValue;
}

```


Fig. 5: RAG construction

Listing 2: After Refactoring

```

public int readBits(int numBits) {
    // Initial validation and variable initialization
    ...

    int wholeBytes = numBits / 8;

    // Extracted method for reading whole bytes
    returnValue = readWholeBytes(wholeBytes, numBits,
        ↪ returnValue);
    numBits -= 8 * wholeBytes;

    // Read any remaining bits.
    ...

    assertValidOffset();
    return returnValue;
}

private int readWholeBytes(int wholeBytes, int numBits, int
    ↪ returnValue) {
    for (int i = 0; i < wholeBytes; i++) {
        int byteValue = getByteValue();
        numBits -= 8;
        returnValue |= (byteValue & 0xFF) << numBits;
        byteOffset++;
    }
    return returnValue;
}

private int getByteValue() {
    if (bitOffset != 0) {
        return ((data[byteOffset] & 0xFF) << bitOffset)
            | ((data[byteOffset + 1] & 0xFF) >>> (8 -
        ↪ bitOffset));
    } else {
        return data[byteOffset];
    }
}

```

2) *Prompt Construction and LLM Generation* : The prompt composition is crucial, as the quality of the LLM response depends on its detail. We'll use the one-shot prompting technique, adding a hint with an example of successful refactoring of similar code by developers. This will provide a clue on how to refactor smelly code snippets. This technique has been frequently used in research and has led to good results. There are two prompts: a system prompt and a user prompt. The system prompt defines the role of the model, provides clear instructions, and specifies the desired response. The user prompt contains smelly code snippet, code smell and an example of successful refactoring. According to research, this type of prompt composition is the standard and helps improve generation results.

E. Validation Component

Since refactoring shouldn't change the behavior of the code, testing the new code with tests is an important and necessary step; otherwise, its completeness cannot be judged. Code compilation testing is also necessary; although LLM produces good results in code generation, it is not immune to errors. The purpose of this component is to check whether the code passes compilation and tests. Its process is shown in Fig. 6.

The generated refactored code first undergoes compilation checks, then tests. If an error occurs at one of these stages, LLM is given one attempt to correct the code, taking that error into account. If the fix is unsuccessful and the code still fails one of these stages, the code is reverted to the version before refactoring.

IV. RESUME AND FUTURE WORK

Despite the work done, there is still room for improvement in this system.

This paper only presented the automated code refactoring approach, but has not yet conducted an evaluation, so it is likely that some components and algorithms will be further modified to improve the results. These include the code smell detection component, where auxiliary algorithms for identifying certain smells will be refined. Also, for the test checking component, the approach for generating new tests will be refined. And in the RAG approach, the evaluation algorithm for identifying the optimal example will be refined. And finally, the algorithm for evaluating refactoring sequences in the refactoring distribution component, which currently scores several sequences equally, is being refined.

Extensions may also affect the number of supported languages and code smells. Currently, the approach provides refactoring for eight code smells in Java. But in the future, it could support refactoring these eight smells for multiple programming languages or even expand the base of supported smells.

Fig. 6: Validation Component

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Agentic AI in the SDLC: A Prelude to Automated Refactoring

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Abstract—Most LLM-based refactoring tools still address code smells independently, although smells often co-occur and interact. We present a multi-agent pipeline that combines SonarQube-based detection, dependency-aware planning, and LLM-based patch generation. The method plans refactorings before generating edits, using positive and negative dependencies between smell-removal operations.

Index Terms—code smells, refactoring, large language models, multi-agent systems, software maintenance

I. INTRODUCTION

Code smells complicate comprehension and maintenance [1]. Because several smells often appear in the same class, refactoring decisions are not independent [2]. A change that removes one smell can also remove another one, but it may also create a new problem if executed too early. We therefore frame automated smell removal as a planning task, not only as code generation.

II. RELATED WORK

Prior studies established that code smells are widespread and that their accumulation harms maintainability and program comprehension [2]. Cedrim et al. [3] showed that many refactorings fail to reduce smells and some even introduce new ones, which suggests that execution order matters. Markovič and Polášek described positive and negative dependencies between smell-removal operations [4]. Their rules highlight that some negative effects depend on the current structure of the class, not only on the smell type being removed. Recent LLM-based systems such as iSMELL support smell detection and repair, but they do not explicitly plan around inter-smell dependencies [5].

III. OUR APPROACH

The pipeline combines several agents. Preparation agents inspect the repository, identify the build system, and establish

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a test baseline. A detection agent queries SonarQube and converts issues into supported smell types.

A planning agent builds a directed dependency graph over the detected smells. Positive edges denote cases where refactoring smell A may also remove smell B ; negative edges capture cases where resolving A may introduce B . Best-First Search then explores alternative repair orders to minimise the total remaining smell severity.

After planning, an LLM-based refactoring agent applies the selected transformations. Each patch is validated by tests, and a failed step can trigger rollback and replanning. This separation lets symbolic search control sequencing while the LLM focuses on producing edits.

IV. FUTURE WORK

The consequent full article will include a detailed evaluation of the refactoring process, capturing multiple code quality metrics before and after individual repair steps. A labelled dataset of multi-smell Java classes reconstructed from Refactoring-Miner 2.0 and SWE-Refactor would enable broader evaluation on developer-committed refactoring sequences, using metrics such as plan efficiency, introduced-smell rate, and compile-and-test success after LLM-generated patches.

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Animated UML as a gateway to understanding software design patterns

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Abstract—Understanding the relationship between structure and runtime behaviour is a key challenge in software engineering education. Standard teaching relies on static UML diagrams, which fail to capture runtime execution. This paper introduces an approach that enhances class diagrams with behavioural information to make them executable models. By providing real-time visual feedback on method invocations and object interactions, this approach aims to foster more accurate mental models and to reduce cognitive load when analysing software behaviour.

Index Terms—Software comprehension, design patterns, executable UML, AnimArch

I. BACKGROUND

The ability to comprehend software is not merely about reading code; it requires an in-depth understanding of how various components coordinate their behaviour to achieve system goals. Despite their ubiquity, UML class diagrams remain static, failing to depict the sequence of method calls or the lifespan of objects. Research shows that static materials can create a gap between design and implementation [1]. Existing tools support diagrams and pattern identification but rarely show execution [2]. Approaches such as xUML [3] and AnimArch [4] address this issue by shifting the focus from 'dead' documentation to 'living' models that react and evolve visually as the underlying logic executes.

II. OUR APPROACH

Our approach is based on the AnimArch tool [4], which integrates UML class diagrams with executable models. Behavioural logic is defined in a simplified object action language (OAL) and executed step by step. The simulation begins at a selected entry point, where OAL is transformed into an executable structure. As the system processes each command, AnimArch dynamically highlights the relevant classes and their associations within the diagram. This allows users to observe which parts of the system are active at any moment.

We prepared examples of selected patterns (Observer, Builder, Bridge). Our Interpreter implementation (Fig. 1) shows how a recursive object hierarchy navigates grammatical rules, making backtracking and depth-first traversal visible.

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Fig. 1. Class diagram of Interpreter pattern example

III. FUTURE WORK

The next stage of our research will involve empirical validation with students on a software architecture course. Using a cross-over experimental design, we will compare traditional instruction based on static UML diagrams with animation-supported teaching using AnimArch. We anticipate that introducing animated execution flows will reduce the cognitive burden on students when they have to simulate code behaviour mentally [5]. Our aim is to show that interactive visuals support more accurate mental models of object-oriented collaboration. Beyond this initial study, we plan to expand the range of available patterns and investigate how these executable models can facilitate understanding of large-scale, unfamiliar software architectures.

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Towards Test Generation via Collaborative AI Agents and Knowledge Graphs

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Abstract—Automated software testing of complex systems remains a challenging task. This work introduces a novel framework for generating unit tests using a coordinated set of intelligent agents enhanced with retrieval-augmented techniques. Instead of relying on a single large language model, the proposed solution distributes responsibilities across multiple specialized agents that collaboratively analyze source code, extract structural knowledge, and iteratively refine test cases. A graph-based representation of the system under test is constructed to capture relationships between components, enabling more informed reasoning during test generation. The framework prioritizes efficiency and data privacy by utilizing locally deployed language models. This paper outlines the core ideas and positions them as a foundation for further exploration.

Index Terms—Large Language Models; Automated Testing; Multi-Agent Systems; Test Generation; Software Engineering

I. BACKGROUND

As software systems grow in scale and complexity, the need for reliable and efficient testing becomes increasingly critical. Manual test creation is labor-intensive and often fails to keep pace with rapid development cycles. Recent advances in large language models have opened new possibilities for automating this process, particularly due to their ability to interpret and generate source code. However, these models frequently struggle with producing tests that are both logically sound and contextually accurate, especially when dealing with large codebases. To address this issue, we propose a system that shifts from monolithic model usage toward more structured and context-aware methodologies.

Traditional approaches to automated test generation include search-based techniques, such as EvoSuite [1], an evolutionary algorithms, which aims to optimize test coverage through iterative refinement. More recently, language model-driven solutions have been explored, such as Aster [2], AgonTest [3] and Diffblue [4], that leverage the natural language understanding and code generation capabilities of frontier models.

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These approaches demonstrate promising results in generating syntactically correct tests but often fall short in terms of correctness, completeness, and maintainability.

II. OUR APPROACH

The proposed framework adopts a multi-agent architecture in which each agent is responsible for a specific subtask within the test generation pipeline. These tasks include extracting dependencies, generating test cases, and validating outputs. The agents operate over a shared state, allowing them to incrementally build and refine their understanding of the system. To enhance contextual awareness, a knowledge graph is constructed from the analyzed codebase, capturing relationships between classes, methods, and modules.

III. FUTURE WORK

Future research will focus on expanding the capabilities of the framework to handle larger and more diverse codebases, as well as improving the quality and coverage of generated tests. Additional evaluation metrics will be introduced to better assess correctness and usability in real-world scenarios. Further exploration of advanced retrieval mechanisms is also planned. Ultimately, the goal is to develop a robust and scalable solution that can be integrated into modern software development workflows.

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Enhancing knowledge-based semantic similarity methods for Slovak

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Abstract—Knowledge-based methods for semantic textual similarity offer cost-effective and interpretable alternatives to neural approaches when suitable lexical resources are available. We present a knowledge-based approach for computing sentence-level semantic similarity in Slovak that dynamically constructs semantic trees from sentence lemmas and applies the Wu–Palmer similarity measure with best-match aggregation. Our method achieved a Pearson correlation of $r = 0.3094$ with human annotations, outperforming $r = 0.237$ achieved by Wu–Palmer with Slovak WordNet in previous works.

Index Terms—semantic textual similarity, knowledge-based methods, conceptual dictionary, Wu–Palmer similarity, natural language processing

I. METHODOLOGY

Our approach transforms input sentences into semantic representations through a multi-stage pipeline. First, we extract lemmas from input sentences and retrieve their associated concepts from the Slovak Conceptual Dictionary [1] via its public API¹. Unlike traditional methods that rely on static taxonomies, we dynamically construct a semantic tree structure for each sentence pair, containing only concepts relevant to the compared sentences. This focused approach reduces computational complexity while maintaining semantic expressiveness.

Semantic similarity between individual concepts is computed using the Wu–Palmer similarity measure [2], which evaluates semantic closeness based on the depth of concepts and their closest shared ancestor (Least Common Subsumer) in the hierarchical structure. The final sentence similarity score is obtained through a best-match aggregation strategy, formalized as:

$$\text{sim}(S_1, S_2) = \text{Avg}_{w_1 \in L_1} \left[\text{Max}_{w_2 \in L_2} \text{WuPalmer}(w_1, w_2, T) \right]$$

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¹<https://pojmy.kinit.sk/concepts>

where L_1 and L_2 are the sequences of lemmas from sentences S_1 and S_2 , T is the dynamically constructed semantic tree, and $\text{WuPalmer}(w_1, w_2, T)$ computes concept similarity based on hierarchical relations. This strategy identifies the best matching concept from the second sentence for each concept in the first sentence, then averages these maximum similarities.

II. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

We evaluated our approach on a subset of the Slovak SICK dataset (SICK-SK) [3] containing 7,569 sentence pairs. Our method achieved a Pearson correlation of $r = 0.3094$, outperforming Wu–Palmer similarity used with standard Slovak WordNet which achieves only $r = 0.237$ on the same dataset [4]. This indicates potential in leveraging structured conceptual dictionaries can enhance semantic similarity computation for Slovak language processing.

III. FUTURE WORK

Future work will address current limitations by incorporating additional semantic relations from the conceptual dictionary, exploring alternative aggregation strategies that better capture compositional semantics, and investigating hybrid approaches that combine knowledge-based methods with large language models for enhanced tree construction and similarity computation.

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